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List of abbreviations

18F-FP-CIT PET	18F-fluorinated N-3-fluoropropyl-2-beta-carboxymethoxy-3-beta-(4-iodophenyl) nortropane (18F-FP-CIT) positron emission tomography (PET)
ADL	Activities of daily living
aHR	Adjusted hazard ratio
AI	Artificial intelligence
ALC	Acute Levodopa Challenge
AMP-PD	Accelerating Medicines Partnership: Parkinson's Disease
AUC	Area Under the Curve
AUC	Area Under the Curve
AUPRS	Area Under the Precision Recall Curve
AUPRS	Area Under the Precision Recall Curve
BDI	Beck Depression Inventory
BIDI-II	Beck Depression Inventory II
BJLOT	Benton Judgment of Line Orientation Test
BMI	Body mass index
BN	Bayesian network
C	Clinical
CDR SB	Clinical dementia rating sum of boxes
CE-mark	Conformité Européenne
CF	Chronic Treated
CI	Coefficient interval
COURAGE-PD	Comprehensive Unbiased Risk Factor Assessment for Genetics and Environment in Parkinson's
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
CV	Cross Validation
D	Demographic
DA	Dopamine agonists
DAT	Dopamine transporter (DAT) imaging
DL	Deep learning
DDS	Dopamine-dysregulation syndrome
DF	Drug Free
DIGPD	Drug Interaction with Genes in Parkinson's Disease
DMLF	Dense Multi-Layer Perceptron
EMG	Electromyography

ESS	Epworth Sleepiness Scale
ET	Essential tremor
EUROHIS-QOL8	8-item global quality of life questionnaire
EuroQol	European harmonization of the measurement of health-related quality of life
FD	Functional dependency
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FoG	Freezing of gait
FOGQ	Freezing of Gait Questionnaire
GDS	Global Deterioration Scale
GeDS	Geriatric Depression Scale
GLSLM	General Least Squares Linear Model
GRS	Genetic Risk Score
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Study
H&Y	Hoehn and Yahr Scale
HADS	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale
HbA1c	Glycated haemoglobin
HC	Healthy controls
HR	Hazard ratio
HRQL	Health-related quality of life
HVLT	Hopkins Verbal Learning Test
HY	Hoehn and Yahr Scale
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases 10th Revision
IH	Idiopathic Hyposmia
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IPDG	International Parkinson's Disease Genomics Consortium
IPD	Idiopathic Parkinson Disease
iRBD	idiopathic REM sleep behaviour disorder
KASP	Kompetitive Allele Specific Polymerase
L	Lifestyle
LABS-PD	The Longitudinal and Biomarker Study in PD
LADS	Leeds Hospital Anxiety & Depression Scale
LASSO	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator
LEDD	Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose
LGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine

LID	Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia
LOSO	Leave One Subject Out
LR	Logistic Regression
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
MDS	Movement Disorders Society
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale
MDS-UPDRS II	Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale part II
MDS-UPDRS III	Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale part III
ML	Machine learning
MMNS	Mild motor-non-motor subtype
MMSE	Mini Mental State Examination
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MR	Mendelian Randomization
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
M5F	M5 model trees
MS	Motor symptoms
NA	Noradrenaline
NB	Naive Bayes
NMS	Non-motor symptoms
NMSS	Non-motor Symptoms Scale
NPI	Neuropsychiatric Inventory
OD	Olfactive dysfunction
OPDC	Oxford Parkinson's Disease Centre Discovery Cohort
OR	Odds ratio
PCRLDR	Multiplex polymerase chain reaction-ligase detection reaction method
PD	Parkinson Disease
PD-CRS	Parkinson's Disease Cognitive Rating Scale
PD-HD	Dualhit in PD
PD-MCI	Parkinson Disease Mild Cognitive Impairment
PD-RBD	Parkinson Disease-REM Behaviour Disorder
PDQ-39	39 item Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire
PDQ8	Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire
PDSS	Parkinson's Sleep Scale
PET	Positron Emission Tomography

PHS	Polygenic Hazard Score
PIGD	Postural Instability Gait Difficulty
PKG	Personal KinetiGraph
PPMI	Parkinson's Progression Marker Initiative
PQ-10	Rating of global perceived QoL (PQ-10) on a scale from 0 (worst) to 10 (best)
pRBD	Probable RBD
PRS	Polygenic Risk Scores
QoL	Quality of life
QUIP	Questionnaire for Impulsive Compulsive Disorder
QUIP-RS	Questionnaire for Impulse Control Disorders in Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
RBD	Rapid Eye Movement Sleep Behaviour Disorder
RBDQ-HK	RBD Questionnaire-Hong Kong
RBDSQ	REM Sleep Disorder Questionnaire
RF	Random Forest
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROMP	Radboud Oral Motor Inventory for Parkinson's Disease
RPE	Rate of perceived exertion
RR	Relative risk
S&E	Schwab and England Scale
S&E-ADLS	Schwab and England Activities of Daily Living Scale
S/E	Schwab and England Scale
SCD	Subjective Cognitive Decline
SCOPA-AUT	Scale for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease for Autonomic symptoms
SD	Standard deviation
SDM	Symbol Digit Modalities
SPECT	Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography
SMNS	Severe motor-non-motor subtype
SNCA	Synuclein Alpha gene
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
sPD	Sporadic PD
STAI	State Trait Anxiety Inventory
SVM	Support Vector Machine
T2DM	Type 2 diabetes mellitus
TD	Tremor dominant

TUAG	Timed Up and Go Test
UA	Uric Acid
UK	United Kingdom
UPDRS I-IV	Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale part I to IV
UPDRS	Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
UPDRS II	Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale part II
UPDRS III	Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale part III
UPSIT	University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test
US	United States
VAS	Visual analogue scales
VIPD-Q	Visual disturbances in patients with Parkinson's Disease questionnaire
WES	Whole-Exome Sequencing
WGS	Whole-Genome Sequencing
WM	White Matter

Executive summary

This document has been written by the AI-PROGNOSIS project partners under the EU Horizon Europe RIA program (Grant Agreement No 101080581). The document presents the literature review performed to delineate the State-of-the-Art to date in predicting Parkinson's disease (PD) risk, PD progression and response to medication. It also summarizes the relevant digital technologies that are currently available. Based on the literature review findings and the available digital technologies, we have requested access to various datasets and biobanks containing health and genetic information. A detailed list is outlined in the current document. Additionally, harmonisation and curation techniques to be employed on these datasets are presented. The review is a preliminary document and will be updated throughout the project's first two years to provide a final version and meet the project's objectives.

1 Introduction

This document is the initial version of the Datasets and Domain Review of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project. The objectives of this report are:

- To provide an extensive domain review regarding the current state-of-the-art (SoA) in assessing Parkinson's Disease (PD) risk based on clinically-driven models and digital biomarkers (dBM) and point out research opportunities and challenges,
- To provide an extensive domain review regarding the current SoA in monitoring PD progression and medication response based on data-driven models and dBM and point out research opportunities and challenges,
- To provide an updated review of FDA- or CE-approved digital technologies currently used to monitor PD,
- To delineate pertinent, multi-source datasets from AI-PROGNOSIS partners' or third-party (large-scale) databases/biobanks/cohorts that include long-term follow-ups of people with PD and incident cases. These datasets have been accessed and assessed in terms of quality according to the established framework,
- To describe how these datasets have been stratified by utility for R&D within the AI-PROGNOSIS project objectives: PD risk, REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) detection, and monitoring of PD progression and medication response,
- To describe how the data have been sanitised, debiased, munged, and harmonised using a common data model, following established standards and clinical knowledge for the standardisation of representations of multi-site outcome assessments.

1.1 Document scope

This document constitutes the preliminary edition of the review developed within the scope of the Horizon Europe AI-PROGNOSIS project, designated as deliverable D2.3 "Initial report on domain review and datasets" and is submitted in Month 9. It precedes the deliverable D2.4 "Updated report on domain review and datasets", scheduled for submission in Month 24. Both documents are integral to Task 2.1 "Domain and data landscape review" under Work Package (WP) 2 "Foundation, data curation and co-creation". This preliminary report provides the building blocks for AI and dBM development in WP3 "Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response".

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured into four principal sections after a brief introduction. Section 2 presents two domain reviews of the current SoA in the assessment of clinical, demographic, and lifestyle variables, genetic associations, data-driven approaches, and digital tracking for a) PD risk and b) PD progression and medication response. References referred to in this section will be listed in two separate Annexes, Annex 1, including the references for PD risk, and Annex 2, those for PD progression and medication response. Section 3 outlines the currently available and validated digital technologies used for PD monitoring. Section 4 describes the third-party open datasets that have been accessed by the consortium and their utility for the project, as well as the datasets that have been declined after request. Section 4 describes the dataset harmonisation and curation process.

2 Literature review

2.1 Search methodology, outline, and definitions

With this objective, two literature searches were conducted for articles published in the past 11 years (1/2013-1/2024) in three databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The first literature search aimed to capture all relevant articles pertaining to clinical and genetic approaches to predict PD risk and monitor disease progression and response to treatment that could be relevant for our project. The second literature search aimed to capture all relevant articles regarding machine learning and digital assessments used to monitor PD risk and PD disease progression monitoring and response to treatment. We included all articles found in a common Rayyan database to be used by all consortium partners. Rayyan is a web-based software application specifically designed for organizing articles and extracting data for undertaking literature and systematic reviews. It allows the selection of articles by keyword or words in the title/abstract, type of article, journal title, etc. The two SoA reviews were divided into subsections as detailed in the Table of Contents above. Each subsection was assigned to two consortium partners based on their area of expertise. Each author accessed both Rayyan databases to select the relevant articles for their topic based on keywords and abstract/title searches as detailed below. When deemed necessary, authors added other search strategies as explained below.

2.1.1 Clinical and genetic assessment approaches

The first bibliographic search aimed to identify the clinical and genetic assessment approaches to investigate PD risk and PD progression and medication response. The search terms used were: (“Parkinson Disease” OR Parkinson*) AND (“Risk factors” OR “treatment outcome” OR “disease progression” AND (“machine learning” OR “big data” OR “algorithms” OR “automatic data processing” OR “biomarker” OR “surveys” OR “disease monitoring”) AND (“olfaction” OR “hyposmia” OR “REM sleep behaviour disorder” OR “daytime somnolence” OR “tremor” OR “rigidity” OR “bradykinesia” OR “posture” OR “balance” OR “falls” OR “freezing” OR “cognition” OR “dementia” OR “cognition” OR “gene” OR “genetics” OR “genome” OR “dyskinesia”).

This search yielded 10,209 (345 PubMed, 9,500 Scopus, 366 Web of Science) references that were included in a Rayyan database (**Figure 1**). Rayyan is a web-based software application that allows organizing articles and extracting data for undertaking literature and systematic reviews. It allows selection of articles by keyword or words in the title/abstract, type of article, journal etc.

After exclusion of duplicates, 4,487 articles remained. The number of duplicates is high because Scopus, PubMed, and Web of Science found the same papers, and Scopus has a much larger number because it is broader and includes more technical papers. There are additional records identified through other sources; specially for the genetic assessment as described below: GWAS (43), PRS (3), and citation searching (2).

We proceeded to filter these articles by excluding all articles that were not in English and had the keywords rats, mice, cells, case reports; and by including all articles containing in the title or abstract: Parkinson* AND Machine learning OR artificial intelligence; Parkinson* AND REM OR RBD OR Sleep OR somnolence OR tremor OR dyskinesias OR rigidity OR bradykinesia OR slowness OR motor OR limb OR posture OR balance OR falls OR freezing OR cognition OR dementia OR cognitive OR dysexecutive OR amnesia OR memory and Parkinson* AND gene OR genetic OR DNA OR SNP OR GWAS. This reduced the number of possibly relevant references to 1,851 articles. The rest of the search strategy is described in each subtopic below in the Results section.

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: 'rats', 'mice', 'cells', 'case reports', 'no-randomized', 'survey', 'cross-sectional', and 'case control'

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

Figure 1 PRISMA flow chart clinical and genetic bibliographic search

2.1.2 Machine learning and digital approaches

The second bibliographic search aimed to identify the relevant articles describing machine learning and digital approaches for identifying PD risk and monitoring PD progression and medication response. The search terms used were: (Parkinson Disease OR Parkinson*) AND (Artificial intelligence OR AI OR "computational intelligence" OR "machine intelligence" OR "machine learning") AND ("Digital Technology" OR "Wearable Electronic Devices" OR "Smartphone" OR accelerometer* OR app OR apps OR "assistive device*" OR "assistive technolog*" OR device* OR "digital health" OR "digital biomarker*" OR "digital phenotyp*" OR ehealth OR e-health OR "electronic health" OR eyetracking OR facetracking OR handtracking OR "health tech*" OR mhealth OR m-health OR "mobile application*" OR "mobile health" OR monitoring OR motiontracking OR selfmonitoring OR selftracking OR sensor OR sensors OR smart-phone* OR smartphone* OR smart-watch* OR smartwatch* OR tracking OR wearable*).

This search yielded 8,388 references (770 PubMed, 6,530 Scopus, 1,088 Web of Science) that were included in a second Rayyan database. There are additional records identified through citation searching (**Figure 2**). After duplicate exclusion, there were 3,551 references. After excluding articles that were not in English and those that included keywords such as "rats", "mice", "cells", "case reports" and including all articles containing in title or abstract: Parkinson AND artificial intelligence OR artificial intelligence OR AI OR computational intelligence OR machine intelligence OR machine learning OR Digital Technology OR

Wearable OR Smartphone OR accelerometer OR app OR apps OR assistive device OR “assistive technology OR digital health OR digital biomarker OR ehealth OR e-health OR mhealth OR m-health OR monitoring OR sensor OR sensors OR smartwatch OR tracking OR wearable, a total of 969 possibly relevant references were identified.

Both the data driven/clinical Rayyan database and the ML/DBM database were further filtered by the clinical and technical partners in the consortium regarding the different sections of the reviews by a more targeted selection of keywords, as described in more detail in the Results section below, under each topic.

*After excluding by automation tools with the keyword's: "rats", "mice", "cells", "case reports", "no-randomized", "survey", "cross-sectional", and "case control"

** Full text was read to confirm eligibility

** Excluded, with reasons: wrong population, wrong publication type, wrong intervention. Described below for each subtopic

***Described below for each subtopic

Figure 2 PRISMA flow chart for wearable sensors and machine learning bibliographic search.

2.2 Parkinson's disease risk

2.2.1 Introduction

Early PD can be divided into three stages: 1) preclinical PD, where the neurodegenerative processes have started, but there are no detectable symptoms or signs; 2) prodromal PD, where non motor or/and motor symptoms and signs are present, but not sufficiently to reach the defining features of the disease (this phase can last years to decades and indicates the slowly progressive spread of PD pathology); and 3) clinical PD, where the diagnosis can be made based on the classic motor signs (Berg and Postuma, 2014). The risk markers for developing PD are currently based upon established demographic factors such as age, sex,

family history of PD or genetic background (known gene mutation or polygenic risk score), lifestyle factors such as regular exposure to pesticides or occupational solvents, physical inactivity, non-use of caffeine or never having smoked and clinical factors such as diabetes mellitus, physical inactivity and low plasma urate levels (Heinzel et al., 2019). However, prodromal PD is not established only by the presence of risk markers since, by definition, some evidence of ongoing neurodegeneration must also be present. Markers of prodromal PD have been proposed based on data from 1) imaging and histopathological longitudinal and cross-sectional studies that correlate risk factors with clinical symptoms preceding the typical motor manifestations, 2) longitudinal studies that analyse phenoconversion to PD in cohorts of individuals with different combinations of risk factors, and 3) cross-sectional case-control genome-wide association studies (GWAS) and polygenic risk score (PRS) studies that have identified genetic variants or combination of them that increase the likelihood of developing PD. The currently identified prodromal markers for PD are RBD, reduced striatal dopaminergic innervation as measured with single photon emission tomography (SPECT) or positron emission tomography (PET), subthreshold parkinsonism, abnormal quantitative motor testing, olfactory loss, constipation, excessive daytime somnolence, orthostatic hypotension, erectile and urinary dysfunction, depression and a global cognitive deficit.

For the purpose of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, this review aims to investigate the diagnostic value of demographic, lifestyle and clinical factors, as well as genetic factors and dBMs associated with PD risk and prodromal PD. For genetic markers we particularly focus beyond the monogenic forms of PD considering common genetic variants with low individual strength, but cumulative predictive effect that can be calculated into a polygenic risk score (PRS). In order for the multisource data to provide meaningful and accurate PD risk assessments, machine learning applications are crucial. We hence reviewed the most commonly used machine learning approaches for identifying people at risk of developing PD, as well as the digital assessments of two of the well-established prodromal clinical risk factors of PD: RBD and daytime somnolence.

We present the literature review methodology and results for each section below.

2.2.2 Clinical, demographic, and lifestyle factors associated with PD risk

Study selection

The search was performed within the Rayyan clinical and genetic assessments bibliography (1803 references) using the following combination of search terms: 'diabetes' OR 'uric acid' OR 'demographic' OR 'age' OR 'sex' OR 'lifestyle' OR 'urban' OR 'rural' OR 'pesticides' OR 'employment' OR 'exercise' OR 'diet' alongside "risk" and "prodromal," which yielded 88 for 'risk' and 17 articles for 'prodromal'. Three independent reviewers screened the abstracts and full texts when necessary to confirm eligibility. **Table 1** outlines the selection which was based on the risk of PD or PD phenoconversion in relation to demographic, clinical, or lifestyle factors, thus excluded articles focusing on digital biomarkers or neuroimaging studies. Cross-sectional studies and review articles were excluded. A total of 28 studies were included following this selection criteria.

Table 1 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD Risk

Item	Definition
Population	General healthy populations or prodromal PD populations
Analysis	Incident PD/PD phenoconversion

Results	Clinical, demographic or lifestyle variables
---------	--

Study characteristics

Of the selected articles, 15 investigated clinical variables, 5 focused on lifestyle variables and 8 studied a combination of these factors. Most were observational cohorts, except 4 case control studies (Park et al., 2022; Song et al., 2020; Shrag et al., 2023; Xiang et al., 2023). Time of follow up ranged from 3-47 years. There were 20 general population studies (**Table 2**), most of them following large cohorts (range 146-938.635) through health registries longitudinally with incident PD as the main outcome. Six of them (Doun et al., 2022; Marini et al., 2020; Noyce 2017; Park et al., 2022; Sharamagkgas et al., 2023; Sood et al., 2023) used predictive algorithms to determine clinical, demographic and lifestyle variables associated with developing PD risk. Eight studies investigated prodromal PD populations, most of them focused on RBD, while one study looked at essential tremor patients and 2 considered people with hyposmia. These latter studies were smaller, with a sample size ranging from 36-1160 people.

Clinical, demographical and lifestyle factors

General population studies investigated clinical non-motor symptoms associated with PD, such as hyposmia, RBD, distressing dreams, sleep and fatigue, affective disorders, subjective cognitive decline, and dysautonomic symptoms, while others looked at prodromic motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, walking pace or tapping speed. Some studies investigated the association of PD with other diseases, such as hyper uricemia, hypertension, stroke, dislipemia and diabetes mellitus. Many cohorts investigated lifestyle factors, such as smoking, caffeine and alcohol intake, religiosity, physical activity, and demographic factors, such as age and sex, body mass index and socioeconomic status.

Table 2 Studies about clinical (C), demographic (D) and lifestyle (L) factors associated with PD risk

Author/Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
Beydou et al., 2022	C	14.39 (±6.18)	1756	To evaluate sleep and affective (mood/anxiety) disorders as clinical predictors of incident Parkinson's disease (PD) among women ≥65 years of age.	Time-to-event was calculated from baseline (1993–1998) to year of incident PD, loss to follow-up, death, or December 31, 2018, whichever came first.	Women older than 65	Among older women, joint sleep/affective disorders and affective disorders alone are strong clinical predictors of incident PD over 14 years.
Dou et al., 2022	C	5	3 models N=609; N=516; N=477	Develop and validate clinical risk models using non-motor predictors to distinguish between early PD and healthy individuals.	Multipredictor modelling to distinguish PD from HC.	PPMI data base	Eight variables: age, gender, family history, UPSIT, MOCA, RBDSQ, alpha synuclein in CSF and SNCA rs356181 polymorphism in model. High accuracy. AUC of 0.93
Flores-Torres et al., 2023	C	47	12.427	Examine whether subjective cognitive decline (SCD) is more likely to be present in women with features suggestive of prodromal PD (defined as hyposmia, RBD and constipation) compared with women without these features	Bi annual self-administered questionnaires about hyposmia, constipation and RBD	Nurse Health Study. The prodromal PD Subgroup	Women experiencing the three examined nonmotor features (hyposmia, constipation, and probable rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder) had the worst mean SCD score and the highest odds of poor subjective cognition
Jacobs et al., 2020	C, L	12.01	1276 PD 500,406 controls	Investigate the association of clinical, and lifestyle risk factors and prodromal features with incident Parkinson's disease and the interaction of genetic risk with these factors.	Determined association of risk factors with incident PD using adjusted logistic regression models. Constructed polygenic risk scores (PRSs) using external weights and selected the best PRS from a subset of the cohort (30%). The PRS was used in a separate testing set (70%) to examine gene-environment interactions and compare predictive models for PD.	UK Biobank	Evidence of association between PD and a positive family history of PD, a positive family history of dementia, non-smoking, low alcohol consumption, depression, daytime somnolence, epilepsy and earlier menarche. The effect of diabetes on PD risk appears to depend on background genetic risk for PD.
Kang et al., 2023	C, L	17	938.635	Investigate the incidence of PD in Korean population by age and year for each sex as well as the modifiable risk factors for PD. Explore the HR and RR for each modifiable risk factor	Chart review by ICD-10 diagnosis of defined modifiable risk factors: hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, ischemic stroke, haemorrhagic stroke, ischemic heart disease, depression,	Korean population in National Health service	1.1% developed PD. Incidence of PD increased with age up to 80 years. Presence of hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidaemia, ischemic stroke, haemorrhagic stroke, ischemic heart disease, depression, osteoporosis, and

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
					osteoporosis, obesity, physical activity, smoking and alcohol consumption. End point was PD development	without PD or dementia	obesity were independently associated with a higher risk for PD
Liu et al., 2023	C	12.5	419.572	To quantify the association of handgrip strength and self-reported walking pace with incident PD in the general population.	Handgrip measured by dynamometer and gait measured by self-report. Study endpoint was PD diagnosis	General population without PD from UK Biobank	Low handgrip strength and slow walking pace together (HR 2,89 95% CI 2.30-3.65) were significantly associated with a higher risk of incident PD, regardless of the individuals' genetic risk profile
Marini et al., 2020	C	10	574	To apply the PREDICT-PD algorithm of risk indicators for PD in a prospective community-based study x representative of the general elderly population	PREDICT-PD risk scores were calculated based on risk factor assessments obtained at baseline. Outcome: incident PD	General elderly (The Bruneck study)	The PREDICT-PD score was associated with an increased risk for incident PD in our sample and may represent a useful first screening step in future algorithms aiming to identify cases of prodromal PD
Noyce et al., 2017	C, D, L	3	1323	To test an online, evidence-based algorithm to identify risk indicators of PD in the UK population.	Participants completed an online survey and keyboard-tapping task annually over 3 years, and underwent smell tests and genotyping. Outcomes: incident PD, and intermediate markers of PD: smell loss, RBD score, and slowed tapping speed	UK population	The online PREDICT-PD algorithm is a unique and simple method to identify indicators of PD risk. The predictive power for incident PD was improved by the addition of genetic variants to risk scores.
Otaiku, 2023	C	50	6991	Investigate the association between distressing dreams in childhood and the risk of developing cognitive impairment or PD by age 50.	Proxy report of distressful dreams (from mother) at age 7 and 11 correlated with incident PD at age 50 (diagnosed by doctor)	British Birth Cohort Study	Having persistent distressing dreams during childhood may be associated with an increased risk (OR 1.85 95% CI 1.1-3.1) of developing cognitive impairment or PD by age of 50.
Otaiku, 2023	L	8.1	2.672	Investigate whether low religiosity in adulthood is associated with increased risk for developing PD.	Self-report questionnaires on religiosity. Estimated OR for developing PD adjusted for sociodemographic and health factors.	English Longitudinal Study of Aging and the Midlife in US study	Low religiosity in adulthood may be a strong risk factor (OR 9,99 CI 3.28-30.36) for developing PD.

Author/Year	Factors (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
Park et al., 2022	C, D, L	10.4	1.102	PD prediction models using ML algorithms	Chart review of national registry of patients with >5 follow-ups between 2002-2015 investigating C, D and L variables. Endpoint was diagnosis of PD. Machine learning algorithm were applied for PD prediction	National Health Insurance Service-Health Screening datasets group with PD and matched 1:1 non-PD cohort	The most important factor for predicting PD was BMI, followed by total cholesterol, glucose, haemoglobin, and blood pressure levels. Smoking and alcohol consumption (in men) and socioeconomic status, physical activity, and diabetes mellitus (in women) were highly correlated with occurrence of PD
Power et al., 2023	L	8.3	5.125	Investigation of the association of military employment and PD, because persons with military involvement may be more likely to have PD risk factors.	Self-report or PD prescription refills to identify prevalent and incident cases	Adult changes in thought study	At enrolment 6% of 5,125 eligible participants had military employment and 1.8% had prevalent PD; During follow up 3.5% developed PD. We found no association between military employment and PD
Schrag et al., 2023	C, D, L	6 (SD 2)	138.345 PD 276.690 controls	To identify the association of PD diagnosis with a range of lifestyle factors, comorbidities, and potential extracerebral manifestations of PD.	PD patients and matched controls by age, sex, region and first medical consult. Chart review of risk factors and prodromal features of PD, using the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, Tenth Revision (ICD-10) coding.	General German population using insurance claims of outpatient consultations	Risk factors included traumatic brain injury, odds ratio (OR), 1.62; alcohol misuse, OR, 1.32; hypertension, OR, 1.29; anosmia, OR, 2.16; and parasomnias (including RBD), OR, restless legs syndrome (OR, 4.19), sleep apnoea (OR, 1.45), epilepsy (OR, 2.26), migraine (OR, 1.21), bipolar disorder (OR, 3.81), and schizophrenia (OR, 4.48). Associations even 5 to 10 years before diagnosis included tremor (OR 4.49; 9), restless legs syndrome (OR, 3.73), bipolar disorder (OR, 3.80), and schizophrenia (OR, 4.00).
Schrag et al., 2019	C, D	5	8.166	Develop and validate a prediction model for diagnosis of PD based on presentations in primary care.	Multivariate analysis: tremor, constipation, depression or anxiety, fatigue, dizziness, urinary dysfunction, balance problems, memory problems and cognitive	Primary care consultations	The risk algorithm applied to routine primary care presentations can identify individuals at increased risk of diagnosis of PD within 5 years. Also, 99% of those

Author/Year	Factors (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
					decline, hypotension, rigidity, and hypersalivation.		who were not classified as high risk would not be diagnosed with PD
Skaramagas et al., 2023	C		31 PD and 14 HC	To develop a robust model for accurate PD detection using accelerometer data collected from PD and non-PD individuals with mild or no tremor during phone conversations	The dataset used in this study contains IMU signals captured in the wild via the accelerometer sensor embedded in modern smartphones for the purpose of detecting tremorous episodes related to PD	PD and HC	The proposed model outperforms existing approaches and holds promise for detection of PD with subtle symptoms, like tremor, in the wild. Such symptoms can present in the early or even prodromal stage of the disease, and appropriate mobile-based applications may be a practical tool in real-life settings to alert individuals at risk to seek medical assistance or give patients feedback in monitoring their symptoms.
Song et al., 2020	L	5-25	61,748 stress 595,335 matched HC; 44 839 stress 78 482 unaffected siblings	To examine the association between stress-related disorders and risk for neurodegenerative diseases	Matched cohort design. Individuals who received their first diagnosis of stress-related disorders between 1987 and 2008, matched to healthy controls and/or siblings. Followed until 2013. Outcome: Incident PD or other neurodegenerative disease	Swedish National Patient Register.	No statistically significant association was found with stress-related disorders and Parkinson disease
Sood et al., 2023	C	10	1178 HC and 24 Incident PD	Artificial intelligence (AI) to learn and quantify PD marker interdependencies via a Bayesian network (BN) with probabilistic confidence estimation using bootstrapping	Used prospective data of 18 established risk and prodromal markers of PD in healthy, PD-free individuals and incident PD cases collected longitudinally in 4 visits over up to 10 years.	Tubingen evaluation of Risk factors for Early detection of Neuro Degeneration (TREND) study. PD and HC	Altogether our work demonstrates the potential of modern AI approaches (specifically BNs) both for modelling and understanding interdependencies between PD risk and prodromal markers, which are so far not accounted for in PD prediction models, as well as for generating realistic synthetic data.

Author/Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
Terracciano et al., 2023	L	15	491 603	To assess whether loneliness is associated with risk of incident PD and whether the association is independent of other risk factors or modified by age, sex, and genetic vulnerability	This large cohort study found that loneliness was associated with risk of incident PD across demographic groups and independent of depression and other prominent risk factors and genetic risk. The findings add to the evidence that loneliness is a substantial psychosocial determinant of health	UK Biobank	2822 developed PD during the 15-year follow-up. Individuals who reported being lonely had a higher risk of PD (hazard ratio [HR], 1.37; 95%CI, 1.25-1.51). Loneliness was associated with risk of incident PD across demographic groups and independent of depression and other prominent risk factors and genetic risk.
Venkatesan D et al., 2021	L	5.1 ± 2.0	146 total 73 PD 73 HC	Determine the association of lifestyle, environmental factors, biochemical parameters and genetic insights in Indian population	Standardised questionnaires about environmental factors for PD and age matched controls during 5 years.	Tamil Nadu Indian population HC and PD patients	Smoking, alcohol, caffeinated drinks, occupational influence of agriculture and industry and pesticide exposure had more association with PD occurrence.
Sampaio Froehner et al., 2022	C	3	36	Evaluate the risk of developing PD based on DAT Scan in ET patients	Underwent clinical assessment (neurological, MDS UPDRS III and Archimedes spiral) and DAT scan at baseline. Clinical assessment after 3 years	Essential tremor patients	Advanced age at the onset of tremor, the presence of bradykinesia, and asymmetrical alterations in SPECT may be related to progression to PD in patients with ET
Joza et al., 2023	C	3.3 ± 2.2	1160	Study the progression of clinical markers in prodromal Parkinson's disease	Periodic structured sleep, motor, cognitive, autonomic and olfactory testing.	RBD patients from 28 countries (International REM study group)	Motor variables tended to progress faster. By contrast, cognitive, olfactory and autonomic variables showed modest progression with higher variability
Koros et al., 2023	C	5 years	65	Assess the role of serum uric acid as a putative biomarker in a prodromal PD cohort (39 RBD and 26 Hyposmia) with abnormal DAT Scan	Longitudinal serum uric measurements from Prodromal population and compared to de novo sporadic PD (423) and 196 HC	Prodromal PD from PPMI	Serum uric acid levels are higher in prodromal PD subjects compared to those with manifest PD indicating decrease in the levels of serum uric acid occurs with transition from prodromal to clinical PD

Author/Year	Factors (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Population type	Key messages
Postuma et al., 2015	C, D, L	4	279	Assess whether risk factors for PD increase rate of defined neurodegenerative disease in RBD	Self-reported questionnaire about D and L. variables including pesticide exposures, occupation, comorbid conditions, medication use, family history, and autonomic/motor symptoms. At 4 years follow-up, clinical assessment for dementia or parkinsonism. Endpoint:	iRBD population without PD from 12 centres	33.3% developed neurodegenerative disease. Patients who converted were older, with similar sex distribution. Neither caffeine, smoking, nor alcohol exposure predicted conversion. Convertors were more likely to report family history of dementia (odds ratio [OR] = 2.09), without significant differences in PD or sleep disorders. Autonomic and motor symptoms were more common among those who converted.
Shin et al., 2020	C	5	89 total 31 PD, 39 iRBD, 19 HC	To elucidate longitudinal changes in the DAT availability in association with the prodromal markers in iRBD.	All participants were evaluated for olfaction, neuropsychological tests, and the MDS-UPDRS and underwent 18F-FP-CIT PET scans every 2 years. Calculated the DAT pattern by performing the principal component analysis of tracer uptakes in 6 striatal regions	naive PD, HC and iRBD from clinic population	Baseline and longitudinal monitoring of the DAT pattern can be a useful biomarker in identifying individuals with a high risk of disease conversion and in selecting the potential population for clinical trials in iRBD
Vaswani et al., 2022	C	10	186	Hyposmia on a single test has been associated with increased risk of PD, but, taken alone, lacks specificity. We evaluated whether repeating olfactory testing improves the diagnostic characteristics of this screening approach	Serial olfaction tests were performed, assessed with the UPSIT at baseline and on average 1.4 years later. Multiple logistic regression and Cox proportional hazards regression were used to estimate the hazard of development of clinical PD or abnormal DAT imaging.	Hyposmic	Relative risk of clinical conversion to PD was 8.3 (95% CI:0.92–75.2, p = 0.06) and of abnormal DAT scan was 12.5 (2.4–156.2, p = 0.005) for persistent hyposmia, compared to reversion. Repeat olfactory testing may be an efficient and cost-effective strategy to improve identification of at-risk patients for early diagnosis and disease modification studies.
Xiang et al., 2023	C		278-RBD 556 HC	To investigate the risk factors for RBD in a case-control study	Participants with probable RBD (pRBD) were defined using the RBD Questionnaire-Hong Kong (RBDQ-HK).	iRBD and HC	We determined several risk factors for pRBD in this case-control study. Future studies are needed to understand the mechanism underlying the association between these factors and pRBD.
Zhang et al., 2022	C, D, L	5.8	281	To assess risk factors for phenoconversion to PD in patients with RBD	Detailed questionnaire about L. Patients were prospectively followed and received assessments	iRBD from 12 centres	46.3% patients developed neurodegenerative disease. Overall phenoconversion rate was 24.2% after 3

Author/ Year	Factor s (C, D, L)	Study duration (years)	Sample size	Study aim	Methods	Populatio n type	Key messages
					for parkinsonism or dementia during follow-up.		years, and 67.5% after 10 years. Patients with older age (adjusted hazard ratio [aHR] = 1.05) and nitrate derivative use (aHR = 2.18) were more likely to phenoconvert. Prior pesticide exposure, rural living, lipid-lowering medication use, and respiratory medication use were associated with lower phenoconversion risk.

General discussion

This review aims to provide an update on the clinical, demographic and lifestyle variables that increase the risk of developing PD or phenoconversion from prodromal PD to clinical PD, as well as the different types of approaches to assess these markers. These longitudinal studies have variable strengths and limitations based on study characteristics, assessment models (e.g., prospective versus retrospective, machine learning approaches), precision of marker estimates (e.g., clinical versus self-reported) and the certainty of PD phenoconversion (e.g., medical records vs imaging etc.) and data quality of markers (sensitivity and specificity). Population studies aimed to find independent factors that increase the risk of PD incidence, while some, such as the Predict PD algorithm, used multivariate analysis to predict the risk of developing PD (Schrag et al., 2019). The limitation of population studies is that the incidence rate of PD is approximately 200 per 100,000 person-years in those over 60 years old. Therefore, cohorts need to be very large and are thus highly costly, while their representativeness is limited (Noyce et al., 2017). The smaller prodromal population studies aimed to characterize the interaction of these underlying prodromal states (such as RBD or hyposmia) with other demographic or environmental factors. These studies are less costly and help identify populations for clinical trials that seek neuroprotective interventions but are also less representative of the general population.

Clinical PD is a heterogeneous and complex disease with many different possible aetiologies and thus prodromal PD is probably also heterogeneous and needs to be further investigated. For example, a subgroup of PD patients may have few or irrelevant non motor symptoms, and thus their prodromal state probably differs from other PD subtypes. Thus, phenotyping prodromal PD subtypes is likely to be important and will help delineate other variables that may influence if and when individuals phenoconvert to clinical PD.

2.2.3 Genetic markers associated with PD Risk

PD is categorised into familial and sporadic cases. Worldwide studies report familial PD accounts for about 15% and sporadic for about 85% of cases. Familial PD includes inherited or monogenic forms of the disease, while the genetic background of sporadic cases is more complicated (Abu-Manneh et al., 2022). Many Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have been performed on PD to identify the association between common genetic variants and the disease. Although many variant associations have been reported, most have a small effect on disease risk, and an essential proportion of the genetic contribution to PD risk needs to be better understood. Thus, the Polygenic Risk Score (PRS), which combines the small effects of multiple genetic variants into a single value estimating the genetic risk, is currently being evaluated (Chairta et al., 2021). This genetic marker review aims to (1) report the different variants that have thus far been associated with PD through GWAS and meta-analysis and (2) assess the PRS predictive models for PD that have been published.

Study selection

The search was performed within the Rayyan bibliographic searches using the following combination of search terms: “gene” OR “genetic” OR “GWAS” OR “PRS” OR “Polygenic Risk Score” OR “SNP” OR “polymorphism” OR “genetic association” AND “risk” OR “prodromal”, and yielded 240 and 24 articles (15 were common), respectively. Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Twenty-three articles were immediately excluded as they conveyed an incorrect publication type (reviews, case reports, etc). Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility.

Articles that did not refer to humans, were not specific or related to PD risk, and did not have clear genetic/statistical data were also excluded. This filtering resulted in 45 records. As some significant GWAS and PRS studies were missing from the search, a second search was

performed through the GWAS¹ and PRS² catalogues, resulting in 43 and 3 additional studies, respectively. A total of 91 articles were finally recorded. Then, a raw cut-off for the final selection of the studies was determined based on the type of the study and the p-value of associated variants. All PRS studies, as well as all GWAS and meta-analysis studies, with a significant statistical association of p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively, were included in this review. After the cut-off, a total of 43 studies were recorded and summarised. **Table 3** outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Briefly, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study participants included patients diagnosed with PD, AND Study produces/generates or statistically re-analyses genetic data related with PD risk, AND GWAS or meta-analysis study with a significant statistical association, with p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively or PRS study

Table 3 Selection criteria for genetic markers and PD risk

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Data	Generated or re-analysed available genetic data related with PD risk
Results	GWAS or meta-analysis study with a significant statistical association with p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively or PRS study

Study characteristics

The summarised articles include GWAS, meta-analysis, and PRS studies. Some articles combine GWAS and meta-analysis, and some combine GWAS and PRS data. All the studies reported sample size (cases/controls) and the population/cohort characteristics (e.g., ethnicity, database cohort). Healthy control participants were recruited for all the selected studies and their genetic data were compared versus the genetic data of patients with PD to find out genetic variants associated with PD risk.

Genetic associations

Table 4 summarises the study characteristics (sample size, study type), and the genetic data (associated SNP/variant and nearest gene). All the studies were performed on PD patients and healthy controls, and their genetic backgrounds were compared to assess SNPs that are associated with PD risk in general. The genome-wide genotyping arrays were the most common technique used to discover or validate genetic variants associated with PD. Arrays contain hundreds of thousands of unique nucleotide probe sequences, where each probe is compatible with a specific single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) allele. Other methods used either for the discovery or validation of genetic variants were whole-exome sequencing (WES) and whole-genome sequencing (WGS).

In addition, in some studies, DNA samples of the participants were used for the genetic analysis, while in some other studies already available datasets with genetic data (e.g., PPMI) were analysed. Although several studies used and meta-analysed already available genetic data without performing any experimental work, this approach increased the power of the study due to the larger sample size and improved precision of estimates of effect. Table 4 below presents an overview of study characteristics and results in predicting PD (genetics). Articles 1 to 10 were extracted from the Rayyan search, articles 11 to 40 were extracted from the GWAS catalogue and articles 41 to 43 from the PRS catalogue.

¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/>

² <https://www.pgscatalog.org/>

Table 4 Studies about genetic markers and PD risk.

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Wainberg et al., 2023	PD GWAS: 37,688 cases, 18,618 proxy cases from the UK Biobank with a family history of PD, and 1,417,791 HC + summary statistics for all participants from 23andMe	genetic association, identify loci associated with PD through GWAS	LCORL(rs34025766); SETD1A(rs11150601); BCKDK (rs889555); GRN(rs5848); FAM171A2(rs850738); LINC02210- CRHR1(rs62053943); WNT3(rs199526); GAK(rs873786); TMEM175(rs34311866)
Rahman et al., 2023	PD: 6,868, HC: 204	GWAS	GBA: Missense Variant(i4000415); TRIM46: Intron Variant(rs114525519); ASH1L: Intron Variant(rs116540837); PBXIP1: Intron Variant(rs116114495); GBA: intergenic variant(rs1630500); ARHGEF2: Intron Variant(rs71628699); RIT1: Intron Variant(rs1749409); SEMA4A: Missense Variant(rs41265017); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs513043); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs577492); LMNA: Intron Variant(rs553016); PMF1-BGLAP: Intron Variant(rs1800247); (rs2764407); (rs35902694)
Lee et al., 2022	de novo PD: 413, HC: 195	PRS	PRS (87)
Pavelka et al., 2022	IPD :430, HC:556	PRS	PRS (90 SNPS)
Liu et al., 2022	IPDGC, 7,204 PD and 9,412 HC and validation cohorts COURAGE-PD, 8,968 PD and 7,598 HC; UK Biobank, 2,639 PD and 14,301 HC; AMP-PD, 2,248 PD and 2,817 HC	PRS and genetic association in meta-analysis	LINC01262(rs62325099); TBCA (rs2652202); LINC01375(rs12245509); C18orf42(rs292289); PRS (1,060); PRS (1,034); PRS (977); PRS (802)
Lee et al., 2021	PPMI (367 sPD), 72 LRRK2 (G2019S), and 39 GBA (N370S) PD patients, HC: 213); GSH (38 sPD, 71 HC)	genetic association and GRS	PRS (45 SNPs)
Jacobs et al., 2020	PD :1276, HC: 500 406	PRS	PRS (Nalls, 90 SNPs) highest 10% of PRSs

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Bobbili et al., 2020	PD:340, HC: 146	genetic association and PRS	PRS (43 SNPs-singleton loss-of- function variants); (PRS_LRRK2)
Li et al., 2019	PD: 418, HC: 426	genetic association and PRS	PRS1 (13 SNPs); PRS2 (9 SNPs); PRS3
Rizig et al., 2023	PD:1488, HC: 196 430	GWAS and meta-analysis	GBA1(rs3115534)
Siitonen et al., 2017	PD: 403, HC: 1,650; Replication: NA	GWAS, find genetic associations with PD	COL18A1(chr21:46916033); ADAMTS9, AS2(chr3:64699445); PPFIBP1(chr12:27737074); SNX29P2(chr16:29348809); WWOX(chr16:79360135); ZFAT(chr8:135611154); ZNF98(chr19:22620820); ZNF277(chr7:111916329); FER(chr5:108436958); RPL18P3(chr5:120977240); FRRS1L(chr9:111929013); PBX1(chr1:164546863); CEL(chr9:135955826)
Pickrell et al., 2016	9,619 European ancestry cases, 324,522 European ancestry controls; Replication: NA	summary statistics of GWAS	PKP2, SYT10(rs144847051); HLA-DQA1, HLA-DRB5(rs17425622); GBA(rs2230288); STK39, CERS6(rs13016703); GAK(rs35541465); GCH1(rs11158026); DCUN1D1, MCCC1(rs9858038); FAM126A, KLHL7(rs10256359); RAB7L1, NUCKS1(rs823118); TIAL1, BAG3(rs188789342); FAM47E(rs6812193); BST1, CD38(rs4266290); RIT2(rs4130047); ZNF184,HIST1H2BL(rs4713118); CCDC62(rs11060180); CTNND1, OR9Q1(rs687432); PRICKLE1, ADAMTS20(rs148294058); SH3GL2(rs2209440); SYT17, CLEC19A(rs11343); NDUFAF2(rs162227); GPRIN3, SNCA(rs356182); LRRK2(rs28903073); CRHR1, LRRC37A3(rs365825)
Rodrigo et al., 2021	5,167 European ancestry cases, 5,366 European ancestry controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	ASH1L(rs145330152); TEKT4(rs187989831); TMEM175(rs34311866); SNCA(rs983361); WDR41(rs137887044); MUC12(rs78837976); CARS2(rs74125032); HASPIN(rs117672332); MAPT(rs7221167); WNT3(rs199501); GBA(rs35749011); SNCA(rs3806789); HASPIN(rs11653889);
Park et al., 2023	554 East Asian ancestry female cases, 2,610 East Asian ancestry female controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	(rs34778348); (rs3796661)
Hamza et al., 2010	PD:2,000; HC: 1,986; Replication: Up to 1,447 PD, 1,468 HC	GWAS	SNCA (rs356220); GAK (rs11248051); HLA-DRA(rs3129882)
Satake et al., 2009	PD: 988, HC: 2,521; Replication: PD: 933, HC: 15,753	GWAS	SNCA (rs11931074); BST1(rs4538475); LRRK2(rs1994090); SLC45A3, PARK16, PM20D1, NUCKS1, RAB7L1, SLC41A1(rs947211)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Do et al., 2011	PD: 3,426, HC: 29,624; Replication: NA	GWAS	SCARB2(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356220); MAPT(rs12185268); MCCC1, LAMP3(rs10513789); GAK(rs6599389); LRRK2(rs34637584); GBA(i4000416)
Nalls et al., 2011	PD: 5,333, HC: 12,019; Replication: PD: 7,053 cases, HC: 9,007 controls	Meta-analysis	GAK (rs6599388); BST1(rs11724635); LRRK2(rs1491942); SYT11(rs34372695); ACMSD(rs6710823); MCCC1, LAMP3(rs11711441); SNCA(rs356219); STK39(rs2102808); HLA-DRB5(6:32588205); CCDC62, HIP1R(rs12817488); MAPT(rs2942168)
Liu et al., 2011	PD: 268, HC: 178; Replication: PD:1,782; HC: 1,658	GWAS, meta-analysis	NSF (rs183211); UNC13B(rs10121009); WNT3(rs415430)
Hill-Burns et al., 2014	sPD: 1,565, familial PD: 435, HC: 1,986; Replication: sPD: 1,528, familial PD: 707, HC: 796	GWAS	HUSEYO(rs2338971); SNCA(rs356220); SNCA(rs356220); HLA(rs3129882); HLA(rs3129882); HUSEYO(rs2338971)
Smeland et al., 2021	PD: 20,184, HC: 397,324; Replication:NA	GWAS	KLHL7(rs28624974); RN7SL474P(rs11203810); SH3GL2(rs13294100); CCNT2-AS1(rs6430538); STK39(rs4667572); TBC1D5(rs13078687); PKP2(rs138895122); CCDC62(rs11060112); BST1(rs12651314); GPR65(rs8005172); RP11-16217, 1(rs3889108); STX1B(rs140820592); ELOVL7(rs1867598); POLRMTP1(rs148534175); HLA-DRB1(rs2647062); RAB25(rs34372695); CTSD(rs1293298); NUCKS1(rs3805); BAG3(rs144814361); IGSF9B(rs3802920); BICD1(rs77669894); SLC2A13(rs28370664); MCCC1(rs140278703); TMEM175(rs34884217); GCH1(rs11158026); FAM47E:FAM47E-STBD1:FAM47E-STBD1(rs12643261); SNCA(rs10516839); KANSL1(rs113564729); ZNF608(rs6875262); RIT2(rs12456492); RSL24D1P1(rs9468195)
Brolin et al., 2022	PD: 929, HC: 935; Replication:NA	GWAS, meta-analysis	(rs12771445)
Le Guen et al., 2021	PD: 6451 (male), 3551 (male proxy cases), HC: 251,229; Replication: PD: 1027, HC: 1147	Meta-analysis	(rs111841435); (rs28602900); (rs7066890); (rs11796528); (rs41306249); (rs28602900)
Chang et al., 2017	PD: 20,184, HC: 397,324; Replication: PD:5851 , HC: 5866	Meta-analysis	MICU3(rs591323); BAG3(rs117896735); DLG2(rs3793947); MIR4697(rs329648); LRRK2(rs76904798); OGFOD2(rs11060180); GCH1(rs11158026); TMEM229B(rs1555399); VPS13C(rs2414739); ZNF646, KAT8(rs14235); ARHGAP27, CRHR1, KANSL1, SPPL2C, MAPT, STH(rs17649553); SYT4(rs12456492); LSM7(rs62120679); DDRGK1(rs8118008); ITPKB(rs4653767); IL1R2(rs34043159); SCN3A(rs353116); SATB1(rs4073221); NCKIPSD, CDC71(rs12497850); ALAS1, TLR9, DNAH1, BAP1, PHF7, NISCH, STAB1, ITIH3, ITIH4(rs143918452); ANK2, CAMK2D(rs78738012); ELOVL7(rs2694528); ZNF184(rs9468199); CTSD(rs2740594); SORBS3, PDLIM2, C8orf58, BIN3(rs2280104); (rs10929159);

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
			(rs67460515); (rs10463554); (rs17767294); (rs943437); (rs2921073); (rs2296887); (rs9568188); (rs9516970); (rs8017172); (rs316619); (rs5910); (rs6416935); GBA(rs35749011); NUCKS1, SLC41A1(rs823118); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); TMEM163, CCNT2(rs6430538); STK39(rs1474055); MCCC1(rs12637471); TMEM175, DGKQ(rs34311866); FAM200B, CD38(rs11724635); FAM47E(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356182); HLA-DRB6, HLA-DQA1(rs9275326); KLHL7, NUPL2, GPNMB(rs199347); SH3GL2(rs13294100); FAM171A1(rs10906923); GALC(rs8005172); COQ7(rs11343); TOX3(rs4784227)
Tirozzi et al., 2023	PD: at least 37,688, HC: at least 18,618; Replication:NA	GWAS	(rs356219); (rs1372518)
Pankratz et al., 2012	PD: 4,238, HC: 4,239; Replication: PD: 3,738, HC: 2,111	Meta-analysis	SNCA(rs356220); intergenic(rs9917256); BST1(rs4698412); CNKSR3(rs2275336); LOC642072(rs2395163); GBA(rs12726330); intergenic(rs6430538); DGKQ(rs11248060); intergenic(rs1296028); SH3GL2(rs1536076); intergenic(rs11026412); SLC2A13(rs10877840); intergenic(rs10519131); POL3S(rs11865038); WNT3(rs199515); RIT2(rs12456492)
Saad et al., 2011	PD: 1039, HC: 1984; Replication: PD: 3232, HC: 7064	GWAS	SNCA(rs356220)
Vacic et al., 2014	PD: 1130, HC: 2611; Replication: PD: 306, HC: 2583	GWAS	LRRK2(rs1442190); MAPT(rs17577094); GBA(rs1630500)
Kim et al., 2024	57,893 European ancestry cases, 1,505,102 European ancestry controls, 7,046 East Asian ancestry cases, 176,756 East Asian ancestry controls, 2,440 Hispanic or Latin American cases, 582,220 Hispanic or Latin American controls, 288 African ancestry cases, 193,985 African ancestry controls; Replication:NA	GWAS and Meta-analysis	(rs12497850); (rs6803771); (rs7636454); (rs11729193); (rs75072999); (rs34311866); (rs11941559); (rs7673321); (rs6854006); (rs356182); (rs1372518); (rs79214011); (rs75541595); (rs1867598); (rs246815); (rs9461359); (rs9468199); (rs12528068); (rs9487736); (rs41286192); (rs34096562); (rs11783129); (rs13294100); (rs13664); (rs2178923); (rs4910150); (rs6592142); (rs3802920); (rs73273590); (rs34773022); (rs10847864); (rs1078514); (rs1956438); (rs11158026); (rs1561758); (rs1870293); (rs850731); (rs8327); (rs713522); (rs199453); (rs61169879); (rs8091977); (rs55818311); (rs6060983); (rs1736020); (rs2248244); (rs11164870); (rs114138760); (rs146143531); (rs35682329); (rs10737170); (rs35161831); (rs148163066); (rs17411858); (rs28370650); (rs17442721); (rs17443414); (rs190807041); (rs11177328); (rs10513789); (rs71314284); (rs16843452); (rs4698412); (rs1550556); (rs4859676); (rs114762839); (rs79483792); (rs78327649); (rs145138919); (rs13117519); (rs7434295); (rs34133110); (rs3104776); (rs113487377); (rs11650438); (rs665268); (rs62066707); (rs62053943); (rs7225082); (rs34724124); (rs148528915); (rs77483524); (rs4485435); (rs4588066); (rs75344947); (rs4815573); (rs73174657); (rs10775809); (rs12734374); (rs10903); (rs12118655); (rs4653767); (rs1326293); (rs11683001); (rs57891859); (rs12987123); (rs6808178); (rs199351); (rs1293298);

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
			(rs6469271); (rs10756905); (rs6476434); (rs118117788); (rs6658353); (rs4421827); (rs1108439); (rs16833168); (rs6806917); (rs1442190); (rs6582586); (rs78299420); (rs28659953); (rs11610045); (rs1127021); (rs8018800); (rs8012377); (rs112288215); (rs28648524); (rs2251086); (rs11956597); (rs9393826)
Foo et al., 2017	PD: 779, HC: 13,227; Replication: PD: 5,125, HC: 17,604	GWAS	MCCC1, DCUN1D1, LAMP3(rs2270968); SNCA, GPRIN3(rs8180209); LRRK2, SLC2A13, C12orf40(rs1384236)
Nalls et al., 2019	PD: 15,056, 18,618 proxy cases, HC: 449,056; Replication: PD: 22,632, HC: 968,735	meta-GWAS and PRS	CHRN1(rs12600861); RETREG3(rs12951632); UBTF(rs2269906); FAM171A2(rs850738); CRHR1(rs62053943); CRHR1(rs117615688); WNT3(rs11658976); BRIP1(rs61169879); DNAH17(rs666463); ASXL3(rs1941685); RIT2(rs12456492); MEX3C(rs8087969); SPPL2B(rs55818311); CRLS1(rs77351827); DYRK1A(rs2248244); SEMA4A(rs35643925); TMEM163(rs4954162); SNCA(rs356228); SNCA(rs356203); ZNF608(rs6875262); SLC44A4(rs9267659); FGD4(rs181609621); LRRK2(rs117073808); CNTN1(rs141128804); GXYLT1(rs138017112); ITGA8(rs896435); GBF1(rs10748818); BAG3(rs72840788); INPP5F(rs117896735); RNF141(rs7938782); DLG2(rs12283611); IGSF9B(rs3802920); LRRK2(rs76904798); LRRK2(rs34637584); SCAF11(rs7134559); HIP1R(rs10847864); FBRSL1(rs11610045); CAB39L(rs9568188); MBNL2(rs4771268); MIPOL1(rs12147950); GCH1(rs11158026); RPS6KL1(rs3742785); GALC(rs979812); VPS13C(rs2251086); SYT17(rs6497339); CD19(rs2904880); SETD1A(rs11150601); NOD2(rs6500328); SCARB2(rs6825004); FAM47E(rs4101061); FAM47E-STBD1(rs6854006); SNCA(rs356182); SNCA(rs5019538); CAMK2D(rs13117519); CLCN3(rs62333164); ELOVL7(rs1867598); PAM(rs26431); C5orf24(rs11950533); LOC100131289(rs4140646); KCNIP3(rs2042477); HLA-DRB5(rs112485576); TMEM163(rs57891859); FYN(rs997368); SATB1(rs73038319); GPNMB(rs199351); IP6K2(rs12497850); CTSB(rs1293298); MED12L(rs11707416); BIN3(rs2280104); MCCC1(rs10513789); GAK(rs873786); TMEM175(rs34311866); BST1(rs4698412); LCORL(rs34025766); PMVK(rs114138760); KRTCAP2(rs35749011); GBAP1(rs76763715); FCGR2A(rs6658353); VAMP4(rs11578699); NUCKS1(rs823118); RAB29(rs11557080); ITPKB(rs4653767); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); KCNS3(rs76116224); TRIM40(rs9261484); MAP4K4(rs11683001); RIMS1(rs12528068); STK39(rs1474055); RPS12(rs75859381); LINC00693(rs6808178); GS1-124K5.11(rs76949143); KPNA1(rs55961674); FGF20(rs620513); SPTSSB(rs1450522); FAM49B(rs2086641); SH3GL2(rs13294100); SH3GL2(rs10756907); UBAP2(rs6476434); GXYLT1(rs144755950); MAP3K14(rs17686238); CRHR1(rs9912362); MAPT-

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
			AS1(rs7221167); KANSL1(rs7225002); NSF(rs199453); DDRGK1(rs2295545); CASC16(rs3104783); CHD9(rs10221156); PRS(PRS (1805)); PRS(PRS (90))
Foo et al., 2020	6,724 East Asian ancestry cases, 24,851 East Asian ancestry controls; Replication:57,545 European ancestry cases, 1,868,816 European ancestry controls, 988 Japanese ancestry cases, 2,521 Japanese ancestry controls	GWAS and Meta-analysis	SNCA(rs6826785); PARK16(rs6679073); MCCC1(rs2292056); ITPKB(rs16846351); DLG2(rs12278023); FYN(rs1887316); RIT2(rs4130047); BST1(rs6449168); SV2C(rs246814)
Simon-Sanchez et al., 2009	PD: 1,713, HC: 3,978; Replication: PD: 3,361, HC: 4,573	GWAS	SNCA(rs2736990); NSF(rs199533); MAPT, C17orf69, KIAA1267, LOC644246(rs393152)
Sakaue et al., 2021	2,638 European ancestry cases, 477,380 European ancestry controls, 340 East Asian ancestry cases, 175,788 East Asian ancestry controls; Replication: NA	GWAS	(rs35643925); (rs356220)
Blauwendraat et al., 2020	PD: 1,588, HC: 7,584; Replication: PD: 1,194, HC: 13,901	GWAS	SNCA(rs356219)
Lill et al., 2012	PD: 2,197, HC: 2,061; Replication: Up to 98,080 European and Asian ancestry individuals	Meta-analysis	LRRK2(rs34778348); LRRK2(rs1491942); GAK, DGKQ(rs11248060); MAPT, STH(H1H2 (chr17:42131818–41149582)); SNCA(rs356219); SNCA(rs6532194)
Spencer et al., 2011	PD: 1,705, HC: 5,175; Replication: PD: 1,039, HC: 1,984	GWAS	MAPT(rs8070723) SNCA(rs356220)
Nalls et al., 2014	PD:13,708, HC: 95,282; Replication: PD: 5,353, HC:5,551	Meta-analysis	CCDC62(rs11060180); GCH1(rs11158026); TMEM229B(rs1555399); VPS13C(rs2414739); BCKDK, STX1B(rs14235); MAPT(rs17649553); RIT2(rs12456492); SPPL2B(rs62120679); DDRGK1(rs8118008); FGF20(rs591323); GBA, SYT11(rs35749011); NUCKS1, RAB7L1(rs823118); SIPA1L2(rs10797576); ACMSD, TMEM163(rs6430538); STK39(rs1474055); MCCC1(rs12637471); TMEM175, GAK, DGKQ(rs34311866); BST1(rs11724635); SCARB2, FAM47E(rs6812193); SNCA(rs356182); HLA-DQB(rs9275326); GPNMB(rs199347); INPP5F(rs117896735); DLG2(rs3793947); MIR4697(rs329648); LRRK2(rs76904798)
Pan et al., 2023	PD: 1,972, HC: 2,478; Replication: PD: 8,209, HC: 9,454	GWAS	(rs421016); (rs823118); (rs11557080); (rs34594498); (rs34778348); (rs11158026); (rs2251086); (rs61204179); (rs10513789); (rs4698412); (rs356182); (rs997368)

Study characteristics			Genetic data
Authors	Sample size	Study type	Nearest gene and Associated SNP/variant
Bandres-Ciga et al., 2019	PD: 4,639, HC: 2,949; Replication: NA	GWAS	SNCA(rs356182); LRRK2(rs190807041); KANSL1, MAPT(rs113434679); HLA-DQB1(rs9275152); CRHR1(rs62053943);
Ibanez et al., 2017	PD: 829, HC: 432	PRS	PRS (16)
Sia et al., 2021	PD: 333, HC: 25,313	PRS	PRS (6)
Chairta et al., 2021	PD: 235, HC: 464	PRS	PRS (12)

General discussion

This review aimed to report the genetic factors that are associated with the disease risk. The resulting data suggest that many genes and genetic variants might be related to PD. Although various SNP associations exist in certain populations, there is some overlap between different studies and populations. For example, SNP rs1630500 was found to be associated with PD risk in a study carried out in the Fox Insight cohort (Rahman et al., 2023) and a study carried out in an Ashkenazi Jewish population (Vacic et al., 2014). It was also observed that SNPs in some genes, such as *SH3GL2* and *LMNA*, are frequently associated with PD as more than one variation associated with PD is located within these genes (Rahman et al., 2023).

Some studies were carried out in specific and small populations, while other studies combined different available data and performed meta-analyses. A study in a specific population has the limitation of a small sample size but simultaneously has the advantage of discovering something unique for the studied population. Large GWAS in combined populations (e.g., European) or meta-analysis studies enable the discovery of stronger and additional variants associated with PD by increasing the sample size and, thus, the accuracy of the study. PRS studies were also performed on PD and are equally essential as they combine the small effect of multiple genetic variants, capturing the overall genetic background of complex diseases. All these variants should be studied further, and the strongest might be useful as candidate predictive biomarkers for PD.

2.2.4 Machine learning approaches for PD risk modelling

Study selection

Within the Rayyan software our keywords “machine learning”, “artificial intelligence”, “sensitivity”, “specificity”, “area under the curve”, “AUC” alongside “risk” and “prodromal” yielded 71 and 15 records respectively. Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where necessary, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. Studies comparing PD with other diseases such as Alzheimer’s Disease, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy, or Lewy Body disease were dropped to minimize the analysis complexity. Also, genetic studies were excluded and can be found in the “Genetic Markers” subdomain of this deliverable, resulting in 13 records in total.

Table 5 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Briefly, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study participants were people with PD before being diagnosed, or people with prodromal PD
AND
Study data analysis was performed using machine learning tools i.e., machine learning models, including at least train/test or train/validation sets, and contained metrics of ML model performance, such as the Area Under the Curve (AUC), sensitivity, and specificity.

We did not restrict our search to studies utilizing digital technologies as our aim was to provide a comprehensive review of commonly used machine learning approaches for identifying people at risk of developing PD.

Table 5 Selection criteria for machine learning and PD risk

Item	Definition
Population	Incident PD, or prodromal PD
Analysis	Machine learning approach
Results	At least one model performance metric

Study characteristics

Six studies analysed open-source data (e.g., biobanks, PPMI or other data-sources) and the remainder employed their own experimental design and data collection methods.

Among these, five aimed to predict future diagnosis of PD (incident PD), monitoring participants for periods ranging from 5 to 10 years. Eight papers predicted the presence of prodromal symptoms. The latter included people with REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD; 5 papers) and people with Idiopathic Hyposmia (IH; 3 papers).

The included studies recruited people with PD with range of mean age 60 to 81; one study did not report age, but stratified participants in 10-year age bands.

A few studies failed to report important clinico-demographic information. Indicatively, one study did not report sex, seven studies did not report disease duration, all but two studies did not report PD subtype, and six studies did not provide information for the reported motor severity score (MDS-UPDRS-III).

Measurements and ML approaches

Table 6 summarizes the models and approaches used in the included studies, highlighting the use of various input features such as voice (five studies) and kinematic data from wearables (five studies).

The most common model used to predict PD risk was Random Forest (RF), utilised in seven studies. Other models used were Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes Classifiers (NB), Binary Logistic Regressors (LR), Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), XGBoost, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM), and General least squares linear models (GLSLM). Survival probability analysis was performed by one study using Survival Random Forest.

Input datasets are often plagued by collinearities, stemming from the utilisation of high dimensional datasets. To mitigate this risk, ten of the selected studies opted for feature selection, before applying any ML algorithm. This approach aims to improve model accuracy and interpretability of the findings. In addition, all but one study documented a validation strategy for evaluating the robustness of the model results.

Table 6 Studies about machine learning and PD risk

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Arora et al., 2018	Voice, balance, gait, finger tapping, RT, rest and postural tremor	RBD=104, PD=334, HC=84	RBD=64.5, PD=66.1, HC=66.3	RBD=88, PD=63, HC=67	RF	5 different ML models & majority voting	10-fold CV, LOSO, LOO	-	HC vs RBD: 91.9, PD vs RBD: 87.5	HC vs RBD: 90.0, PD vs RBD: 90.1		Smartphones and ML can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Posture, rest tremor and voice data provide the most discriminatory power
Arora et al., 2021	Voice (337 voice features)	RBD=112, PD=335, HC=92	RBD=68.4, PD=69.5, HC=68.5	RBD=87, PD=61, HC=79	RF	RF feature importance	LOSO	-	HC vs RBD:60.7, PD vs RBD:74.9	HC vs RBD:67.6, PD vs RBD:73.2		Smartphone voice signals and ML can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Scores were lower when only one recording per patient was used
Cavallo et al., 2019	MDS related upper limb tasks (48 features)	IH=30, PD=30, HC=30	IH=66, PD=67.9, HC=65.2	IH=70, PD=83, HC=83	SVM, RF, NB	A) Pairwise comparisons. (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	10-fold cross validation	SVM=71, RF=79, NB=70	SVM=71, RF=79, NB=80	SVM=86, RF=89, NB=70	Precision : SVM=72, RF=80, NB=72 F: SVM=71, RF=80, NB=71	Upper limb features discriminate among IH, RBD and HC. Best model performance was achieved when IH was grouped with HC

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Jeancolas et al., 2022	Voice features	RBD=41, PD=117, HC=98	(M/F) RBD=68.2/- , PD=63.8/63 .7, HC=60/59. 3	RBD=100, PD=64, HC=55	SVM	-	-	Male: PD vs HC=89, RBD vs HC=63, RBD vs HC*=70 , Female: PD vs HC=70 *RBD with motor symptoms	Male: PD vs HC=86, RBD vs HC=59, RBD vs HC*=73 Female: PD vs HC=70 *RBD with motor symptoms	Male: PD vs HC=92, RBD vs HC=67, RBD vs HC*=67 Female: PD vs HC=70 *RBD with motor symptoms		Voice related features can discriminate among RBD, PD and HC. Model performance is better in men than women. Model performance worsened when phone mic features are used
Rovini et al., 2018	Lower limb features (23 features)	IH=30, PD=30, HC=30	IH=66.0, PD=67.9, HC=65.2	IH=70, PD=83, HC=83	SVM, RF, NB	A) Pairwise comparisons (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	10-fold cross validation	SVM=69, RF=77, NB=76	SVM=69, RF=77, NB=76	SVM=84, RF=88, NB=88	Precision : SVM=74, RF=77, NB=76 F: SVM=71, RF=77, NB=76	Models trained on lower limb features can discriminate among IH, PD and HC. Models composed by both lower limbs provided better performance (compared to right and left separately).

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Rovini et al., 2019	Upper and Lower limb features (71 features)	IH=15, PD=15, HC=15	IH=66.5, PD=66.6, HC=64.9	IH=67, PD=47, HC=73	SVM, RF	A) Pairwise comparisons. (Wilcoxon; p<0.05) B) Spearman correlation to identify collinearities	5-fold cross validation	SVM=78, RF=91	SVM=78, RF=91	SVM=89, RF=96	Precision : SVM=80, RF=93 F: SVM=79, RF=92	Upper and lower limb features can discriminate among IH, PD and HC. The best discrimination achieved when PD were compared to HC. Models composed of both upper and lower limbs (rather than separately) provided better performance
Rusz et al., 2018	Voice features (11 features)	RBD=40, PD*=25, HC=25 <i>*de-novo PD</i>	RBD=66.4, PD*=62.3, HC= -	RBD=90, PD*=87, HC=-	Binary LR	A) Fisher least squares difference, B) consistency (r>.8) between recording devices	LOSO	-	PD vs HC=75 PD vs RBD=67 HC vs RBD=70	PD vs HC=79 PD vs RBD=71 HC vs RBD=65	AUC: PD vs HC=85 PD vs RBD=78 HC vs RBD=69	The model showing the best discriminatory performance was composed by 3 features
Schalkamp et al., 2023	Genetics, lifestyle, biochemical, prodromal symptoms and accelerometer data	PD=158, Prodromal PD=113 HC=matched	PD=67.6, Prodromal PD=69.3 HC=67.6	PD=61, Prodromal PD=69 HC=6961	LASSO, Survival RF	LASSO feature importance	Nested 5-fold cross validation	-	-	-	AUPRS: PD vs HC=78, Prodromal PD vs HC=78	Accelerometry was the most important predictor among clinical, demographic, genetic data, and prodromal features. Sleep quality and

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
												duration are reduced in PD, with a unique reduction in acceleration and more severe sleep deterioration compared to other diseases.
Allwright et al., 2023	Demographics, level of activity, clinical, medical records, blood assays	334062 (of which 2719PD)	60.2	PD=62, HC=44	XGBOOST, SVM, RF, LR	SHAP value importance to get the 50 most recurrent across 100 iterations	80-20 train-test	-	-	-	AUC=67	XGBoost outperformed the rest of the models. Being male, having bad overall health rating, slow walking pace, elevated IGF-1, lymphocyte count, and neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio were the highest risk factors.
Yuan et al., 2021	demographics, diagnoses other than PD, timings between diagnoses	PD=8000, HC=42000 *2 independent data-sources	72-73	PD=58-61, HC=59-61	LR, RNN	Penalized feature selection	5-fold cross validation	-	-	-	AUC: LR=80, RNN=87	ML can identify the risk of converting to gait or tremor-specific PD. Participants were stratified into those developing gait or tremor symptoms first.

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
Schrag et al., 2019	Symptoms and lifestyle factors	PD=8166, HC=46755	-	PD=60, HC=59	Backward Multivariate LR	Backward feature selection	70-30 train-test	-	43	99	PPV=37, NPV=99, AUC=80	Within a 5-year follow-up period, the algorithm predicted a future PD diagnosis correctly in 37 cases and predicted no future PD diagnosis in 99% of cases.
Karabayer et al., 2022	Clinical and risk factor features	292 participants (25 developed PD within 5 years)	PD=80-81, HC=81	N/A	LGDBM	N/A	5-fold cross validation				AUC: PD3*=82, PD5**=77 *Converted in 3 years, **Converted in 5 years	ML trained with clinical data can predict future PD diagnosis. Model predicted those who converted within 3 years more accurately than those converting within 5 or more years.
Rusz et al., 2021	Voice (7 features)	RBD=119, PD=110, HC=88	RBD=68.6, PD=67.4, HC=68.3	RBD=79, PD=74, HC=73	GLSLM	N/A	LOSO	-	PD vs HC=72, PD vs RBD=64, HC vs RBD=60	PD vs HC=72, PD vs RBD=64, HC vs RBD=60	AUC: PD vs HC=80, PD vs RBD=72, HC vs RBD=65	Voice features with ML can discriminate RBD and HC from PD. RBD was discriminated from HC with less discriminatory performance. Monopitch, prolonged pauses, and imprecise

Study Characteristics					Method			Model Performance				Key take-aways
Study	Measurements	Sample	Age	Male%	Models	Feature selection	Validation	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Other	
												consonants provided the best discriminatory power.

General Discussion

The aim of this review was to assess the effectiveness of machine learning to predict the risk of developing PD. The findings highlight the successful application of ML techniques in predicting both future PD diagnosis and prodromal PD diagnosis. Smartphone-based assessments, particularly focusing on voice signals and upper/lower limb features, demonstrate promising discriminatory power between people with PD, and prodromal PD (RBD or Hyposmia) and HC. Specifically, for the voice signals, gender differences are apparent, exhibiting better performance in men.

Noteworthy, to the best of our knowledge, only a limited number of recent studies delved into identifying important features for predicting incident PD. The rest of them focused on indirectly estimating PD risk, by predicting people who were clinically classified as prodromal PD.

Accelerometry emerges as a crucial tool for predicting incident PD, showcasing better performance in identifying incident PD and showcasing its potential for prodromal PD detection. Among the reviewed papers, (Schalkamp et al., 2023) stands out as particularly critical for the objectives of AI-PROGNOSIS. Leveraging multimodal data, including smartwatch accelerometry, from the UK Biobank cohort, this study accurately predicted PD onset up to seven years prior to the clinical diagnosis. Notably, accelerometry data unveil increases in acceleration particularly during sleep, which are distinct to PD and highlight the severity of sleep disturbances in PD compared to other conditions. Leveraging accelerometry data, use of ML algorithms successfully predicts future PD diagnosis and offers a potential tool in detecting populations that may be susceptible to neuroprotective trials and early PD management. They achieved this by augmenting data by splitting it into 30-second intervals and categorizing physical activity, enhancing the discriminatory performance of the predictive models.

We also encountered an additional critical study (Makarious et al., 2022) that did not pass our initial search criteria, due to its focus on unmedicated PD, rather than prodromal stages of the disease. Despite this, we consider the inclusion of this study in this discussion crucial, due to its exhaustive benchmarking of different ML approaches. This study used open-source data (Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative; PPMI and Parkinson's Disease Biomarker Program PDBP), aiming to predict PD utilizing UPSIT and genetic data. The machine learning models applied in its analysis constitute a super-set of the methods presented in the literature table of this sub-domain review. These include: LR, RF, AdaBoost, Gradient Boost, SGD, SVM, ML perceptron, KNN, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and XGBoost. Model performance was tested using the AUC method. UPSIT smell test score and Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) contributed most to the predictive power of the models.

2.2.5 Digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder and daytime somnolence

Study selection (for REM behaviour disorder)

Digital technology is rapidly advancing in the field of neurology, offering – among other things – new avenues for assessing sleep-related disorders in PD. This review section focuses on the digital assessment of REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD) and daytime somnolence, two prevalent non-motor symptoms in PD patients. We explore studies that utilize wearable sensors, smart devices, and mobile applications to monitor and evaluate these sleep disturbances. Such digital tools facilitate the continuous and objective monitoring of RBD and daytime somnolence in the patient's natural environment, enhancing the understanding of symptom patterns and severity. This approach not only supports clinical decisions but also ties in with the endeavour of identifying those at risk for PD.

Within the framework of the Rayyan application and the accompanying bibliography, we searched for the key words “REM” or “RBD”. The initial list of the results resulted in 30 different papers (REM 9, RBD 6, 15 both RBD and REM). Which resulted into 3 relevant papers as can be seen in the **Table 7**. Furthermore, we extended the initial keywords to include “sleep” which resulted in an extra 67 papers (97 in total), but no extra paper was eligible for selection; those are listed in **Table 8**.

Table 7 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Briefly, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study included participants diagnosed with PD and/or RBD
AND
The outcome of interest was the identification/classification of nights or patients with RBD
AND
Use of a wearable experimental device for passive data recording such as e.g., a smart watch or a motion sensor

Table 7 Selection criteria for digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder

Item	Definition
Population	Patients with PD and/or RBD
Outcome	Identify patients or nights with RBD
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

Table 8 Studies about digital assessments of REM behaviour disorder

Authors	Study aim	Sample size	Sensors used	Model	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
Dagay et al., 2023	Explore the feasibility and validity of a new wearable system for accurately measuring sleep at home.	29 PD, 21 HC	PSG and new wearable	n/a	Cohen's kappa, sensitivity	Agreement between the two systems reached Cohen's kappa (k) of 0.688 with agreement in each stage of: wake k = 0.701; N1 = 0.224; N2 = 0.584; N3 = 0.410; and rapid eye movement = 0.723. The system reliably detected rapid eye movement sleep without atonia with a sensitivity of 85.7%.	The results demonstrate that the system is valid, accurate and allows for the exploration of sleep at home.
F.Raschella et al., 2022	Classification of RBD patients with ML and actigraphy	26 PD of which 18 RBD, 18 HC	Actigraphy (and PSG for comparison)	Several machine learning classification algorithms (linear discriminant analysis; support vector machine logistic regression; nearest neighbour; Random Forest)	Accuracy	Accuracy of 92.9 ± 8.16% during in-clinic tests. When validated on home recordings in Parkinson's disease patients, accuracy reached 100% over a 2-week window, and was 94.4% in non-Parkinson's disease control patients.	Actigraphy allows for an accurate classification of RBD subjects.
Ko et al., 2022	Classification of sleep stages (Non-REM, REM and abnormal REM)	27 PD, 30 HC	Smartwatch (Asus VivoWatch BP)	k-means clustering	Accuracy of NREM/REM detection	Accuracy of 2-stage (NREM/REM) classification 68.88%, for the 3-stage classification (Light/Deep/REM) 64.02%)	The use of the smartwatch could enable detection of RBD, as exemplified by a higher percentage of abnormal REM-sleep experienced by PwPD as compared to controls (8.8 vs. 1.6%, p=0.04).

Study selection (for daytime somnolence)

Within the framework of the Rayyan application and the accompanying bibliography, we searched for the keywords: “somnolence” or “daytime” or “sleep”. The selection criteria are outlined in the **Table 9**. The initial list of the results provided 0 publications for “somnolence”, 6 for “daytime” and 97 for “sleep”. After an assessment of the 103 publications none was considered relevant, according to the following criteria:

Study included participants diagnosed with PD and episodes of daytime somnolence
AND
The outcome of interest was the identification of periods with daytime somnolence
AND
Use of a wearable experimental device for passive data recording such as e.g., a smart watch or a motion sensor

Table 9 Selection criteria for digital assessments of daytime somnolence and PD risk

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients with episodes of daytime somnolence
Outcome	Identify periods of daytime somnolence
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

We used the same keywords within “Google Scholar,” and we identified 348 relevant publications. After careful assessment of the studies, a total of 3 papers were included in the systematic review a list of which is presented in **Table 10**.

Table 10 Studies about digital assessments of daytime somnolence

Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Sensors used	Model performance metric	Model performance scores	Key take-away
Kotschet et al., 2014	PD 68, HC 30	To identify immobility via a wearable device	Parkinson's KinetiGraph system (PKG)	Concordance with PSG	There was concordance between immobility and PSG scores in 85.6% of the 1805 two-minute epochs: 1206 epochs were negative for sleep by both methods and 342 epochs were positive for sleep by both methods ($p < 0.0001$, Chi Squared test).	Immobility (or proportion of time immobile), as measured by the PKG, is a useful surrogate measure of daytime sleep or at least somnolence in PD patients.
Höglund et al., 2021	PD 52	To investigate the relationship between daytime sleepiness and other non-motor and motor fluctuations in people with PD	Parkinson's KinetiGraph system (PKG)	Correlation of PKG data with sleepiness as reported by ESS and patient diary (KSS)	n/a	PKG data were weakly correlated with diary data. The fluctuation score (calculated using PKG-measurements) was the only PKG variable that correlated with daytime sleepiness.
Bolitho et al., 2013	PD 85, HC 21	To explore actigraphy as a measure of napping and its relation to performance on neuropsychological tests	Wrist actiwatch (minimittter Actiwatch Spectrum)	Correlations between excessive daytime napping as measured by actigraphy and neuropsychological tests	N/A	Patients with PD reported significantly greater number of nap bouts as well as time spent napping in the day, compared to healthy age matched controls. Patients with PD who exhibited excessive napping through the day had poorer performance on neuropsychological tests.

General discussion

In this review, we focussed on research on identification of RBD and daytime somnolence that rely on gathering data passively, i.e., via body-worn sensors such as motion sensors or smartwatches. Hence, articles detailing algorithms to detect RBD using only traditional polysomnography (PSG) were excluded. Of the included articles for RBD detection, there is excellent diagnostic sensitivity and congruence with traditional PSG, when using only sensor-derived data (Oz et al., 2023; Raschella et al., 2022). These systems determine either the presence or the absence of RBD, the identification of different sleep stages seems to remain a bigger challenge with one study reporting an accuracy of around 64% (Ko et al., 2022). Encouragingly, these findings demonstrate that reliable RBD detection is possible without the use of traditional PSG, which seems relevant especially in the prodromal stages of PD and in identifying target populations for disease modifying studies.

Daytime somnolence is most commonly assessed using questionnaire data (e.g., the Epworth Sleepiness Scale). Currently, there are no studies aiming at directly investigating or quantifying daytime somnolence. Two of the studies inferred daytime sleepiness from episodes of immobility during the day (Bolitho et al., 2013; Kotschet et al., 2014), one study found that only dyskinesias as measured by actigraphy correlated with self-reported measures of daytime sleepiness (Höglund et al., 2021). In the latter study, there is evidence that increased daytime sleepiness is associated with worse cognitive performance. Taken together, these findings suggest that there is a need of an extensive and dedicated study for assessment of digital biomarkers in daytime somnolence as promising results have been shown in other (related) diseases, such as Lewy body dementia (Wang et al., 2022) for the development of reliable sensors to directly assess daytime somnolence in PD, as this relates to aspects of safety (e.g. driving a car) and could also be related to disease progression, as exemplified by the association between daytime sleepiness and worse cognitive performance.

2.2.6 Summary, unmet needs, and research opportunities

Within the scope of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, we focused on PD risk with regards to clinical, demographic, lifestyle and genetic factors. We also reviewed the potential role of machine learning approaches and digital sensors in determining PD risk. The results of the review alongside the derived unmet needs and arisen research opportunities are outlined in **Table 11**.

To determine the clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors that may influence the risk of developing PD, there are predominantly general population and prodromal PD longitudinal studies that focus on phenoconversion to PD as an outcome. The resulting data suggest that many non-motor symptoms (particularly daytime somnolence and RBD), prodromic motor symptoms related to bradykinesia and demographic and lifestyle factors as well as comorbid diseases may increase the risk of developing PD. To determine the genetic markers related to PD risk, investigators use their own generated data or re-analysis of existing genetic databases on PD patients using GWAS, meta-analysis, and PRS studies. The resulting data suggest that many genes and genetic variants might be related to PD.

Machine learning approaches have proved useful in determining the risk of PD phenoconversion in both general populations and prodromal cohorts. Accelerometry data as well as clinical, genetics and lifestyle features are relevant factors to be included in successful models. Digital sensors have demonstrated their role in diagnosing RBD as they highly correlate with PSG data which is currently the gold standard to confirm diagnosis. Both RBD and daytime somnolence are prodromal non motor symptoms and thus can be useful tools to detect prodromic populations.

Table 11 Unmet needs and research opportunities in PD Risk.

Unmet needs	Research opportunities
Predicting the risk or phenoconversion to Parkinson's disease	
<p>To date, most investigation regarding clinical PD risk are based on population studies that are very costly due to the relatively low incidence of PD.</p>	<p>Taking advantage of the widespread use of mobile phones, the AI-PROGNOSIS project will design applications like mAI-Health to detect prodromal and incidental PD. This will be less costly in terms of economic resources, time, etc. than the usual population studies.</p>
<p>Phenotyping prodromal PD subtypes is likely to be important and will help delineate other variables that may influence if and when individuals phenoconvert to clinical PD.</p>	<p>Diagnosing the prodromal phase of PD with high sensitivity and specificity will inevitably lead to a change in paradigm as our current concept of prodromal PD, in fact, becomes PD (Postuma et al., 2018). In the AI-PROGNOSIS project we aim to consider prodromal subtypes using machine learning models to define subtype-specific markers, thus increasing the diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD.</p>
<p>PD risk to prodromal PD to full clinical PD remains unknown. Further stratification of PD risk states and PD prodromal states would be helpful to select populations that are closer to phenoconversion.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project will use machine learning approaches to predict PD phenoconversion. Self-reported symptoms may complement objectively assessed signs in the diagnosis of prodromal PD and thus the AI prognosis mAI health app plans to combine these inputs</p>
<p>Genetic studies in a specific population are less costly but limited by small sample size while large GWAS or meta-analysis increase the sample size but are more costly. PRS studies capture the overall genetic background of complex diseases but are also expensive and harder to interpret.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project includes genetic studies and machine learning models with large numbers of variables for subjects at risk of developing PD that will be followed clinically and through DAT imaging.</p>
<p>As the field of genetic risk factors advances, the genetic risk load and one's individual genetic pathways that contribute to neurodegeneration need to be considered. Gene environment interactions may modulate the effects of many of the risk and prodromal factors that have been established in this review and need to be investigated further.</p>	
Machine learning approaches	
<p>The current Bayesian model for predicting PD³ is based on the independence of the established risk and prodromal markers. However, some of these (e.g., physical inactivity, diabetes or hypotension) may be causally linked to each other or co-occur because of a common pathological process (e.g., RBD and hyposmia). Further investigation of marker clustering and interactions with demographic and genetic</p>	<p>Machine learning approaches can analyse marker clustering and assess interactions with demographic and genetic variables thus improving diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD</p>

³ www.movementdisorders.org/pdcalculator

variables will probably improve diagnostic accuracy of prodromal PD.	
Digital assessment of RBD and Daytime Somnolence	
Studies on the development of reliable sensors that detect REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder in selected populations is needed due to its importance as a prodromal marker. Continuous markers that signal faster progression or advanced prodromal PD states would aid in selecting populations and designing neuroprotective clinical trials.	Digital biomarkers for RBD as designed in the AI-PROGNOSIS project can provide these accurate measures that provide continuous monitoring along time and thus provide prodromal progression markers

2.3 Parkinson's disease progression and response to medication

2.3.1 Introduction

PD is a neurodegenerative disease and thus, by definition, progresses and the cardinal motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, rigidity, resting tremor and gait problems worsen. With time, the non-motor symptom burden (i.e., dysautonomia, sleep and mood disturbances, cognitive deficits) also increases, effectively leading to diminished quality of life. In addition, PD is a highly heterogeneous disorder and has multiple subtypes stratified according to presentation, medication responsiveness, and progression.

Identifying these subtypes is a priority as it can help estimate disease course and survival, providing a more accurate prognosis at the time of diagnosis. This is significant because PD has a very heterogeneous course in the early to middle stages, with different rates of progression and levels of disability. Initially, subtyping focuses on motor features (Postuma, Fereshtehnejad 2017) but new approaches suggest subtypes defined by both motor and non-motor features, with ongoing refinement through the incorporation of data from imaging, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and genetic biomarkers may be more useful.

Regarding medication response, substitutive dopaminergic therapy effectively treats PD, but as the disease progresses, two key problems arise: 1) the response to medication changes and 2) some symptoms that are resistant to dopaminergic therapy can develop (i.e., imbalance, dysarthria, posterior cognitive dysfunction). As medication response changes due to continuous nigrostriatal degeneration, PD becomes a fluctuating disease. After a mean average of 5-6 years, most patients will encounter times where they do not get benefit from dopaminergic therapy called "off periods". During these episodes, which can happen from one to many times a day and for a variable amount of time (from minutes to hours), patients can experience the spectrum of Parkinsonian motor and nonmotor symptoms. At some point in disease progression (about 5.5 years), most patients will also show adverse effects from PD treatment and develop involuntary movements that remind one of chorea and are called dyskinesias. These usually occur in the areas most affected by PD and thus occur in the face, neck, limbs, or trunk.

PD progression varies among individuals, encompassing slower and faster-progressing forms and more disabling motor fluctuations and dyskinesias.

This review focuses on demographic, clinical, and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression and response to medication. We also focus on the genetic aspects, specifically on those genes with a poorer prognosis in the evolution of the disease. Furthermore, common machine learning approaches are reviewed for predicting progression factors, alongside digital assessments of symptoms most closely linked to disease evolution: tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesia, posture, balance, and cognition.

2.3.2 Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Study selection

The purpose of this part of the review is to summarise studies that identify clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors that predict or determine PD progression, more specifically, those that predict or determine changes in:

- Motor impairment (including freezing and dysphagia)
- Non-motor impairment (including cognition and hallucinations)
- Disability (including falls and functional impairment)
- Medication (e.g., increase in the Levodopa Equivalent Dose)

Only publications reporting validated clinical scales were included. Moreover, studies were required to report longitudinal data with a minimum of 3 months follow-up. Studies focusing on predictive fluid and imaging biomarkers were excluded as they are not in the scope of our project. The paper selection criteria are outlined in **Table 12**.

Within the bounds of the Rayyan software, the following key words were used: “Progression” OR “Demographics” OR “Lifestyle” OR “Diabetes” OR “Uric acid” OR “Urban/rural/rurality” OR “Employment” OR “Exercise” OR “Diet” OR “Pesticides” OR “Agriculture/agricultural” OR “Small particles” OR “Farmers” alongside the following keywords: “Prognosis/prognostic” OR “Prediction/predictors” OR “Subtyping/subtypes” OR “Progression”. Using the above keywords, 71 papers were identified and subsequently screened by three independent reviewers. Abstracts and, where required, the full article were read to confirm the articles' eligibility and extract the relevant information. A total of 31 articles fulfilled the eligibility criteria. Most of the papers were excluded for having a cross-sectional design (as was the case of population-based studies) or focused on fluid or neuroimaging biomarkers.

Table 12 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Item	Definition
Population	Patients with diagnosed PD
Analysis	Longitudinal/prognostic associations between clinical, demographic and lifestyle features and PD progression
Results	Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Study characteristics

Out of the selected 31 papers (**Table 13**), 23 focus on clinical factors and 8 on lifestyle factors, and all of them consider demographic factors. A total of 12 papers report data derived from the PPMI data base. Except for 2 randomised clinical trials on the effects of exercise (Alagumoorthi et al., 2022; Lauhoff et al., 2013), all other papers report longitudinal, observational designs in cohorts from various countries, ranging from Norway (Hiorth YH et

al., 2017) to Spain (Santos et al., 2021) or China (Zhao et al., 2022; Ou et al., 2021). The reported follow-up period ranges from 3 months to up to 10 years.

Papers define PD progression in many different ways, but most commonly in terms of decline in motor symptoms as measured with the MDS-UPDRS-III and decline in cognition as measured with the MoCA (Ou et al., 2021). Other ways to define PD progression include time to reach disease milestones (Brumm et al., 2023), cognitive impairment measured with other scales such as the CDR sum of boxes (Meyers et al., 2021), onset of dementia (Compta et al., 2013), changes in the Hoehn & Yahr (H & Y) scale (Ren et al., 2021; Markaki et al., 2021), onset of freezing of gait (Wang et al., 2022) and functional dependency measured with ADL (activities of daily living) (Santos et al., 2021).

Table 13 Studies about clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with PD progression

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Alagumoorthi et al., 2022	L	192	0.25	To assess the effectiveness of Wii sports-based strategy training on risk of falling, falls, and quality of life in PD	Fall rate, Berg balance scale, Time up and go test, Parkinson's disease questionnaire 39	A 12 weeks exercise training using the Wii sports-based strategy decreases the number of fallers, fall rate, measures of risk of falling but did not alter the quality of life in adults with idiopathic PD
Aleksovski et al., 2018	C	254	4	Analyse the clinical progression of PIGD compared to TD	MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, Semantic Fluency, QUIP, GDS, STAI, and SCOPA-AUT	PIGD are characterized by more severe disease manifestations at diagnosis and greater cognitive progression, more frequent hallucinations, psychosis as well as features of dopamine-dysregulation syndrome (DDS) than TD patients
Athauda et al., 2022	L	167	3	Investigate the influence of type 2 diabetes (T2DM) on aspects of disease progression in PD	MDS-UPDRS II-III, NMSS, SE-ADL	T2DM is associated with faster disease progression in PD
Bruce et al., 2023	C	871	2-10	Identifying predictors of disease severity and progression	UPDRS-III, UPDRS-II, H&Y, MMSE	Modelling disease course using multiple objective assessments over an extended follow-up duration identified groups that more accurately reflect differences in PD course, prognosis, and outcomes than assessing single parameters over shorter intervals.
Brumm et al., 2023	C	376	5-10	Time-to-first-event analysis exploring whether baseline characteristics were associated with progression on 25 milestones across six domains ('walking and balance'; 'motor complications'; 'cognition'; 'autonomic dysfunction'; 'functional dependence'; 'activities of daily living')	Reaching 1 milestones (25 total milestones, chosen by a working group of clinical experts)	Baseline features predicting faster time to reaching a milestone included age, greater MDS-UPDRS total scores, higher GeDS-15 depression scores, lower dopamine transporter binding, and lower CSF total α -synuclein levels.
Bugalho et al., 2021	C	72	4	Address the evolution of motor symptoms (MS) and non-motor symptoms (NMS), predictors of motor, cognitive, disability, and health-related quality of life (HRQL) status	MoCA, MDS-UPDRS II and III, S&E, HY, and EuroQol (VAS and Index)	NMS progresses heterogeneously. The multivariate analysis has shown that S&E and NMSS Domain 4: perception / hallucinations scores are the stronger predictors of HRQL and cognitive dysfunction variation
Cehn et al., 2022	C	420	5	To identify whether the concurrent presence of olfactory dysfunction and probable RBD (pRBD) in PD	Progression in clinical/neuroimaging	Coexisting pRBD and OD (olfactive dysfunction) in patients with PD may be associated with faster progressions in motor measurement and in

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
				(Dualhit in PD, PD-DH) is associated with disease progression.		cognitive and autonomic symptoms, indicating PD-DH as a more aggressive subtype for PD
Chen et al., 2021	C	128	3-7	To develop a prognostic model for predicting mild cognitive impairment (MCI) in PD-RBD	PD-MCI yes or no	UPSIT, the mean signal and asymmetry index of the putamen on DAT imaging, p-tau/ α -syn and p-tau in CSF, and rs55785911 genotype were predictors of PD-MCI in PD-RBD patients
Chen et al., 2023	C	409	5	To assess the clinical features and explore the underlying biomarkers as predictors of CI in patients with newly diagnosed PD	Progression in clinical/neuroimaging	Cognitive impairment is predicted by: older age, hypertension, baseline lower MoCA scores, MDS-UPDRS III scores, and APOE status
Combs- Miller et al., 2019	L	74	2	To determine factors that predict motor, activity, and participation-based outcomes over two years in exercisers with PD.	Decline in motor activity (exercise behaviour) and quality of life (PDQ-39)	At least one exercise behaviour (minutes of exercise/week, peak rate of perceived exertion (RPE) and mode of exercise) was a significant predictor across most of the models. Younger age, male gender and lower disease severity also significantly predicted better outcomes over time.
Compta et al., 2013	C	27	1.5	To explore the relative and combined longitudinal CSF, neuropsychological and quantitative MRI associations with PD progression to dementia	Dementia yes/no (MDS criteria, MMSE < 24)	Combination of CSF amyloid- β , neuropsychological and cortical thickness biomarkers might provide a basis for dementia-risk stratification and progression monitoring in PD.
Constantini et al., 2023	L	426 de novo untreated PD patients	5	Examine the moderating effects of sex and uric acid on cognitive functions and psychiatric symptoms in early PD depending on motor symptom asymmetry	MDS-UPDRS III, MoCA, Geriatric Depression Scale (GeDS), State Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)	Lower serum UA appears to be associated with better memory performance in LPDf (female left dominant) patients. RPDm (males right dominant) patients exhibited particularly impaired cognitive and psychiatric outcomes.
Dou et al., 2022	C	415 de novo PD patients	5	Evaluate the progression of non-motor symptoms (cognitive impairment, RBD, and depression) in early PD	UPSIT score, GDS score, QUIP score, MoCA score, CSF A β , α -syn, t-tau, MDS-UPDRS total score, MDS-UPDRS Part III score, ESS score, RBDSQ score, and level of LEDD.	RBD and education levels were associated with depression in PD. Olfactory impairment may be a significant predictor predicting the occurrence of non-motor symptoms in PD, particularly cognitive decline.

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Fereshtehneja et al., 2017	C	421 de novo treatment-naive PD patients	>1	Identify distinct Parkinson's disease subtypes to predict progression and develop more efficient personalized care approaches	UPDRS I-III, Schwab and England ADL, MoCA	Diffuse malignant Parkinson's disease progressed faster in overall prognosis, with greater decline in cognition and in dopamine functional neuroimaging after an average of 2.7years
Hayete et al., 2017	C	244	7	To identify predictors of long-term motor and cognitive outcomes and rate of progression in PD	UPDRS III, MoCA, HY, S/E ADL, MMSE, BIDI-II, PDQ39, DAT brain imaging	Functional status (UPDRS parts I and II) at baseline is the strongest predictor of motor and cognitive decline. Older age at baseline was predictive of worse cognitive outcome. Lower DAT uptake at baseline, particularly in the caudate nuclei, and the presence of the minor allele of rs11724635 may also contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes.
Hiorth et al., 2017	C	181	7	To examine the frequency, development, concomitants, and risk factors of falls	Score > 1 on UPDRS item 13 (falling unrelated to freezing) or a score > 3 on UPDRS item 14 (falling related to freezing)	Higher age at baseline, PIGD phenotype at 1-year visit, and follow-up time were independent risk factors for incident falls during follow-up
Johansson et al., 2023	C	431	2	Assess the influence of subtyping (mild-motor predominant, intermediate, or diffuse-malignant) on clinical characteristics at baseline and on two-year progression	ROMP, MDS UPDRS I-IV, MoCA, BIDI-II, STAI, QUIP, PDQ39, VIPD-Q	Diffuse-malignant subtype motor symptoms are less lateralized and less confined to either the upper or lower extremities. Also was associated with increased severity of overall motor impairment and faster rates of progression but there were no between-subtype differences in the severity of resting tremor.
Lauhof et al., 2013	L	23	0.27	To establish the effect of a 6-week program of cycle ergometry training on exercise tolerance, balance, activities of daily living (ADL) and quality of life in individuals with Parkinson's disease. phase. Intervention consisted of 30-min cycle ergometry training once weekly.	Outcome measures included Six Minute Walk Test, Physiological Cost Index, Berg Balance Scale, Timed Up and Go Test (TUAG), ADL and mobility sections of UPDRS and the Parkinson's disease questionnaire (PDQ).	Not significantly influence exercise tolerance in this sample, but improved balance, functional ability and PD-related disability were noted
Li et al., 2023	L	501	5	Evaluate the risk of progression according to the proximity to	MMSE \leq 24 and UPDRS \geq 35	Pesticide exposure may be relevant for PD progression. There are implicated ten specific

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
				residential and workplace pesticides application.		pesticide active ingredients in faster PD motor and non-motor decline
Liu et al., 2021	C	923	3	Investigate the impact of RBD on the longitudinal change of motor and nonmotor symptoms in patients with PD	UPDRS I-IV, Purdue Pegboard test, Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, (HADS) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), MoCa, MMSE	RBD is not just a prodromal symptom. PD with RBD is associated with higher rates of levodopa unresponsive symptoms, including cognitive impairment, PIGD phenotype, gait freezing, and falls.
Markaki et al., 2021	L	224	3	Investigate the association of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels with motor and cognitive symptom progression	Hoehn and Yahr stage ≥ 3 and mild cognitive impairment	Nondiabetic PD patients with low as well as high HbA1c developed balance impairment and reached the endpoint H&Y ≥ 3 earlier than non-diabetic patients with euglycemia
Meyers et al., 2021	C	148	4.6	To examine specific symptom progression patterns and possible disease staging in Parkinson disease clinical subtypes (“Motor Only”, “Psychiatric & Motor”, “Cognitive & Motor”)	UPDRS 3 Total, CDR sum of boxes, GDS, NPIQ	Parkinson disease clinical subtypes progress in clear, temporally distinct patterns from one another, particularly in cognitive and psychiatric features.
Ou et al., 2021	C	379	Minimum 1 year	To evaluate whether the control status of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) influences the progression of Parkinson’s disease (PD)	UPDRS-III, time to death or time to MoCA 3-point decrease.	Poorly controlled diabetes is an independent risk factor contributing to motor progression in PD (but not cognitive progression nor time to death).
Ren et al., 2021	C	PPMI: 421; LABS-PD: 463	Up to 9 years	Develop a prognostic model using multiple, easily acquired longitudinal measures to predict temporal clinical progression from Hoehn and Yahr (H&Y) Stage 1 or 2 to Stage 3 in early PD.	progression to HY 3	Incorporating longitudinal information of multiple clinical measures significantly.
Riboldi et al., 2022	C	423	3	To test the hypothesis that symptoms of dysautonomia and RBD may help to independently prognosticate disease progression.	MDS-UPDRS I, II, III, Total, H&Y, STAI, MOCA, GDS	Dysautonomia symptoms (SCOPA-AUT) predict severe progression of motor and non-motor symptoms better than RBD symptoms (RBDSQ) across the 3-year follow-up period
Santos et al., 2021	C	507	2	To compare the progression of independence in activities of daily living (ADL) in Parkinson’s disease	Functional dependency was defined as an S&E-ADL score less than	Autonomy for ADL worsens in PD patients compared to controls. Cognitive impairment, gait problems, fatigue, depressive symptoms, more

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
				(PD) patients versus a control group, as well as to identify predictors of disability progression and functional dependency (FD).	80%. NMS, QoL, H&Y, UPDRS III-IV, FOGQ, PD-CRS, NMSS, BDI-II, PDSS, NPI, QUIP-RS, PDQ-39, PQ-10, EUROHIS-QOL8	advanced disease, and a non-tremor phenotype are independent predictors of FD in the short-term
Shakya et al., 2022	C	408	3	Identify PD subtypes with distinct disease progression profiles		2 distinct subtypes of Parkinson's disease: (a) mild motor-non-motor subtype (MMNS) with milder motor, non-motor, and neuropsychiatric features and (b) severe motor-non-motor subtype (SMNS) with intense motor and non-motor features by including motor and non-motor features. Both subtypes showed peculiar progression patterns, with SMNS showing a more rapid decline in global cognitive functioning and MMNS showing a more rapid decline in motor functioning.
Urso et al., 2022	C	422	6	To investigate whether PIGD subtype classification or PIGD-related clinical features predict the development of cognitive decline in de novo PD patients.	HVLT recognition discrimination, Benton Judgment of Line Orientation, Letter-Number Sequencing, semantic (animal) fluency test, or Symbol-Digit Modalities	Postural instability, as assessed by MDS-UPDRS III, may serve as a possible indicator of the risk of developing cognitive impairment in de novo PD patients rather than the PIGD phenotype
Wang et al., 2022	C	183	5	To predict the onset of freezing of gait (FoG) in de novo PD patients using a battery of risk factors including clinical data	Onset of FoG	Combining motor and non-motor features including PIGD score, poor cognitive functions and CSF Abeta can identify PD patients with high risk of FoG onset.
Zhang et al., 2022	L	139	2	To determine the roles of BMI and metabolic status on cognitive outcomes in Parkinson's disease (PD)	MoCA, Hopkins Verbal Learning Test, Benton Judgment of Line Orientation Test (BJLOT), Letter Number Sequencing and Semantic Fluency Test, Symbol Digit Modality Test, MDS-UPDRS III, H&Y stage	Metabolically unhealthy normal weight group showed more cognitive decline in global cognition (MoCA) and visuospatial perception (BJLOT) after a 48-month follow-up

Author/ Year	C, D, L Factors	Sample size	Study duration (years)	Study aim	Outcome to define progression	Key take-aways
Zhao et al., 2022	C	350	2	To develop a risk prediction model incorporating various elements available through clinical investigations to predict the probability of future onset of FOG in patients with PD	Onset of FoG	Longer disease duration, depressive symptoms and a higher total LEDD are associated with the onset of future FoG.

General discussion

Demographic factors such as age, gender and education were often identified as either independent predictive factors of disease progression (e.g., Brumm et al., 2023; Dou et al., 2022) or as effect modifiers of other clinical or predictive factors (Constantiniet et al., 2023). The following lifestyle factors emerged as influencing PD progression: exercise (Alagumoorthi et al., 2022; Combs-Miller et al., 2019; Lauhoff et al., 2013), diabetes (Athauda et al., 2022; Ou et al., 2021), unhealthy metabolic status (Zhang et al., 2022), elevated serum uric acid (Constantini et al., 2023), pesticide exposure (Li et al., 2023) and glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in non-diabetic patients (Markaki et al., 2021).

Clinical factors that have been associated with disease progression in PD include greater motor and/or non-motor symptoms (Chen et al., 2023; Brumm et al., 2023; Urso et al., 2022; Wang. et al., 2022), dysautonomic symptoms (Ribold et al., 2022), functional status (Hayete et al., 2017), RBD (Liu et al., 2021) and postural instability and gait disorders (Aleksovski et al., 2018). Adding to this literature, there is increasing evidence suggesting that PD clinical subtypes characterised by distinct clinical features progress in clear, temporally distinct patterns from one another across motor, cognitive and psychiatric domains, opening new promising avenues for the personalised prognosis of PD patients (Meyers et al., 2021; Shakya et al., 2022; Fereshtehnejad et al., 2017; Johansson et al., 2023).

2.3.3 Clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with response to dopaminergic medication

The purpose of this specific subsection is to summarize articles that identify the clinical, demographic or lifestyle factors associated or related to the response to dopaminergic treatment, specifically those predicting changes in motor impairment (including freezing or falls), non-motor impairment (including cognition or hallucinations), global disability, the requirement to adjust medication dose (e.g. increase Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose) or the occurrence of medication-related adverse events (especially dyskinesias or impulse control disorders).

Study selection

From both literary searches, we utilized the Rayyan software employing the following keywords: 'levodopa' OR 'treatment' OR 'levodopa response' OR 'levodopa sensitivity' OR 'levodopa-induced dyskinesia', alongside 'phenotype' and 'subtype', yielding 86 and 45 articles respectively.

Table 14 outlines the selection criteria of the literature research. Articles related to other conditions like Alzheimer's Disease, Progressive Supranuclear Palsy, or Lewy Body disease were excluded as they were not the focus of the study. Additionally, cross-sectional studies and review articles were also excluded. All studies exclusively focusing on biomarkers and neuroimaging were also excluded.

Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts resulting in 6 selected articles. Two articles were added through references of the reviewed papers (Cilia et al., 2014; Verschuur et al., 2019).

Table 14 Selection criteria for clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with medication response

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD treated with levodopa or drug naive

Analysis	Associations between clinical, demographic and lifestyle features and levodopa response or adverse events
Results	Therapy adjustment, clinical PD progression or adverse events related to medication

Study characteristics

Of the 8 articles included (**Table 15**), 7 are longitudinal prospective registries with a range of follow up from 3 months to 5 years. One of them is a retrospective study based on medical records (Djaldetti et al., 2022).

All the studies included PD patients treated with levodopa except for 2 of them, which discusses de novo patients without treatment (Di Lazzaro et al., 2021; Verschuur et al., 2019) and their progression and response over time. In the study by Cilia et al. (2014), there is a subgroup of 21 patients who were drug naive at baseline, which revealed the median time to the development of motor fluctuations and dyskinesias after initiation of levodopa therapy.

In 3 of the PD populations treated with levodopa, attempts were made to divide them into subtypes, and predictive algorithms were used to determine possible factors affecting medication response (Zhou et al., 2023; Djaldetti et al., 2022; Kohat et al., 2021). In 2 of them, wearable devices are used to compare them with clinical data when deciding to make changes in medication (Joshi et al., 2019; Di Lazzaro et al., 2019).

Only two articles focused on adverse effects (Luca et al., 2021; Cilia et al., 2014), the first discusses levodopa-induced dyskinesias in relation to cognitive aspects, and the second one in relation to treatment and disease duration.

Table 15 Studies about clinical, demographic and lifestyle factors associated with medication response

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
Di Lazzaro et al., 2021	36	36 de novo drug-free PD patients	Identify prognostic biomarkers in newly diagnosed PD and quantify therapy-response by technology-based kinematic assessments.	2 ± 2.04	V0: 22.3 ± 9.14 , V2: 17.3 ± 6.67 , V3: 15.36 ± 6.75	V0: 0, V2: 273.86 ± 110.85 , V3: 368.47 ± 132.2	MDS UPDRS III scores decreased significantly after the initiation of the dopaminergic therapy (all tasks except tremor), and clinical improvement was observed in a measurable manner using wearable sensors. No significant differences were recorded in NMSS.
Zhou et al., 2023	60	228	Compare PD subtypes with distinct trajectories of clinical, neurodegeneration events and treatment response	4.29 ± 2.82	22.69 ± 12.97	346.25 ± 272.41	Subtype 1 (with RBD, autonomic dysfunction as early manifestations) had weaker levodopa response and poorer prognosis than subtype 2 (with hyposmia, cognitive impairment, as early manifestations)
Djaldetti et al., 2022	At least 6	296	Identify factors predictive of long-term response to levodopa.	9.2 ± 4.5	UPDRS I-IV: Pre-levodopa: 27.4 ± 10.4 Post-levodopa: 14.3 ± 6.6	Included only patients who reached a minimal dose of 300 mg of levodopa	Time to initiation of levodopa treatment had no effect on responsiveness except in patients older than 72 years, who were less responsive. The main determinants of variations in levodopa responsiveness are gender, age, and clinical phenotype. Early use of dopamine agonists does not hamper levodopa responsiveness.
Joshi et al., 2019	At least 3	63	Frequency of Personal KinetiGraph (PKG) report use in treatment change decisions	10.8			Global bradykinesia requiring 1 or more doses of levodopa was the most frequently observed subtype in 47% of bradykinesia cases. Predictable dyskinesia requiring one or more treatments represented 44% of dyskinesia cases.
Kohat et al., 2021	36	170	Understand the distribution of PD motor subtypes: tremor dominant (TD) / postural instability gait	6.35 ± 6.50	23.51 ± 11.36	233.56 ± 177.72	LEDD is higher in the PIGD subtype. Lower LEDD and higher TD/PIGD ratios are independent predictors of stability of TD subtype

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
			disorder (PIGD) / indeterminate; and baseline factors that predicted subtype stability.				
Luca et al., 2021	48	139 LID - 18 LID +	Evaluate possible associations between cognitive dysfunctions and development of Levodopa Induced Dyskinesia (LID)	2.6±2.5 LID - 5.7±3.2 LID +	24.7±12.5 LID - 36.0±14.8 LID +	266.5±285.9 LID - 935.6±443.5 LID +	Impairment of the attention and executive domains increased the risk of dyskinesia
Cilia et al., 2018	Cross sectional analysis and longitudinal analysis (31.2 ± 15.6)	-Cross sectional: 59 Ghanaian PD with levodopa 160 Italian PD with levodopa -Longitudinal 21 drug-naive PD patients	Investigate if the occurrence of motor complications is primarily related to the duration of levodopa therapy or to disease-related factors.	5.8 Ghana PD patients	23.5 Ghana PD patients	365 Ghana PD patients	Motor fluctuations and dyskinesias are not associated with the duration of levodopa therapy, but rather with longer disease duration and higher levodopa daily dose.
Verschuur et al., 2019	Early-start group: 20 months treated with levodopa -Delayed-start group: 10 weeks treated with placebo followed by 10 treated	PD de novo patients (drug naïve): -222 early-start group -223 delayed-start group	Determining if levodopa also has a disease-modifying effect (measured by the difference in the mean change from baseline to end follow up period on the UPDRS scale.	Diagnosis <2 years	Early start group: 18.4±8.7 Delayed-start group: 19.5±9.4	300 or placebo	Among patients with early PD treatment with levodopa had no disease-modifying effect. The rates of dyskinesia and levodopa-related fluctuations in motor response did not differ significantly between the two groups.

Author/ Year	Study duration (months)	Sample size	Study aim	Disease duration (years)	Motor severity (UPDRS part III)	Levodopa equivalent diary dose (LEDD)	Key take-aways
	with levodopa						

General discussion

It has been particularly challenging to find relevant articles regarding predicting response to dopaminergic treatment. This is probably because most articles related to treatment response were written at the beginning of levodopa introduction in the late 1960's, which is beyond our search filter criteria (2014-2024). Additionally, most articles only focus on levodopa and not on other pharmacological therapies.

Responsiveness to levodopa varies greatly among patients with Parkinson's disease, and the factors that affect it are poorly defined. The aim of the review was to identify these intrinsic factors related to demographic, clinical, or lifestyle features.

The resulting data suggest that all patients experience an improvement in motor impairment when taking levodopa, with tremor showing the smallest improvement. In general, all patients were assessed using the UPDRS-III to measure motor performance and there seems to be a good correlation with wearable sensors to predict response or progression (Joshi et al., 2019). As PD advances, axial symptoms like freezing of gait, postural changes and loss of balance respond less to levodopa (Kohat et al., 2021).

When trying to stratify patients with a poorer response to medication, it appears that those who show REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) or early autonomic symptoms, tend to have a worse progression of the disease and weaker levodopa response (Zhou et al., 2023).

The article by Djaldetti et al. (2022), suggested that for older patients (72 years or more), responsiveness was better when levodopa was initiated early after symptom onset, whereas for younger patients, delaying treatment was less critical in terms of levodopa responsiveness. Apart from age, there seems to be variation in response based on the clinical phenotype, with the PIGD subtype requiring higher doses (Kohat et al., 2021). The longitudinal analysis by Cilia et al. (2014) revealed that the median time to develop motor fluctuations and dyskinesias was 5.5 for motor fluctuations, and 6.5 for dyskinesias independent of when levodopa was started. It also showed that motor fluctuations and dyskinesias are not associated with the duration of levodopa therapy, so delaying its use for this reason is not justified.

2.3.4 Genetic markers associated with PD progression and medication response

A genetic marker is a DNA sequence with a known physical location on a chromosome. Genetic markers can help link an inherited disease to a single gene or a group of genes contributing to disease pathogenesis.

Study selection

Within the bounds of the Rayyan bibliographies we searched the keywords “dopaminergic medication” OR “levodopa” OR “longitudinal” OR “progression” AND “gene” OR “genetic”, “GWAS” OR “PRS” OR “polygenic risk score” OR “SNP” OR “polymorphism” OR “genetic association”. yielding 14 records (levodopa/dopaminergic medication), 186 for “progression”, 64 for “longitudinal”, respectively. In addition, 17 additional studies that were initially identified in the genetic associations related to PD risk were included in this section as they focused more on disease progression. Furthermore, for all PRS studies, as well as all GWAS and meta-analysis studies, only those with a significant statistical association of p-values less than 5×10^{-8} and 5×10^{-6} , respectively, were included. Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. The full text was read to confirm the eligibility of the article where required. Studies comparing PD with other neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's Disease, Huntington's Disease, Lewy Body disease, Multiple Sclerosis and Progressive Supranuclear Palsy were excluded to focus only on PD specific studies. Thus, a total of 35 studies were included within this review.

Table 16 outlines the study eligibility criteria, in short, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study participants were individuals with PD prior to diagnosis, naive drug free PD patients or PD patients with a diagnosis
AND
In the case of dopaminergic medication response, a Levodopa dose was required for PD individuals irrespective of PD stage and onset.
AND
Disease progression and longitudinal outcome were also investigated, if possible, in terms of clinical genetic markers, Levodopa response, neuroimaging and fluid biomarkers.

Table 16 Selection criteria for genetic markers associated with PD progression and medication response

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients
Outcome	Genetic associations related to Levodopa dose, PD Progression and Longitudinal outcome
Results	Clinical genetic markers and Levodopa related to progression or longitudinal outcome of PD

Study characteristics

Thirty-six studies met the inclusion criteria (**Table 17**). From these studies ten reported Levodopa response, whereas the remaining studies failed to report Levodopa dose in terms of genetic markers, PD progression and longitudinal PD outcomes.

Thirteen studies used open-source data (PPMI, Track PD study, Oxford Discovery cohort and other-data sources) while the remaining twenty-three studies included within the review employed their own experimental design and data collection approaches. Ten studies included clinical genetic markers in relation to dopaminergic response, PD progression and longitudinal outcomes, whereas twenty-six studies did not report Levodopa response in relation of genetic markers, progression and longitudinal outcomes.

Clinical genetic markers, levodopa, progression and longitudinal outcomes of PD

The included studies present diverse approaches at the experimental, statistical and bioinformatic level to capture genes and their role in influencing progression and longitudinal outcome of PD but also how patients respond to Levodopa.

Table 17 Studies investigating the association between the genetic markers and PD progression and medication Response

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Cacabelos et al., 2021	DF-PD & CF-PD=127	-	-	Atremorine (5g, p.o)	ACMSD-T/T (p < 0.001) BCKDK-A/G (p < 0.003) BCKDK-A/A (p < 0.02) BCKDK-G/G (p < 0.001) GCH1-A/A (p < 0.05) GCH1-A/G (p < 0.001) GCH1-G/G (p < 0.007) GPNMB-A/A (p < 0.001) GPNMB-G/G (p < 0.007) (NUCKS1-T/T) (p < 0.02) NUCKS1-C/C (p < 0.001) LRRK2-A/A (p < 0.001) SNCA-A/G (p < 0.004) NMs (p < 0.001) IMs (p < 0.001) PMs (p < 0.001) UMS (p < 0.001) SOD2-T/T (p < 0.001) SOD2-C/T (p < 0.001), SOD2C/C carriers (p < 0.001) STP1B-CT (p < 0.001) ABCB1 (p < 0.001) SLC6A2-G/G (p < 0.04) SLC6A3-C/C (p < 0.001) SLC6A3A/C (p < 0.02) APOE-3/3 (p < 0.01) APOE-2/3 (p < 0.001) APOE-2/4 (p < 0.02) APOE-3/4 (p < 0.001) DRD2-G/G (p < 0.005) CYP2C19-NMs & UMs (p < 0.05) CYP2C9-NMs	Atremorine induced Dopamine response in PD patients. Several metabolic genes (CYP2D6, CYP2C19, CYP2C9, CYP3A4) transporter genes (ABCB1, SLC6A1) show differential DNA methylation after Atremorine administration

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(p < 0.01) CYP3A4-PMs (p < 0.01)	
Martinez-Carrasco et al., 2023	N=2784, Tracing PD =1478 OPDC =705 PPMI =283 PD STAT =77 PDBP =241	-	10 years	Baseline PPMI: 217 (197) OPDC: 280 (205) PPMI: 0 (0) PD STAT: NA PDBP: 414 (207)	rs72673189 (p=1.53x10-8) rs189093213 (p=2.81x10-9) rs180924818 (p= 6.27x10-9) rs1641433611 (p=4x10-4) rs113276175 (p= 4x10-4) rs6265 (p=4.95x10-2) rs1800497 (p=8.89x10-3)	Increased probability of developing LiD (females & younger age at onset). PRS significantly associated with an increase of LiD. rs72673189, rs189093213 & rs180924818 significantly associated with time to LiD onset.
Hayete et al., 2017	Newly diagnosed PD patients =244	Follow-up 7 years	Since Diagnosis LABS-PD Baseline 0.8 (0.8) Baseline data for model 0.8 (0.8) Last follow-up 7.8 (0.8)	-	rs11724635 with MoCA scores, year 5 (p = 2.7E-5) year 6 (p= 0.053) & year 7 (p= 0.0424), ApoE isoforms, MAPT, SNCA (n.s)	rs11724635 associated with faster cognitive progression. Predictors of cognitive function were: UPDRS (parts I, II), S/E-ADL, striatal dopamine transporter binding & SNP rs11724635 in (BST1). Lower DAT uptake at baseline in the caudate nuclei & presence of rs11724635 may contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes.
Ortega et al., 2021	N=1193, GBA PD: =128	15 years	GBA PD: 6.9 (5.9) LRRK2 PD: 8.3 (6.5)	GBA PD: 692.7 (551.1) LRRK2 PD: 747.4 (545.1)	Mild: N370S & R496H (p=0.001) Variant: E326K, E326K/E326K, T369M	GBA PD faster decline in MoCA than those with LRRK2/GBA PD, LRRK2 PD, Idiopathic PD LRRK2 G2019S x GBA interaction in MoCA decline

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
	LRRK2 PD =155 LRRK2/GBA PD =21, Idiopathic PD =889		LRRK2/GBA PD: 6.0 (6.7), Idiopathic PD: 5.5 (4.9)	LRRK2/GBA PD: 283.2 (262.2) Idiopathic PD: 580.7 (489.7)	(p=0.001) GBA PD & cognitive decline compared to (p= <0.001) LRRK2/GBA PD (p= <0.001), LRRK2 PD: (p=0.001), Idiopathic PD: (p=0.005), LRRK2 G2019S × GBA interaction in MoCA decline (p= 0.04). GBA PD motor progression compared with those with idiopathic PD (p=0.03) or LRRK2 PD (p=0.004).	GBA PD had worse motor progression compared with idiopathic PD or LRRK2 PD
Fischer et al., 2022	N=217, Placebo =112 Tocopherol =105	-	Early PD stages (I & II)	-	SNPs altered BDNF transcript expression in brain regions. Caudate nucleus: rs1157659 (p=0.0051), rs11030094 (p=0.0059), rs6265 (p=0.0067). Survival analysis for time to needing dopaminergic therapy rs10501087: T/T (p=0.002) (HR: 28.3) &T/C (p=0.004) (HR:7.6) rs11030094: A/A (p=0.03) (HR:2.5), A/G (p=0.03) (HR:2.0) rs1491850 (time >12 months) T/T (p= 0.02) (HR: 5.1) & T allele carrier vs C/C (p=0.04) (HR:3.5)	rs10501087, rs1491850 & rs11030094 associated with a slower rate of PD progression in unmedicated state. rs908867 & rs1157659 did not alter time to initiate Levodopa

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Cacabelos et al., 2020	(N=127). DF-PD =81 CF-PD =46	-	DF-PD & CF-PD	Atremorine (5g, p.o)	rs460000 (SLC6A3) (DA transporter): SLC6A3-C/C (p<0.05) A/A (p=<0.05), A/C (p<0.02), C/C (p<0.001), SLC6A2 (NA transporter): SLC6A2-A/A (p< 0.05), A/G (p<0.001), G/G (p<0.04). rs2020934 (SLC6A4) SLC6A4-A/A: (p<0.001), A/C (p<0.01), C/C (p<0.001) Dopamine (basal) (pg/ml) (p<0.001) Total 441.56±146.15 DF 12.14±0.34 CF 1221.53±389.94 Dopamine (treatment) (pg/ml) (p<0.001) Total 9847.21±1912.03 DF 6463.21±1306.90 CF 16028.54±4783.98	Basal plasma levels of DA lower in DF-PD than CT-PD. Low basal DA levels in SLC6A3-C/C carriers & DA response to Atremorine was significant in A/A, A/C, C/C carriers. Variations in both NA & DA transporters affect the response of DA to Atremorine. CF-PD patients show higher basal DA level after 12 h fasting. Females showed lower basal DA levels than males. DF-PD patients who take Atremorine (first time) showed an increase in DA levels. CT-PD showed an increase in DA levels. Atremorine enhances in dopaminergic effects of conventional anti-PD drugs. Atremorine influences neurotransmitter levels (catecholamines) & hormones regulated by DA (prolactin) with no effect on 5-HT or histamine synthesis and release
Tsiouris et al., 2020	New diagnosed & untreated PD patients =423	5-13 years (depending on cohort)/ 3rd/6th/9th/ 12 months	New diagnosed and untreated PD patients	-	2-year follow-up: Rapid progression (top 20%) vs Slower progression (Rest): rs823118 (p=0.415) rs329648 (p=0.191). Rapid progression (top 10%) vs Slower progression (Rest): rs11060180 (p=0.001) rs823118 (p=0.042)	Improvement when a longer follow-up period is considered in the estimation of the progression rate. Moving from 2-4 years the classification accuracy increased in all cases tested, better outcome in identifying rapid progression phenotype. Prolonged patient evaluation can provide better outcomes in identifying rapid progression phenotype.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Wang et al., 2022	N=389, PPMI dataset =346, Controls =171 Huashan dataset (Validation cohort) PD =43, Controls =23	Followed up to 5 years (every 3 months during first year & every 6 months during subsequent 4 years)	New diagnosed PD patients	-	SNCA in relation to UPDRS II PAP (p=0.023) SNCA in relation to ADL PAP (p=0.0048).	Patients with low subcortical DBM values are associated with faster progression of motor symptoms across the 2 datasets. Structural measurements of BR affect the clinical progression of motor symptoms in PD patients. PD patients with greater brain resources (higher deformation-based morphometry values) had a greater compensatory capacity, which was associated with slower rates of clinical progression.
Cao et al., 2021	PD patients =365	Not provided Follow up 5 years	Rapid motor progression	-	Baseline autonomic dysfunction was associated with rapid progression (p=0.039). rs6808178 (LINC00693) associated with faster motor progression. (p=0.0004) after correction of multiple testing (p<0.0011).	Genetic & clinical features together demonstrated more predictivity towards fast motor progression. (LINC00693 rs6808178, CHMP2B rs115185635, IP6K2 rs12497850, TMEM175 rs34311866, OGFOD2 rs11060180, CAB39L rs9568188, and DLG2 rs3793947 were associated with rapid motor deterioration in PD.
He et al., 2021	N=103 PD Stage II =8 Stage III =42 Stage IV =22 & =72 HC =31	-	Stage II Stage III Stage IV	-	Distinguished stages II, III & IV from controls. hsa-miR-374a-5p Stage II: (AUCs: 0.758) (p=0.026), Stage III: (AUC: 0.780) (p=0.0001) Stage IV: (AUCs :0.798) (p=0.0012) hsa-miR-374b-5p Stage II: (AUCs: 0.798) (p=0.0101) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.742) (p=0.0004)	hsa-miR-374a-5p, hsa-miR-374b-5p, hsa-miR-199a-3p, hsa-miR-28-5p, hsa-miR-22-5p & hsa-miR-151a-5p are potential biomarkers for stage-specific diagnosis of PD

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					<p>Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.761) (p=0.0013). Distinguished stage II from control, stage III and stage IV.</p> <p>hsa-miR-199a-3p Control: (AUCs:0.738) (p=0.0402), Stage III: (AUCs: 0.729), (p=0.0416) Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.756) (p=0.0348). Distinguished stage III from control, stage II and stage IV.</p> <p>hsa-miR-28-5p Control: (AUCs:0.746) (p=0.0004) Stage II: (AUCs: 0.789) (p=0.0103), Stage IV: (AUCs: 0.738) (p=0.0019). Distinguished stage IV from control, stage II and stage III.</p> <p>hsa-miR-22-5p Control: (AUCs:0.817) (p<0.0001) Stage II: (AUCs: 0.773) (p=0.0244) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.700) (p=0.0089)</p> <p>hsa-miR-151a-5p Control: (AUCs: 0.741), (p=0.0031) Stage II: (AUCs:0.796) (p=0.0147) Stage III: (AUCs: 0.708) (p=0.0066),</p> <p>hsa-miR-29a-3p Control: (AUCs: 0.743) (p=0.0027)</p>	

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					Stage II: (AUCs: 0.813) (p=0.0056) Stage III: (AUCs:0.712), (p=0.0056)	
Henderson et al., 2021	N=30 PD =15 HC =15	-	Early PD stage	-	FOSB (p=4.93E-05) ETV7 (p=4.93E-05) TUBB6 (p=7.32E-05) PC (p=1.70E-05) ZDHHC11 (p=9.27E-05) KLC3 (p=9.55E-05) LINC00265 (p=7.21E-06) TARS2 (p=7.31E-05) ZNF142 (p=4.28E-05) RPS24 (p=2.21E-05) CDK14 (p=1.06E-04) CLEC2B (p=5.84E-05) RPL34 (p=9.98E-05) BCL2A1 (p=6.74E-05) TCF4 (p=8.46E-05) COMMD6 (p=5.25E-05) LY96 (p=2.58E-05) LSM3 (p=2.59E-05) S100AB (p=1.11E-05) LSMEM1 (p=3.36E-05) COX6C (p=1.01E-04) COX7B (p=9.97E-05) RCAN1 (p=2.59E-05) RNF175 (p=6.96E-05) RAD51C (p=3.18E-05) FAM200B (p=4.75E-05) Inc-PDK3-1 (p=8.66E-05) GLIP41 (p=4.59E-05) KIN (p=1.09E-04) NPEPPS (p=1.07E-04) Hypermethylated	Differentially expressed genes were involved in transcription & mitochondrial function. PD methylation profiles were readily distinguishable from healthy controls. Differentially methylated regions (DMRs) were functionally varied, including near transcription factor nuclear transcription factor Y subunit alpha (NFYA), receptor tyrosine kinase DDR1, RING finger ubiquitin ligase (RNF5), acetyltransferase AGPAT1, and vault RNA VTRNA2-1. Expression quantitative trait methylation sites were found at long non-coding RNA PAX8-AS1 & transcription regulator ZFP57 among others. Functional epigenetic modules were highlighted by IL18R1, PTPRC, and ITGB2.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					DMR2 (RNF5P1, RNF5, AGPAT1) (p=0.0004), DMR4 (LOC151174, LOC643387) (p=0.0006), DMR5 (VTRNA2-1) (p=0.0009) DMR6 (SPEF2) (p=0.0013) DMR7 (TYW3, CRYZ) (p=0.0014) DMR17 (KLF14) (p=0.0057) DMR16 (PM20D1) (p=0.0065) DMR22 (GPR75, LOC100202652) (p=0.0068) DMR19 (ARHGAP22) (p=0.0074) DMR20 (DUSP19) (p=0.0078) DMR25(SMC1B, RIBC2) (p=0.0151), DMR28 (UBLCP1) (p=0.0158), DMR1 (NFYA) (p=0.0003) DMR8 (RNF39) (p=0.0005) DMR10 (C6orf25) (p=0.0018), DMR10 (C1orf65) (p=0.0025) DMR9 (DDX43) (p=0.0025) DMR13 (HOXA4) (p=0.00031) DMR14 (HLA-DPB2) (p=0.00031) Hypomethylated DMR15 (CYP1A1) (p=0.00052) DMR18 (DDR1) (p=0.00075) DMR21 (KCNAB3) (p=0.00081) DMR23 (C3orf24) (p=0.0105) DMR24 (PSMA8) (p=0.0140) DMR31 (C1orf11) (p=0.0168)	

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					DMR27 (NAPRT1) (p=0.0178) DMR29 (AKR1E2) (p=0.0205) DMR30 (TILL10) (p=0.0227) cis-eQTM (CpG) (PAX8-AS1): cg19083407 (p=1.53E-10), cg23564664 (p=5.13E-10), cg07594247 (p=9.29E-10) cg17445212 (p=1.10E-09), cg12889195 (p=1.93E-09), cg07772999 (p=7.87E-09), cg11763394 (p=9.34E-09), cg21550016 (p=9.97E-09), cg02675527 (p=1.10E-08), cg21482265 (p=1.69E-08) (ZFP57): cg15708526 (p=3.34E-09), cg07134666 (p=5.11E-09), cg15570556 (p=6.24E-09), cg16885113 (p=1.29E-08), cg08022281 (p=1.69E-08), cg004071440 (p=3.43E-08), cg11383134 (p=5.22E-08), cg03449857 (p=5.68E-08), cg20228636 (p=7.76E-08). trans-eQTM (CLEC11A): cg13291296 (p=6.34E-11), (SIPA1L2): cg11460641 (p=8.30E-12), cg26287080, (p=2.58E-11), cg21622464 (p=5.13E-11), cg24297509 (p=1.42E-10), cg26914392 (p=1.76E-10) (TRBV19): cg11199182 (p=8.30E-11), cg25335258 (p=1.22E-10), cg11342941	

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					<p>(p=2.03E-10), cg17153055 (p=2.12E-10) (RPL29): cg26835568 (p=4.52E-12) cg01772663 (p=2.13E-11), cg02810976 (p=1.04E-10), g21475003 (p=1.16E-10), cp08272591 (p= 1.19E-10), cg06312137 ,cg00266592 (p=5.70E-10),cg25593954 (p=1.49E-10),cg12067423 (p=1.53E-10),cg02942845 (p=2.40E-10) (TRBV11-2): cg16515546 (p=1.40E-13),cg13291296 (p=7.40E-12),cg21950182 (p=4.00E-11), cg17731973 (p=6.65E-11), cg156614872 (p=7.48E-11), cg06809285 (p=1.31E-10), cg21028260 (p=2.02E-10), cg18696632 (p=3.40E-12), cg18803655 (p=4.96E-12), cg21475544 (p=6.74E-12), cg21300072 (p=2.44E-10), cg01840459 (p=2.26E-10) (RPL26L1): cg08029281 (p=2.22E-10) (GEMIN8): cg22128645 (p=1.41E-10), (HSPB11): cg08029281 (p=4.83E-11) (PCSK1N): cg25751895 (p=1.64E-10) (ACOT11): cg24512544 (p=5.29E-11)</p>	

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					<p>(TOMM7): cg08029281 (p=3.71E-10)</p> <p>(TTN-AS1): cg22793142 (p=1.94E-10)</p> <p>(DND1P1): cg12609785 (p=1.95E-10)</p>	
Liang et al., 2022	PD =53 HC =49	2 years/Not provided	-	324.78±37.92	<p>Serum sNogo-B levels: PD vs HC (p=0.0001)</p> <p>α-Syn levels: PD vs HC: (p < 0.0001)</p> <p>serum sNogo-B level: Early vs advanced: (n.s). Serum sNogo-B (AUC = 0.801, p < 0.0001)</p> <p>serum α-Syn (AUC = 0.93, (p < 0.0001), combination of them (AUC = 0.9534, p <0.0001)</p> <p>sNogo-B level was mildly negatively correlated with UPDRS III scores (p = 0.049) & negatively correlated with the H&Y stage (p = 0.0001)</p> <p>serum sNogo-B & NMSS scores (n. s.), levodopa equivalent dose (n. s.)</p>	<p>Serum sNogo-B levels lower in PD compared to HC.</p> <p>Decreased serum sNogo-B may be a potential biomarker for PD. The lower Nogo-B level reflects worse motor function of PD.</p> <p>Serum sNogo-B is of added value to serum α-Syn panel in distinguishing PD from controls.</p>
Koros et al., 2021	<p>PPMI Data:</p> <p>GBA-PD =120</p> <p>de novo sporadic PD =369</p> <p>HC =195</p>	Longitudinal 2-year/ Year 1 and Year 2	<p>GBA PD: 4.47 (±4.13)</p> <p>Sporadic PD: 0.54(±0.6)</p>	-	<p>Adjustment for age, sex & BMI: GBA-PD cohort exhibited lower 2-year longitudinal uric acid level as compared to the controls (p = 0.016). Baseline uric acid measurements: A marginal difference (p = 0.119), but year 2 uric acid levels were lower in the GBA-PD cohort (p < 0.001). No</p>	<p>Low serum uric acid might be a progression biomarker in GBA-PD. Serum uric acid did not differ between GBA-PD vs sporadic PD.</p> <p>A gradual decrease of uric acid levels in both PD cohorts.</p>

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
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					difference in baseline (p = 0.664) Year 2 (p = 0.117) & 2-year longitudinal serum uric acid (p = 0.315) in the GBA-PD cohort as compared to sporadic PD	
Abdelmoaty et al., 2022	PD =5	12 month/ 2 & 6 post-treatment	8±5	Carbidopa-Levodopa 25–100 mg, (n=3) Carbidopa-Levodopa 50–200 mg (n=1) Carbidopa-Levodopa 23–95 mg (n=1)	Downregulation HMOX1 (p=3.47x10-8) 2 months & (p=9.58x10-12) 6 months, TLR2 (p=0.0348) (2 months) & TLR8 (p=1.66x10-6) 6 months, RELA (p=0.0147) & IKBKG (p=00146) 2 months, LRRK2 (p=8.54x10-6) (2 month) (p=9.38x10-4) (6 month). Upregulation ATG3 (p=0.0279) ATG7 (p=0.0428) GABARAPL2 (p=0.0096) Expression of potential gene or protein biomarkers with UPDRS III scores: LRRK2 (n. s.) HMOX1 (p=0.013), TLR2 (p=0.005) (decreased gene expression & improved motor function). Indirect correlation changes in UPDRS III scores & ATG7 (p=5.1x10-7). LRRK2 & HMOX1 effect on UPDRS III score change (p=0.0336), LRRK2 & TLR2 (p=0.0012), TLR2 had a greater effect (p=0.0018). LRRK2 & ATG7 strong potential to affect	Sargramostim induces monocyte antioxidant and anti-inflammatory autophagy functions were differentially expressed by 2 and 6 months. LRRK2, HMOX1 & TLR2 proteins were significantly downregulated in 60%–80% of patients at 2 and 6 months of Sargramostim treatment. Downregulation of TLR8 & RELA proteins after 2 months in 60% (3/5) of patients with significant downregulation in 1/3 of patients for each protein. Monocyte profiles & both clinical motor function & disease progression during immune modulatory therapy

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
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					<p>changes in UPDRS III score ($p=1.12 \times 10^{-6}$), LRRK2 & ATG7 ($p=1.3 \times 10^{-6}$) predict a lower UPDRS score from baseline score. TLR2 & TLR8 ($p=0.0009$), TLR2 showing a greater effect ($p=0.0002$), TLR2 & ATG7 expression was significantly linked to the UPDRS III score ($p=1.1 \times 10^{-5}$), ATG7 having the greater influence ($p=0.0012$), combined effect of TLR8 & ATG7 correlated with the change in UPDRS score ($p=3.8 \times 10^{-6}$), ATG7 producing a greater diminution effect ($p=6.8 \times 10^{-7}$) a 1-fold increase in ATG7 expression decreased UPDRS III score change by 4 points. 7 variables showed a strong correlation on score changes from baseline ($p=10 \times 10^{-5}$). HMOX1, TLR8, & ATG7, ($p=2.0 \times 10^{-6}$) accounted for a score change from baseline strongest effect on change from UPDRS baseline was provided by ATG7 ($p=2.1 \times 10^{-6}$).</p>	
Ghit & El Deeb et al., 2022	N=35 PD =20 HC =15	1 year/Not mentioned	-	Treatment duration: 3.9 ± 3.4	Cytokines (IL10, IL12, & TNF- α) & α -Synuclein in PD patients significantly higher than those in healthy individuals ($p < 0.0001$).	Increased sera levels of cytokines in PD patients as well as a positive correlation among them. A significant increase in sera levels of α -synuclein are associated with a decrease in miR-214 (regulates its gene expression). A decrease in sera levels of miR-221, miR-141, UA, PON1, & ARE, a role against

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
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					miR-214, miR-221, miR-141) as well as antioxidants (UA, PON1, and ARE) in PD patients were lower than HC ($p < 0.0001$). Correlation among serum levels of immune & non-immune markers in PD patients and HC. Positive correlation IL10 & IL12 ($p < 0.0001$) TNF- α & IL10 ($p = 0.002$) TNF- α & IL1 ($p < 0.0001$), Antioxidant enzymes PON1 & ARE ($p = 0.002$). Negative correlation serum levels of miR-221 & TNF- α ($p = 0.01$)	oxidative stress. to correctly predict disease state and progression. A mix of non-invasive biomarkers is required.
Li et al., 2019	PD =418 HC =426	3 years	-	-	rs4698412 (BST1) ($p = 0.004307$) rs4538475 (BST1) ($p = 0.01923$) rs11060180 (CCDC620) ($p = 0.02327$) rs199498 (MAPT) ($p = 0.0363$) rs6532194 (SNCA) ($p = 5.87 \times 10^{-7}$) rs11931074 (SNCA) ($p = 4.84 \times 10^{-6}$) rs3857059 (SNCA) ($p = 9.57 \times 10^{-6}$) rs356220 (SNCA) ($p = 1.86 \times 10^{-5}$) rs356165 (SNCA) ($p = 1.87 \times 10^{-5}$)	Only 13 of the 46 SNPs identified in other populations had significant correlations with PD & the PRSs based on these 13 SNPs were associated with the PD risk & age at onset in our Chinese cohort. The CSF α -synuclein level had no correlation with the PRS in normal subjects.

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					rs356219 (SNCA) ($p=2.31 \times 10^{-5}$) rs356182 (SNCA) ($p=7.2 \times 10^{-5}$) rs2736990 (SNCA) ($p=0.000108$) rs894278 (SNCA) ($p=0.0472$) Model 1 SNPs associated with PD ($p < 0.05$) in cohort were selected to generate the PRS model ($p < 0.001$) Model 2 SNPs with a P value threshold of 0.01 in the logistic regression analysis ($p < 0.001$) Model 3 All selected SNPs located in SNCA loci ($p < 0.001$) Correlations between PRSs & CSF α -synuclein levels were analysed in the control group ($n = 262$) no significant relationships were found (model 1: $p = 0.80$, Spearman $\rho = -0.016$; model 2: $p = 0.77$, Spearman $\rho = -0.018$; model 3: $p = 0.64$, Spearman $\rho = -0.029$). No significant relationship between the PRSs & CSF α -synuclein levels (model 1, $\beta = 0.07$, $p = 0.37$; model 2, $\beta = 0.08$, $p = 0.29$; model 3, $\beta = 0.09$, $p = 0.25$)	

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Jian et al., 2022	<p>GSE7621 PD =16 HC =9, GSE20141 PD =10 HC=8 GSE49036 PD =15 HC =9 GSE20164 PD =6 HC =5 GSE20163 PD =8 HC =9 GSE20292 PD =11 HC =18 GSE34865 PD=0 HC =57 GSE166024 PD =14 HC =0 GSE114517 PD =17 HC =12</p>	-	-	-	<p>16 classifiers, including <i>MAP4K4, LRP10, UCHL1, PAM, RIT2, SNCA, GCH1, DDIT4, RGS4, MAPK9, CAV1, RELA, DUSP1, ATP6V1G2, ATF4 & ISCU</i>, greater than (AUC=0.6), indicating that their featured genes had a promising potential to characterize PD. <i>MAP4K4, LRP10</i> and <i>UCHL1</i> (AUC=0.7) the classifiers featured by ferroptosis-related genes <i>DDIT4, RGS4, MAPK9</i> and <i>RELA</i> (AUC=0.7). Hazards ratio: <i>DDIT4</i> (p=0.02) <i>RGS4</i> (p=0.011) <i>RELA</i> (p=0.045) <i>SNCA</i> (p=0.475) <i>CAV1</i> (p=0.006) <i>GCH1</i> (p=0.094) <i>UCHL</i> (p=0.178) <i>LRP10</i> (p=0.068)</p>	<p>16 DEGs were singled out due to comparable AUC (>0.6) in Random Forest classifiers, including seven PD-related genes (<i>MAP4K4, LRP10, UCHL1, PAM, RIT2, SNCA, GCH1</i>) & nine ferroptosis-related genes (<i>GCH1, DDIT4, RGS4, MAPK9, CAV1, RELA, DUSP1, ATP6V1G2, ATF4</i> and <i>ISCU</i>).</p> <p>Cox model featured by an eight-gene signature, including four PD-related genes (<i>SNCA, UCHL1, LRP10, and GCH1</i>) & four ferroptosis-related genes (<i>DDIT4, RGS4, RELA, and CAV1</i>), & validated it successful in an independent dataset, indicating that it would be an effective tool for clinical research to predict PD progression.</p> <p>Ferroptosis-related DEGs were closely correlated with the known PD-related genes, revealing the involvement of ferroptosis in the development of PD.</p>
Chung et al., 2021	<p>Norwegian ParkWest Study PD =171 APOEe4=114</p>	7 years/3 clinical visits	Early-stage PD	-	<p><i>COMT</i>¹⁵⁸Val/Val & faster decline in executive function (p=0.028) verbal learning & memory (p=0.029) & visuospatial skills (p=0.027) <i>BDNF, MAPT & APOE</i></p>	<p><i>COMT</i> predicted to a decline in executive function, verbal learning & visuospatial skills.</p> <p><i>BDNF, MAPT & APOE</i> were not linked with changes in individual cognitive domains.</p> <p><i>APOEe4</i> carriers are at 3-times increased risk of developing MCI or dementia.</p>

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	<p>APOEε4+ =57 MAPT-H2 =38 MAPT-H1/H1- =133 COMTMet =134 COMTVal/Val =37 BDNFMet =60 BDNFVal/Val n=111</p>				<p>genotypes were not significantly associated with longitudinal changes in individual cognitive domains.</p> <p><i>APOE-ε4</i> carriers had increased risk of mild cognitive impairment & dementia (OR 3.03; p = 0.006)</p>	
Redensek et al., 2022	<p>PD =231 HC = 161</p>	<p>Treatment duration 7.3 years (3.6-13.5)</p>	Not provided	<p>LED enrolment: 975mg/day (600-1,363.15)</p>	<p>VDR rs2228570 (p<0.001). VDR rs1544410 (GG vs. GA+AA) (p=0.005) associated with visual hallucinations, VDR rs739837 (TT vs. GG) (p=0.036) VDR rs731236 (TT vs. TC+CC) (p=0.011) (TT vs. TC) (p=0.028) (TT vs. CC) (p=0.035), rs1544410 (GG vs. GA) (P=0.014) with occurrence of orthostatic hypotension</p>	<p>VDR rs2228570 is associated with PD risk</p> <p>Associations of specific <i>VDR</i> genotypes with adverse events of dopaminergic treatment</p>
Real et al., 2023	<p>PD=3923</p>	-	-	-	<p>LRRC66 (rs140229141) (p= 6.03E-08) MGST1 (rs137899695) (p= 6.09E-08) DMBT1P1 (rs1175592627) (p= 1.10E-07) MYT1L (rs76738835) (p= 1.23E-07) ROS1 (rs142457969) (p=1.26E-07)</p>	<p>APOE ε4 allele as a major risk factor for the conversion to Parkinson's disease dementia as well as a new locus within the ApoE and APP receptor LRP1B gene. GBA variants were also identified to be associated with higher risk of progression to dementia.</p>

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					OCIAD1 (rs148443315) (p=1.47E-07) AVL9 (rs112302765) (p=1.58E-07) SSR1 (rs60707664) (p=1.60E-07) SLC6A3 (rs28363070) (p=1.62E-07) LINC01572 (rs72791159) (p=2.29E-07) ZNF706 (rs74495475) (p=2.36E-07) PLCL2 (rs137926116) (p=2.43E-07) SQRDL (rs62008270) (p=3.00E-07) UGGT2 (rs79734852) (p=3.18E-07) MDFIC (rs1011449) (p=3.37E-07) CCDC57 (rs116965562) (p=3.56E-07) GRID2 (rs144839542) (p=3.59E-07), GUCY1A2 (rs150641600) (p=3.73E-07) LINC01006 (rs56037079) (p=4.31E-07) LINC01581 (rs10438450) LINC01572 (rs147491123) (p=5.11E-07) PLD5 (rs148758425) (p=2.98E-07) FAR2 (rs34331981) (p=5.60E-07), CCDC27 (rs56079032) (p=6.43E-07) (rs117950086) (p=6.86E-07) NUP188 (rs143101418) (p=6.88E-07) LINC02302 (rs117900786)(p=6.94E-07) (rs150616043) (p=6.95E-07) (rs17460578) (p=7.37E-07) PTPRD (rs111575815) (p=8.56E-07) DDB1 (rs28720292) (p=8.93E-07)	

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
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					MSI2 (rs78754514) (p=9.03E-07) VT11A (rs137890797) (p=9.71E-07), (rs429358) (p=2.00E-15) (rs80306347) (p=7.00E-09) (rs78294974) (p=4.00E-08)	
Dehestani et al., 2022	German GWAS Dataset PD=371 HC= 249	-	-	-	(p=2.00E-02)	PRS significantly predict the PD status. Mito PRS are significantly associated with later age of onset in PD patient.
Pihlstrøm et al., 2022	Reference data (IPDGC) PD =11693 HC = 9841 Test data (NeuroX dbGAP) PD= 5112 HC= 5372 PPMI PD= 360, HC= 160	-	-	-	(p<10E-15)	Feasibility of a polygenic hazard approach in PD, integrating the genetic effects on disease risk & age at onset in a single model. The approach holds promise for risk stratification in future clinical trials of disease-modifying therapies, which aim to postpone the onset of PD.
Liu et al., 2021	European & unknown ancestry individuals = 2,650, Replication =1,171 individuals	-	-	-	Survival analysis: RIMS2: HR: 3.37 [2.24-5.06], (p=5.21X10-9), TMEM108: HR: 3.40 [2.21-5.24], (p=2.69x10-8), WWOX: HR: 2.31 [1.73-3.10], (p=1.98x10-8). Adjusted mean MMSE scores across time. RIMS2: (p=0.003), TMEM108: (p=0.0019), WWOX (p=0.009),	Polygenic progression scores exhibit a substantial aggregate association with dementia risk, while polygenic susceptibility scores are not predictive. This study identified a novel synaptic locus and polygenic score for cognitive disease progression in PD and proposes diverging genetic architectures of progression and susceptibility

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Gu et al., 2022	PPMI PD =367	-	Low risk 7.02 ± 6.65, High risk 7.86 ± 9.28	-	Younger age at onset in patients with PD PRS 1 (26 SNPs) (p=3.00E-03) , PRS2 (23 SNPs) (p=3.00E-03) More extensive WM microstructural degeneration (High PRS) (p<0.05), Younger age of onset than that in low-PRS Individuals (High PRS) (p=4.30E-02) Lower H&Y stage than the low-PRS group (High PRS) (p=4.00E-02)	PD-associated polygenic load aggravates the WM microstructural degeneration and these changes may lead to poor cognition with continuous dopamine depletion. This study provides advanced evidence that combined with a cumulative PRS and DTI methods may predict disease progression in PD patients.
Li et al., 2021	PD =3456 Replication PD =1490	-	-	-	NDN, PWRN4 (rs978373) (p=3.00E-09) SNCA (p=1.00E-06)	These findings improve the current understanding of the genetic aetiology of AAO of PD in different ethnic groups. GWAS on AAO of PD in a large Chinese PD cohort and identified a significant novel locus near NDN, as well as a suggestive locus in SNCA. Demonstrate genetic similarity & heterogeneity affecting AAO of PD in Asians & Europeans
Hill-Burns et al., 2016	PD =431 Replication PD =737	-	-	-	LHFPL2 (rs344650) (p=1.00E-11) TRPS1 (rs74335301) (p=3.00E-06) KLHDC1 (rs79503702) (p=5.00E-08) TPM1 (rs117267308) (p=9.00E-11)	LHFPL2 was associated with earlier onset by 12.33 years. NGRC, 8.03 years in replication & 9.79 years in the combined data. TPM1 variant was associated with earlier onset by 15.30 years in NGRC, 9.29 years in replication, &12.42 [years in the combined data. Neither LHFPL2 nor TPM1 was associated with age-at-onset in non-familial PD.

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Wallen et al., 2018	PD=1950, Replication PD =726	-	-	-	LPPR1 (rs73656147) (p=9.00E-09)	Through association with age at diagnosis, we uncovered LPPR1 as a modifier gene for PD
Latourelle, 2009	Familial PD =857 Idiopathic PD =440, Replication PD Idiopathic PD 747	-	-	-	DSG3 (rs1941184) (p=4.00E-06) OCA2 (rs17565841) (p=3.00E-06) QSER1, PRRG4 (rs10767971) (p=5.00E-07)	rs10767971, is associated with a later age of onset under a recessive model. SNP showing the strongest association to PD onset across the three populations under both the additive & dominant models is OCA2
Tan et al., 2021	=3364, Tracking PD =1966, Oxford Discovery =985 PPMI =413	Length of follow-up Tracking PD 3.8 (1.4), Oxford Discovery 4.3 (1.7), PPMI 5.4 (1.2)	Tracking PD 3.2 (3.0) Oxford Discovery 2.9 (1.9) PPMI 2.0(2.0).	-	APOE, TOMM40, APOCA (p=2.8x10-6) ATP8B2 (p=5.3x10-6) AQP10 (p=5.0x10-6)	APOE ε4 allele carriers had more severe cognitive progression. ATP8B2 was associated with motor progression
Blauwen et al., 2019	IPDGC =17996 23andMe =10572	-	-	-	SNCA (rs356203) (p=2.00E-12) GAK, TMEM175 (rs34311866) (p=1.00E-08)	Not all PD risk loci influence AAO with significant differences between risk alleles for AAO
Cha et al., 2020	Japanese. Responders (Zonisamide, Levodopa) =67 Poor Responders (Zonisamide, Levodopa) =133	-	-	Responders 469.9 (164.3) Poor Responders 498 (170.9)	4.00E-08	MDM4 (rs16854023) showed genome-wide significant association with reduced “off” time. Carriers of responsive genotype showed >7-fold decrease in mean “off” time compared to noncarriers. MDM4 encodes a negative regulator of p53. The association between improved motor fluctuation and MDM4 upregulation implies that p53 inhibition may prevent dopaminergic neuron loss and consequent motor symptoms.

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Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
Ryu et al., 2020	PD =172 HC =569	-	10.8 ± 4.5 (5–31)	-	8.00E-09	FAM129B (rs10760490) was associated with the occurrence of motor fluctuations at 5 years after the onset of PD. GALNT14 (rs144125291) was significantly associated with the occurrence of LID.
Li et al., 2022	N=1080 PD =85 HC =995	Follow-up 7.13 years	-	-	3.00E-08	Genetic cause of survival of PD & provide a novel target RPL3 for further research on PD pathogenesis. Results also demonstrate the potential utility of PRS of survival in identifying patients with shorter survival & providing personalized clinical monitoring and treatment
Paul et al., 2018	PD =285	5 years	2.0 (1.4)	-	(p=0.049)	Susceptibility SNPs for PD combined with a cumulative PRS were associated with faster motor and cognitive decline in patients. Thus, these genetic markers may be associated with not only PD susceptibility but also disease progression in multiple domains.
Pihlstrøm L et al., 2016	PD =336	-	-	-	(p = 0.010)	Cumulative genetic risk to a motor outcome in Parkinson's disease
Zheng et al., 2023	PD =314998	-	-	-	rs10797576 (T/C) (p=1.76x10-10), rs10906923 (C/A) (p=2.37x10-8), rs11060180 (G/A) (p=3.08x10-11), rs11158026 (T/C) (p=2.88x10-10), rs11343 (T/G) (p=1.46x10-9), rs115185635 (C/G) (p=2.2x10-8), rs11724635 (C/A) (p=4.26x10-17), rs117896735 (A/G) (p=1.21x10-11), rs12456492	Physical prefrailty and frailty were associated with incident PD independent of sociodemographic factors, lifestyles, multiple morbidities, and genetic background. These findings may have implications for the assessment and management of frailty for PD prevention.

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(G/A) (p=2.15x10 ⁻¹¹), rs12497850 (G/T) (p=6.8x10 ⁻⁸), rs12637471 (A/G) (p=5.38x10 ⁻²²), rs13294100 (T/G) (p=1.99x10 ⁻¹²), rs14235 (A/G) (p=3.63x10 ⁻¹²), rs143918452 (G/A) (p=2.25x10 ⁻⁷), rs1474055 (C/T) (p=7.11x10 ⁻¹⁶), rs1555399 (T/A) (p=5.7x10 ⁻¹⁶), rs17649553 (T/C) (p=6.11x10 ⁻⁴⁹), rs199347 (G/A) (p=5.62x10 ⁻¹⁴), rs2280104 (T/C) (p=9.06x10 ⁻⁷), rs2414739 (G/A) (p=3.59x10 ⁻¹²), rs2694528 (C/A) (p=1.69x10 ⁻¹¹), rs2740594 (A/G) (p=9.545x10 ⁻¹¹), rs329648 (T/C) (p=8.05x10 ⁻¹²), rs34043159 (C/T) (p=3.83x10 ⁻⁸), rs34311866 (C/T) (p=6x10 ⁻⁴¹), rs353116 (T/C) (p=9.73x10 ⁻⁷), rs356182 (G/A) (p=1.85x10 ⁻⁸²), rs35749011 (G/A) (p=6.1x10 ⁻²³), rs3793947 (A/G) (p=2.59x10 ⁻⁸), rs4073221 (G/T) (p=3.02x10 ⁻⁹), rs4653767 (C/T) (p=2.3x10 ⁻¹⁰), rs4784227 (T/C) (p=8.29x10 ⁻⁸), rs591323 (A/G) (p=3.17x10 ⁻⁸), rs601999 (C/T) (p=8.03x10 ⁻⁹), rs62120679 (T/C) (p=2.52x10 ⁻⁹), rs6430538 (T/C) (p=3.35x10 ⁻¹⁹), rs6812193 (T/C)	

Study Characteristics			Study Population	Genetic Data		
Study	Sample	Study Duration & Monitoring	Disease Duration	Levodopa Dose	p-value	Key take-aways
					(p=1.85x10 ⁻¹¹), rs76904798 (T/C) (p=4.86x10 ⁻¹⁴), rs78738012 (C/T) (p=2.1x10 ⁻⁹), rs8005172 (T/C) (p=1.2x10 ⁻⁹), rs8118008 (A/G) (p=2.32x10 ⁻⁸), rs823118 (C/T) (p=1.96x10 ⁻¹⁶), rs9275326 (T/C) (p=5.81x10 ⁻¹³), rs9468199 (A/G) (p=3.44x10 ⁻¹³)	

General discussion

This review aimed to identify and assess the clinical genetic markers regarding Levodopa response, disease progression and longitudinal outcomes related to PD in terms of clinical, neuroimaging and fluid biomarkers. The findings highlight the magnitude of studies and research on genetic markers and PD. Numerous SNPs were associated with faster cognitive decline as observed in several studies (Hayete et al., 2017; Fischer et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2021; Li et al., 2019). In addition, the study by Hayete et al. (2017) identified that certain SNPs may lower DAT uptake at baseline in the caudate nuclei and therefore contribute to worse long-term cognitive outcomes. Moreover, some SNPs were associated with slower rate of PD progression in an unmedicated state, while faster motor deterioration in PD was observed in patients with certain SNPs (Hayete et al., 2017; Martinez-Carrasco et al., 2023; Ortega et al., 2021). Another study showed that GBA-PD patients had worse motor progression in comparison with idiopathic PD or LRRK2 PD (Ortega et al., 2021). The aforementioned studies shed light on the genes and SNPs that influence PD progression at the level of drug response, clinical outcome measures, longitudinal outcomes and potential biomarkers for disease.

2.3.5 Machine learning approaches for PD progression modelling

Study selection

In the Rayyan bibliographic searches and using the software, we selected the keywords "progression" and "longitudinal," and identified 79 records. We then reviewed the titles and abstracts of these records to identify studies that utilized ML approaches for modelling the progression of PD, excluding review studies and those focused on remote disease monitoring, symptom assessment and classification, and prediction and classification of PD. This process yielded 8 relevant records. An extra number of five papers were identified through extra search of the list of references of the eight initially included papers. Thus, the final number of records is 13.

Table 18 outlines the criteria for determining study eligibility. In summary, a study was deemed eligible if it met the following conditions:

Researching the progression of PD in a cohort of individuals diagnosed with PD,

AND

The analysis of the study data was conducted using ML tools. This includes the application of ML models that incorporate training/testing or training/validation datasets and provide metrics indicating the performance of the ML model in predicting or understanding the progression of PD.

We particularly focused on study designs that incorporated longitudinal data and employed ML approaches to predict the progression of the disease at future time points.

Table 18 Selection criteria for machine learning and PD progression

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Analysis	ML approach for PD progression
Results	At least one model performance metric

Study characteristics

Among the reviewed studies (**Table 19**), at the input level, three studies integrated gait features such as step width and step length for their models (Varrecchia et al., 2021; Rehman et al., 2021; Sotirakis et al., 2023). Four additional studies employed acoustic features like Jitter and Shimmer (Naranjo et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2020; Wan et al., 2018; Nilashi et al., 2017). Furthermore, three studies employed a blend of clinical, imaging and medication data (Severson et al., 2021; Velseboer, 2016; Simuni, 2016). Another study focused on measuring serum cytokine levels (Rastegar, 2019). Additionally, one study utilized a combination of genetic, imaging, clinical and demographic variables (Latourelle, 2017). Whereas another study did not specify the input features used in its model.

At the level of the model, different approaches were utilized. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have been employed (Varrecchia et al., 2021), while other ML algorithms, including Random Forest Regressor and extreme gradient boosting (XGB), have also been adopted (Sotirakis et al., 2023; Raza et al., 2020). Advanced models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with rectified linear activation function (ReLU) were utilized by Rehman et al. (2021); and more specialized methods like the Hypergraph partitioning algorithm and Incremental Support Vector Regression were implemented by Nilashi et al. (2022) and Nilashi et al. (2017). A personalized input-output hidden Markov model was applied by Severson et al. (2021), and a Hidden Markov model by Naranjo et al. (2021). Ensemble methods were also explored, including a combination of DMLP, logistic regression, Random Forests, k-nearest neighbours, and M5P in Wan et al. (2018), and other ensemble utilized using the REFS platform in Latourelle (2017). Other studies like those by Velseboer (2016) and Simuni (2016) have used statistical approaches with multivariable logistic regression analysis and a combination of random survival forests with a Cox model for prognostic indexing, respectively. Additionally, Rastegar (2019) employed Random Forest and elastic-net algorithms to enhance the predictive performance.

Table 19 Studies about machine learning and PD progression

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
Varrecch et al., 2021	76 PwPD and 67 HC	UPDRS III and H-Y staging system	Time distance: walking speed (m/s), cadence (step/s), step width (m), step length (m), stance, swing, and double support phase durations. Kinematic data: The anatomical joint angles of the hip, knee, ankle, trunk, and pelvis and the corresponding ranges of motion of the joints	PCA	ANN	Performance ranged from 82–98% for distinguishing PD from controls, and 66.16–77.2% for staging classification.	the numerical sum of knee and trunk rotation angles, showed a good ability to discriminate PwPD from HCs. Two combinations of four features showed good ability to classify PD stages according to the H-Y scale
Naranjo et al., 2021	36 PwPD	Hoehn and Yahr scale	Hypokinetic dysarthria Cepstral peak prominence Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients Vocal fold vibration Gender	N/A	Hidden Markov model	Global accuracy rate 78.29% MAE 0.035449(0.005178) RMSE 0.080724(0.012229)	The performance result of the HMM model was promising and showed that acoustic features may be useful in tracking the progression of PD
Rehman et al., 2021	119 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	Magnitude of the three axes of the raw gait data signals	In the deep learning model, a 1D convolutional bloc extracted features from the magnitude of the raw gait data	Convolutional Neural Network (rectified linear activation function (ReLU))	Pearson correlation of 0.82, ICC of 0.76, and mean absolute error of 6.29	The DL-CNN model trained on baseline gait data can accurately predict MDS-UPDRS-III scores after 3 years, showing potential for assessing PD motor severity and supporting clinical management.
Sotirakis et al., 2023	91 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	29 features identified as significantly progressing	During model development using forward feature selection and PCA	Random Forest Regressor Multivariate linear regression	Best model (Random Forest) had an RMSE of 10.02 (against UPDRS-III score)	the study's machine learning model could detect PD motor symptom progression earlier and more accurately than clinical assessments

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
Raza et al., 2020	42 PwPD	MDS-UPDRS-III	A total of 16 dysphonia measures extracted from the voice recording obtained through the AHTD device		extreme gradient boosting (XGB) is used as a regression method	MAE of 2.97 ± 0.05 and 6.45 ± 0.21 in the training and testing datasets respectively to predict the overall UPDRS score.	they stated that the IoT framework and machine learning algorithm efficiently predict Parkinson's disease progression, outperforming state-of-the-art techniques
Nilashi et al., 2022	-	motor UPDRS, overall UPDRS	Specific data features analysed were not mentioned.	PCA	Hypergraph partitioning algorithm Neural network Multiple linear regression Support vector regression Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system Self-organizing map Deep belief network Expectation-maximization	Best results for the HGPA+SOM+SVR ensemble: Motor-UPDRS (MAE: 0.5540, RMSE: 0.4116, R ² : 0.9139) Total-UPDRS(MAE: 0.5565, RMSE: 0.4179, R ² : 0.9058)	The study concludes that expectation-maximization with support vector regression ensembles can improve prediction accuracy for Motor-UPDRS and Total-UPDRS scores compared to other techniques
Wan et al., 2018	20 PwPD and 20 HC	UPDRS scores	23 feature parameters extracted from voice samples: movement data from smartphones	N/A	DMLP, along with logistic regression, Random Forests, k-nearest neighbours, and M5P	DMLP classifier produces the best performance	DMLP classifier effectively distinguishes between Parkinson's patients and healthy controls, offering a promising tool for non-invasive monitoring and severity estimation of Parkinson's disease
Nilashi et al., 2017	5875 records	Total UPDRS Motor UPDRS	Jitter, Shimmer, HNR, RPDE, DFA, PPE	non-linear iterative partial least squares (NIPALS)	Incremental Support Vector Regression	MAE and R ² for the Total-UPDRS were respectively MAE = 0.4656 and R ² = 0.885,	the prediction method is integrated with dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques improved the

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
						and for Motor-UPDRS were respectively MAE = 0.4967 and R ² = 0.868.	accuracy prediction of PD and reduced the computation time.
Severson et al., 2021	423 PwPD and 196 HC from PPMI. 610 patients PDBP	Mild cognitive impairment, dementia, dyskinesia, presence of motor fluctuations, functional impairment from motor fluctuations, H-Y score, and death.	Clinical, imaging, and medication data were analysed.	latent variable model for dimensionality reduction and feature selection.	A personalized input-output hidden Markov model was applied for disease progression modelling.	For the PPMI testing set: HMM: Average likelihood of -346 with a standard deviation (SD) of 120. PIOHMM: Average likelihood of -330 with an SD of 105. For the PDBP set: HMM: Average likelihood of -127 with an SD of 114. PIOHMM: Average likelihood of -123 with an SD of 107.	The model discovered eight disease states with non-sequential, overlapping progression trajectories, highlighting the heterogeneity of PD progression and the ineffectiveness of static subtype assignment
Velseboer, 2016	The CARPA cohort included 111 patients, and the CamPaIGN cohort included 108 patients for the validation set.	A composite outcome measure was created, classifying patients as having an unfavourable prognosis based on the presence of postural instability, dementia at the 5-year assessment, or earlier death.	Candidate predictor variables included demographic information, clinical characteristics, and specific assessments like the UPDRS-ME axial score and animal fluency score.	N/A	multivariable logistic regression analysis	AUC = 0.85	The study developed a reliable model for predicting 5-year outcomes in newly diagnosed Parkinson's disease patients, which can be useful for clinical trial selection and patient counselling.

Study	Sample size	Clinical outcome measures	Features	Feature selection	Model(s)	Model performance scores	Key take-aways
Simuni, 2016	423 PD participants and 196 healthy controls were enrolled.	MDS-UPDRS total score	Data included biofluids and imaging biomarkers, notably dopamine transporter (DAT) imaging striatal binding ratios.	N/A	The study employed random survival forests for the analysis and developed a prognostic index based on a Cox model.	For the RSF model with the three top predictors, C = 0.70 and pseudo-R2 = 0.13.	The study found that a subset of three predictors—disease duration, the modified Schwab and England activities of daily living scale, and the MDS-UPDRS total score—modestly predicted time to initiation of symptomatic therapy (C = 0.70, pseudo-R2 = 0.13). Biological variables did not increase prediction accuracy. A prognostic index was created for indicating the risk of initiation of symptomatic therapy in PD patients.
Rastegar, 2019	160 PD patients at baseline	UPDRS III and H-Y staging system	Serum cytokine levels were measured, including 27 inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, using a magnetic human cytokine multiplex assay.	For each algorithm the variables that contributed the most to the predictive performance are listed	Random Forest and elastic-net algorithms	The Random Forest model achieved an NRMSE of 0.1123 for the Hoehn and Yahr scale and 0.1193 for UPDRS III	Peripheral cytokines, particularly MIP1 α and MCP1, significantly contributed to predicting PD progression, suggesting their potential utility in developing refined models for patient stratification and clinical trial endpoints.
Latourelle, 2017	117 controls and 312 PD cases from the PPMI database, with additional validation in an independent cohort (LABS-PD) of 317 PD patients	MDS-UPDRS Parts II and III scores	genetic SNPs, CSF protein biomarkers, DaTscan imaging variables, and clinical and demographic variables.	Bayesian machine-learning techniques (REFS platform) were used to select features and construct predictive models.	An ensemble of models was constructed using the REFS™ platform	In the PPMI sample, the model ensemble exhibited strong performance (R2=41%, 95% CI: 35% – 47%) but showed reduced performance in the LABS-PD cohort (R2=9%, 95% CI: 4% – 16%).	The study confirmed established predictors and identified novel predictors of PD motor progression, including a significant epistatic genetic interaction specific to PD. Genetic variation was found to be the most useful predictive marker.

General discussion

There was a wide diversity in modelling approaches which reflects the complex nature of PD disease progression and the interdisciplinary effort by previous studies to understand and predict it effectively. Most research studies target predictions of progression outcomes at a single future time point rather than examining multiple future intervals. One study predicts the time to initiation of symptomatic treatment using measurements of serum cytokine levels (Simuni et al., 2016). Another study developed a model for predicting 5-year outcomes (e.g., postural instability, dementia, death) in newly diagnosed PD patients (Velseboer, 2016). Gait and acoustic features are well investigated in the prediction of the severity of PD, highlighting the importance of these features. The UPDRS-III and H-Stages are frequently employed as metrics to quantify disease progression. These scales are pivotal for evaluating the severity and progression of motor symptoms. Research focuses on the ON state (when medication is effective) of PD, often overlooking the OFF state (when medication effects are negligible). Replication of existing models across cohorts remains limited, and translation of the results into clinical practice has not yet been achieved. With a few recent exceptions, most of the models rely only on cross-sectional data and assume that each PD subtype follows a fixed progression trajectory, without considering positive or negative medication effects.

2.3.6 Digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Since self-reporting of tremor and dyskinesia symptoms at clinical assessments are less accurate, digital means are increasingly used for systematically capturing, assessing, and monitoring these symptoms on a daily basis. This literature review aims to investigate proposed approaches for assessing tremor and dyskinesia with wearable sensors, smartphones attached to hands or custom-made devices to monitor these motor symptoms. The most popular sensors used are accelerometers, measuring linear acceleration, while gyroscopes, measuring angular velocity can also be used, as human motion mainly consists of rotations about joints. Furthermore, additional sensors, such as magnetometers may be used to provide measurements for correcting accelerometer or gyroscope data (Foxlin et al., 2002). In this way, continuous monitoring of these motor symptoms is achieved, leading to improved disease management.

Study selection

Within the literature search on wearable sensors, with the Rayyan software we used the keywords “tremor” and “dyskinesia” for both bibliographic searches described in Section 2.1. This search yielded 249 unique records (specifically 223 for tremor and 37 for dyskinesia/dyskinesias). A set of exclusion criteria were used, including a) Review articles, b) Articles focusing on other motor symptoms, such as balance, posture or gait, c) Articles focusing on “tremor” that do not include rest tremor data assessment (Rest tremors occur when sitting or lying down and relaxed). Subsequently, three independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. This filtering resulted in 29 records. We identified two other important articles through other references (Powers et al., 2021; Ziogas et al., 2023) and added them for review.

Table 20 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Inclusion criteria included the following:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,
AND
Methods and data for rest tremor or dyskinesia assessment were provided,
AND
Use of data from accelerometer or gyroscope sensors in wearable or smart devices that enable monitoring of symptoms throughout the day OR use of data from video sensors for rest tremor and dyskinesia assessment.

Table 20 Selection criteria for digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Measurement	Rest tremor and/or dyskinesia data available
Sensors	Wearable/video sensors and/or smart devices appropriate for daily use.

Study characteristics

From the 29 studies selected (**Table 21**), most (25) include results regarding rest tremor assessment, while only five (5) include models and results regarding dyskinesia assessment. MDS-UPDRS-III Items 3.17 (Rest tremor amplitude) and 3.18 (rest tremor constancy) are mainly used as clinical outcome for the quantification of tremor symptoms. Dyskinesia assessment using accelerometer data mainly focuses on chorea symptoms (abnormal involuntary movements), as dystonia symptoms involve pose/posture and do not involve movement. Most included studies recruited participants with a mean age ranging from 58 to 85 years; the percentage of male participants ranged from 36 to 87.5%.

Digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

The main objective of this review was to assess the feasibility and efficiency of digital solutions for capturing tremor and dyskinesia of upper limbs. The main objective of AI-PROGNOSIS is to design and develop passive capturing solutions for remote monitoring of tremor and dyskinesia related to PD, outside the clinical setting, using non-obtrusive hardware, such as IMU data from consumer smartwatches. Regarding tremor effects, AI-PROGNOSIS focuses on estimating rest tremor, i.e., tremor occurring when voluntary muscle activity is absent (e.g., when resting on the arm of a chair), where the person is relaxed and completely supported against gravity. Dyskinesia (i.e., involuntary, erratic, writhing movements) will also be detected using IMU data from consumer smartwatches, and emphasis is given to a particular type of dyskinesia, namely chorea, that involves abrupt and unpredictable movements that can be detected using IMU data. We thus excluded papers that do not meet these criteria, e.g. focus on tests in the clinical setting or active tests or do not assess rest tremor or dyskinesia. A notable exception is the use of video sensors for assessing tremor or dyskinesia, where a limited number of some innovative solutions have been included.

Table 21 Studies about digital assessments of tremor and dyskinesias

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Samadi et al., 2020	50 PD	58±7.4 y	N/A	Accelerometer, Sony Xperia SP Android smartphone	Mean PSD, Side Frequency (SF)	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	Naive bayes classifier	Accuracy, specificity, sensitivity	accuracy = 95.91±1.51 specificity = 95.8±1.21 sensitivity = 93.87±0.95	ML models that use frequency domain features from STFT can classify patients to their UPDRS scores
Li et al., 2018	9 PD	64 y	55%	Video at 30fps + Open pose 2D skeleton	32 for each joint. 15 kinematic, 16 spectral, last convex hull of the area that a joint moved within.	Sum of the seven highest impairment scores for each body part (face, neck, right arm/shoulder, left arm/shoulder, trunk, right leg/hip, left leg/hip) across 3 tasks (communication, drinking, ambulation), [0, 28].		Area under ROC (AUC)	The best AUC for detecting onset of dyskinesia was 0.822 and for remission of dyskinesia was 0.958, compared to 0.826 and 0.802 for the UPDRS.	(D) Features achieved similar or superior performance to the UPDRS for detecting the onset and remission of dyskinesia.
Hssayeni et al., 2021		58 ± 10 y	60%	Gyroscope, two sensors were mounted on the wrist and ankle. (Great Lakes NeuroTechnologies Inc., Cleveland, OH at 64Hz	13 temporal and spectral features	mAIMS score. In mAIMS, a severity score between 0 and 4 (no dyskinesia to severe dyskinesia) is given for each one of the four extremities, head/neck, trunk and global. The total mAIMS is the sum of all these sub-scores resulting in a range between 0 and 28.	LSTM	Pearson correlation (r) and mean absolute error (MAE)	r = 0.87 (p < 0.001) and MAE = 1.74 (6.2% of the maximum mAIMS score)	(D) LSTM demonstrated good performance
Wang et al., 2021	55 PD	N/A	N/A	Microsoft Kinect TM v2, specifically	21 hand key-points using media pipe.	Bain and Findley Tremor Clinical Rating Scale [0, 10]	1D CNN - LSTM	Average accuracy, Average	accuracy = 0.81,	hand tremor could be automatically detected

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
				1920x1080 RGB at 30fps	Then, use those to calculate a) frequency of motion direction changes and b) change in distance of hand movement			precision, Average recall, Average F1 score	precision = 0.81, recall = 0.79, F1= 0.80	despite a cluttered background
San-Segundo et al., 2020	12 PD	62-85 y	N/A	Accelerometer from Axivity AX3 at 100Hz	Original spectrum, Tremor spectrum, non-tremor spectrum for x, y, z in accelerometer	Tremor detection, i.e., Tremor/No tremor	1DCNN-MLP	LAB: Area Under the Curve (AUC) and False Positive Rate (FPR) at a 0.90 True Positive Rate (TPR). WILD: Spearman's r between percentage of tremor constancy and weak labels (<33%, 33-66%, and >66% tremor to Almost	LAB: AUC=0.887 FPR=0.30 at 0.90 TPR WILD: weakLAB labels + WILD training /WILD = -0.3 Spearman's r	When developing a real system, use MFCCs-T/NT when the amount of available data is not sufficient to train a deep neural network. In this situation, handcrafted features with traditional machine learning algorithms, like Random Forest, provide a reasonable performance. Additionally, the method for tremor spectrum extraction proposed in this paper contributes to increase this performance independently of the amount of available data. On the other hand, if there are enough data for training, the CNN-T/NT approach is preferred because this approach can learn relevant

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
								none, Half the time, and almost always)		features for tremor detection"
Adams et al., 2023	82 PD, 50 HC. For tremor specifically, 44 PD, 22 HC	PD cohort (n = 82): 63.3 +- 9.4 HC (n = 50): 60.2 +- 9.9	PD cohort : 56% HC: 36%	Accelerometry data and tremor scores were collected from the smartwatch via Apple's Movement Disorders API	Tremor classification from Apple's movement disorder application	The relationship between the passive tremor fraction and tremor res from the MDS-UPDRS was estimated using linear regression.			Tremor fraction measured correlated moderately with self-reported tremor severity (MDS-UPDRS part II, item 10, r = 0.43, p = 0.003), very strongly with clinician-reported upper extremity rest tremor amplitude (MDS-UPDRS part III, item 17, r = 0.86, p < 0.001), and strongly with rest tremor constancy (MDSUPDRS part III, item 18, r = 0.79, p < 0.001	The smartwatch was worn on only one wrist. The side worn by PD participants (more affected side) and controls (individual preference) differed and at times was inconsistent with actual use. Standardizing wear for all participants to one side may be simpler and provide more consistent data.
Liu et al., 2023	130 PD	N/A	N/A	Sony camera 1920x1280@30fps	Eulerian Video Magnification (EVM)	modified MDS-UPDRS [0,1,2,3+]	Resnet50 + Global Temporal Shift Module	AUC, precision, recall, F1 score	mean Precision of 0.92, mean recall of 90%, and F1 score	EVM pre-processing of video and temporal differences as input, along with ResNet

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
					processed video to enhance temporal differences between frames		(based on TSM)		of 0.91 for hand rest tremors.	embedded with a novel module, namely Global Shift Module (GSM), seems to be able to capture rest and postural tremor from videos
Li et al., 2022	93 PD, 27 HC	N/A	N/A	Smartphone camera@30 fps	Hand joints from media pipe to measure speed and distance between thumb and index fingers	MDS-UPDRS finger tapping score (0, 4)	CNN	accuracy	accuracy: 79.7	(D) Better to use extracted joints as input data rather than the video (with a 3DCNN model). Range of motion (i.e. distance between joints) might be a better feature than speed
Bazgir et al., 2018	52 PD (36 Training /16 testing)	PD: 54±13 HC: 53±7	Train: 55% Test: 62.5%	Smartphone attached to hands	F0 (fundamental frequency), MaxPSD, MeanPSD\, SF50, F50, F50-F0	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	4 classifiers: Naive Bayesian/KN N/ANN/SVM	Test accuracy	Naive Bayesian 89% KNN 52% ANN 81% SVM 60%	Of the four tested classifiers, the Naive Bayesian approach was the most accurate one.
Pan et al., 2015	40 PD	44-84y	87.5%	For hand rest tremor user attaches the smartphone to the back of the hand and leaves the hand hanging for 20 seconds	Five power spectrum features and the average acceleration of motion of hand resting tremor.	UPDRS III Item 20 (1-3)	SVM	sensitivity/s pecificity	sensitivity was .77 and specificity was .82	Cost, size, unobtrusiveness, and ease of use are all factors impacting usefulness of such a system.
Lones et al., 2017	Study 1: 6, Study 2:17	Study 1: 71±8.9 Study 2: 65±7.3	Study 1: 66.6% Study	Six degrees of freedom wearable accelerometer	Acceleration time series	UPDRS (0-4)	Genetic Programming : Implicit context	ROC curve, or AUC, when discriminati	AUC up to 0.9	Time domain classifiers have significantly higher AUCs than spectral classifiers, reaching

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
			2: 64.7%	and gyroscope sensor modules			representation Cartesian GP (IRCGP)	ng samples of Grade 3 and 4 dyskinesia from movement samples with no dyskinesia		AUCs more than 0.9 on the test set. More accurate classifiers can be built from accelerometry (than gyro) data. Good ability to separate samples with Grades 3 and 4 dyskinesia from samples with no dyskinesia
Pierleon et al., 2019	40 PD/15 Controls	PD: 65-80 HC: 53-67	56%	Custom wearable device with accelerometer and gyroscope	FFT, F0, PSD estimation	UPDRS scale [0, 4]	Thresholding based two parameters (K,H) calculated from PSD	accuracy	Accuracy = 97.7%	Completely unobtrusive approach based on a custom-made wearable using accelerometer and gyroscope.
Kostikis et al., 2015	25 PD/20 Controls	PD: 70.91 ± 11.78 HC: 67.20 ± 6.25	49%	i-Phone phone's accelerometer and gyroscope	16 classification features	PD/HC discrimination	Six ML algorithms tested	Sensitivity (TP), specificity (TN), and AUC	AUC between 0.80 and 0.94	Proposed method for quantifying upper limb Parkinsonian tremor can be used both in a clinical and home settings
Duque et al., 2020	19 PD, 20 ET and 12 HS			Gyroscope providing angular velocities	Eight kinematic features in the frequency domain	PD(4-6Hz)/ET(1-16Hz)	Many classification algorithms are evaluated. Best: Linear SVM	Accuracy, sensitivity, specificity	Average accuracy 77.89.9% (75.7% sensitivity, 80.0% specificity)	Accuracy of the tremor differentiation using a gyroscope sensor is comparable to the performance obtained using a mobile phone's built-in accelerometer
Jeon et al., 2017	85 PD	65.96 ± 9.19	48%	Accelerometer and a gyroscope	13 features from each of four signals (acceleration, angular velocity, displacement, and angle)		Decision tree (DT), SVM, discriminant analysis (DA), RF, and kNN	Accuracy, Recall. Precision, AUC	85.5% using Decision Tree classifier	Very efficient approach for the development of an automatic scoring system for tremors in PD using machine-learning algorithms

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Sigcha et al., 2021	18 PD	64.9 ± 7.6	44%	Triaxial accelerometer data from smartwatch	Multiple time and frequency characteristics	UPDRS III Item 17 and 18 (rest tremor)	multitask CNN trained with FFT	AUC, sensitivity, specificity	sensitivity: 86.1% specificity: 86.1% AUC: 0.93	Studies the use of consumer smartwatches and their embedded accelerometers for monitoring and evaluating resting tremor in PD patients. Includes a Table of highlighted research articles for tremor analysis using wearable sensors (Table 1).
Legaria-Santiago et al., 2022	PT: 354 (PD) 40(HC) / RT 200 (PD) 20 (HC)	PD: 66 ±9.7 HC:31.28 ±14.1	PD: 38% HC: 75%	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer (only for static acceleration cancellation)	Five biomechanical indicators based on time, frequency, and energy	MDS-UPDRS scale (0, 4)	Fuzzy inference model	Recall, Precision	Normal 0.90(R) .89 (P) / Slight 0.81(R) .82(P) / Mild 1(R) 1(P) / Moderate 1(R) 1(P)	Expert system based on biomechanical measurements and explainable inference rules
Yuan et al., 2021	20 PD	60.7 ± 8.6	75%	Wrist accelerometers	Mean amplitude, Sample entropy, Dominant frequency, Energy, Spectrum concentration around dominant frequency	Tremor detection (0-1)	KNN / RF / AdaBoost / SVM	Sensitivity (%) Specificity (%) Accuracy (%) F1 score (%)	Best classification(detection) model is RF: Sensitivity 95.18 Specificity 94.44 Accuracy 94.81 F1 score 94.83	Balance data before classification using the SMOTE algorithm, A new indicator, namely Tremor timing ratio (TTR), was designed and calculated to quantify tremor severity.
Aghanavasi et al., 2020	19 PD	71.4 ± 6.3 years	73.6%	Accelerometers and gyroscopes on each leg	24 features for each foot	UPDRS scale [0, 4], TRS scale [-4,0], dyskinesia scale [0,4]	SVM, Decision Trees, Linear Regression	Pearson correlation coefficients and Root Mean Squared	correlation coefficient (RMSE)of: TRS:0.81, UPDRS #31: 0.83,	The best combination of feature selection and machine learning methods was stepwise regression and SVM, leg agility data is

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
								Error (RMSE)	SUMUPDRS: 0.78, dyskinesia: 0.67	less suitable for capturing dyskinesias compared to motion sensor data during walking tests
Sun et al., 2023	30 PD	67.43 y	60%	Accelerometers and gyroscopes on both wrists	6 * 14 features from both the time and frequency domains (selection of hand-crafted features based on domain knowledge)	Tremor/No tremor	Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbours, Support Vector Machines, Convolutional Neural Networks	accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score	SVM: accuracy: 92.28%, precision: 92.40%, recall: 92.13%, F1-score: 92.26%	The performance of models using hand-crafted features surpasses CNN data-driven features, providing more specific boundaries in 2-D t-SNE feature visualization
Teng et al., 2023	48 PD, 60 HC	PD 58.6 ± 5.9 y, HC 64.9 ± 4.8 y	N/A	Touchscreen gestures and IMU signals	56 features of 4 categories (finger dexterity, posture stiffness, trajectory information, and pressure information)	Healthy/PD	XGBoost, Decision Tree, Random Forest	accuracy, precision, recall	accuracy: 91.6% (±1.5), recall: 84.85% (±4.7), recall: 85.2% (±2.7) (averaged on tap, swipe)	Integration of data from various sources (e.g., wearables, electrode patches, customized sensors) provides richer information for predicting PD onset, certain features such as finger dexterity and tremor are more important in predicting PD onset
Lo et al., 2019	237 PD	N/A	N/A	Voice, touchscreen, accelerometer	998 (top 30)		Random Forest	AUC	For all outcome predictions AUC>0.9 (all features), AUC>0.75 (top30 features)	Allows for early prediction of key clinical outcomes in Parkinson's disease, potentially enabling personalized care and timely interventions based on predictive

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
										assessments using a smartphone test
Varghese et al., 2016	192 PD, 75 other movement disorders, 51 HC	65.71 ± 9.61 y, 60.88 ± 60.45 ± 14.22 y	62.57 %	Accelerometer			Fully Connected Network, Random Forest, SVM	accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score	Fully Connected Network (task1): accuracy: 89%, precision: 94%, recall: 92%, F1-score: 93%, SVM (task2): accuracy: 79%, precision: 81%, recall: 89%, F1-score: 85%	Mobile system only requires self-generated data from a 15-minute examination, not dependent on further patient data or external information systems, Machine Learning classifiers show high accuracy for distinguishing relevant diagnoses classes
Lin et al., 2023	84 PD, 80 ET	PD:58.13 ± 10.4, ET:58.7 ± 13.9	PD 54.76 % ET 46.25 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope			Random Forest, SVM	accuracy, Kappa, sensitivity, specificity, AUC	accuracy of 84%, Kappa of 0.68, sensitivity of 85.9%, specificity of 82.1%, and AUC of 0.912	Wearable sensor data paired with machine learning can differentiate early-stage PD from ET based on gait and postural transition parameters.
Hssayeni et al., 2019	24 PD	58.9 ± 9.3 y	58.33 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope	78		XGBoost, LSTM	total tremor sub-score [0–28], Resting and Action Tremor sub-score [0-8]	XGBoost: MAE: 1.56, r (p):0.96 (<1×10 ⁻⁴)	XGBoost surpassed LSTM, effectively capturing tremor fluctuations linked to medication intake, However, it exhibited lower specificity for non-tremor-dominant cases, indicating room for enhancement with a larger dataset covering higher tremor sub-scores
Kim et al., 2018	92 PD	67.1 ± 9.0 y	48.91 %	Accelerometer and gyroscope			CNN	accuracy, kappa,	accuracy = 0.85, linear	CNN can automatically learn concepts using

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
								correlation, RMSE	weighted kappa = 0.85, correlation = 0.93, RMSE = 0.35	minimally processed raw data without the use of a manual feature extraction process.
Powers et al., 2021	PD: 343 HC: 171	PD cohort1: 68.1± 9.1 y / PD cohort2: 71.4± 8.9 y / HC: 74.7± 5.4 y	PD: 69% HC: 49%	Raw accelerometer and gyroscope data from Apple Watch	Tremor detection: Sharp peaks in FFT within the 3-7Hz bins. Tremor assessment: Measuring displacement either in time or frequency domain. Dyskinesia: a) motion strength and b) spectral entropy/Calculation of a Choreiform Movement Score	a) Tremor detection (0/1), b) tremor classification into 4 classes: slight/mild/moderate/severe displacements	N/A	Validation of displacement using Motion capture tests	rank correlation coefficient	(D) Tremor: Computed displacement correlated with expert MDS-UPDRS tremor amplitude ratings, with a rank correlation coefficient of 0.80 Dyskinesia: CMS showed significant differences (P<0.001) for all pairwise comparisons using a Wilcoxon rank sum test
Mahadevan et al., 2020	PD: 31 HC:50	PD: 68.1 ± 8.13 HC: 43.9 ± 10.02	PD: 64% HC: 46%	Accelerometer	time and frequency domain features	tremor constancy (MDS-UPDRS III.18) and amplitude (MDS-UPDRS III.17)	Detection: binary resting tremor classifier (RF)	Detection: leave one-subject-out	Tremor Detection: accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score / Resting tremor: Kruskal–Wallis chi-squared, p	Tremor detection: 83% accuracy Rest tremor: good agreement with clinical ratings of resting tremor constancy (Kruskal–Wallis chi-squared = 27.52, p < 0.0001) and resting tremor amplitude (Kruskal–

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male %	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
										Wallis chi-squared = 18.14, p = 0.0004).
Ziogas et al., 2023	16 PD rest tremor dataset introduced by Beuter.	HAT: 58.5 ± 9.78yrs; LAT: 52.7 ± 10.19yrs	N/A	IMU data from a velocity-transducing laser	Set of proposed features that are drawn from the Bispectrum/Bicoherence domains	LAT/HAT (Low/High Amplitude Tremor)	Four classifiers are evaluated: RBF-SVM, Linear SVN, k-NN and Logistic Regression	Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO)	AUC	AUC score of 0.94 for the Medication treatment classification, 0.71 for the DBS treatment and 0.83 for LAT/HAT prediction.

*Papers including results on dyskinesia assessment are designated with (D) in the Notes column. The rest focus only on tremor assessment.

General discussion

Passive solutions for rest tremor monitoring based on Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data are increasingly popular in the literature, while similar approaches for dyskinesia have been less studied. Most papers use features in the time or frequency domain derived from either a) a single accelerometer sensor or b) accelerometer and gyroscope sensors. As noted in Powers et al. (2021), frequency domain approaches have limitations in accuracy due to a) the sinusoidal approximation performed and b) Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) frequency resolution limits; however, they are generally preferable as they are more robust than the time domain methods.

For the estimation of PD rest tremor, studies have reported the resting tremor (RT) of Parkinson's disease occurs at frequencies between 3-7 Hz, so in most cases, features are designed to detect sharp peaks within this range from the FFT or Power Spectral Density. Regarding dyskinesia detection, motion strength and spectral entropy features can be employed.

Also noteworthy are approaches detecting rest tremor from video by using Eulerian magnification to amplify changes in video pixels over time, so that very small motions can become visible to the human eye (Liu et al., 2023).

As evidenced by correlation analysis between digital and clinical measures, efficient rest tremor detection and assessment is possible based on data from a single accelerometer. On the other hand, dyskinesia seems to be much harder to identify.

2.3.7 Digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Digital technology is becoming increasingly popular in capturing specific motor symptoms in movement disorders. This literature review aims to investigate digital methods for assessing bradykinesia and rigidity. We primarily focused on studies leveraging wearable sensors and smart devices to monitor these motor symptoms. Utilising such technology enables the continuous monitoring of bradykinesia and rigidity, outside the clinic, albeit complementing clinical decision and personalising disease management.

Study selection

Within the Rayyan software, in the literature search machine learning and digital assessments, we used the following keywords: “bradykinesia”, “slowness”, “rigidity”, “limb” yielded 265 unique records. 32 of them were immediately excluded as they were reviews. We particularly focused on study designs that can be conducted remotely, at the comfort of people’s homes. Thus, studies involving lab-based equipment were excluded during the screening process. We also dropped studies presenting exclusively active tests. Subsequently, two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Where appropriate, the full text was read to confirm eligibility. This filtering returned five unique records.

Table 22 outlines the criteria for study eligibility. Briefly, a paper was considered eligible if:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,
AND
Clinical data of upper limb bradykinesia and/or rigidity assessment were provided,
AND
Use of experimental apparatus consisted of either wearable or smart devices. Use of devices for passive data recording.

Table 22 Selection criteria for digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Measurement	Upper limb bradykinesia and/or rigidity
Apparatus	Wearable sensors and/or smart devices. Passive testing.

Study characteristics

All five studies (**Table 23**) provided upper limb bradykinesia estimations, with two also estimating upper limb rigidity. MDS-UPDRS-III or the older version, UPDRS-III, were used as the clinical outcome for the quantification of motor symptoms. Interestingly, only two studies recruited a control group.

Noteworthy, the included studies covered a wide range of disease duration and severity. They recruited participants with a mean age ranging from 61 to 68.1 years; the percentage of male participants ranged from 45 to 78%. Mean disease duration varied from 2.5 to 12.5 years. The average motor severity score, in terms of MDS-UPDRS-III or UPDRS-III ranged from 16.9 to 50.5.

Digital assessments

Features derived from accelerometry, wearable electromyography (EMG) and keystroke dynamics can estimate the clinically assessed symptoms of bradykinesia and rigidity as evidenced by correlation analysis between digital and clinical measures. The included studies present diverse techniques for capturing rigidity and bradykinesia. Three studies utilized movement sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes, one study employed wearable EMG sensors alongside accelerometry, and one study utilised a touchscreen keyboard on smartphones to quantify keystroke dynamics.

Table 23 Studies about digital assessments of rigidity and bradykinesia

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male%	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
Iakovakis et al., 2018	PD=18, HC=15	PD=61, HC=57	78 for PD, 54 for HC	Custom smartphone keyboard	Statistical features of key hold time, Normalized flight time	UPDRS-III bradykinesia and rigidity features	RF	Pearson's correlation	Rigidity $r=0.83$, MAE=0.39 Upper Body bradykinesia $r=0.69$, MAE=0.41 Finger taps $r=0.68$, MAE= 0.55	Keystroke dynamics can accurately capture clinical rigidity and bradykinesia.
Rissanen et al., 2021	PD=16	62.75	56	Biceps brachii EMG and Accelerometer (side: most affected; sampling rate: EMG=1000Hz, Accelerometer=50Hz)	for EMG and ACC: kurtosis, burst frequency, correlation dimension, recurrence rate, signal power and sample entropy	UPDRS-III relevant items	PCA to identify the first factor and correlate it with the patients condition	Spearman rank correlation	The first Principal component was correlated with UPDRS-III	The first PC composed by both acceleration and EMG, was correlated with upper limb rigidity. EMG burst frequency was correlated with upper limb rigidity. EMG burst frequency, correlation Dimension, recurrence rate and ACC power (.2-4Hz) were correlated with upper limb bradykinesia
Oyama et al., 2023	PD=96	62.3	45.8	Smartwatch (side: most convenient; sampling rate N/A)	features for: bradykinesia (8), tremor(8), gait(4), overall motor(21)	MDS-UPDRS-III consensus scores	LASSO	Spearman rank correlation	Bradykinesia $r=0.63$,	Good correlation and test-retest reliability (ICC=0.72) and excellent effect size for medication effects.
Mahadevan et al., 2020	PD=31, HC=50	PD=68.1, HC=43.9	64 for PD, 46 for HC	Inertial sensor (accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer) on wrist (side: most affected for PD, dominant for HC; sampling rate: 128Hz)	Bradykinesia (4), Optimal feature: amplitude of hand movements	MDS-UPDRS finger tapping, hand movements, hand pronation-sup.	Mixed effects model	Pearson correlation	$R=0.67$	Bradykinesia feature of amplitude of hand movement for the windows that passed the chained assessments is strongly negatively correlated ($R=-0.69$) with bradykinesia score. Mixed effect model predicts relatively well the b/k hand UPDRS score.
Shawen et al., 2020	PD=13	62.1	69	Movement sensor and Apple watch (side: most affected; sampling rate:	74 kinematic features from each sensor	MDS-UPDRS tremor and bradykinesia scores	RF	AUROC	bradykinesia binary classification (have/not have) = 0.68 multiclass	Combining accelerometer with gyroscope data yielded better performance compared to accelerometer alone. Sampling

Study Characteristics					Method			Validation		Key take-aways
Study	Sample	Age	Male%	Sensors	Features	Label/ Clinical score	Model	Statistics	Results	
				62.5 and 50Hz respectively)					classification = 0,65	rates between 5 and 60Hz did not affect the bradykinesia classification accuracy, but 30Hz are needed to classify tremor.

General discussion

The aim of this review was to assess the effectiveness of digital tools in capturing bradykinesia and rigidity of upper limbs. Despite the abundance of studies conducting data collection in clinical settings, the objective of AI-PROGNOSIS is to assess these motor symptoms remotely and only 5 published studies to date were thus relevant.

The findings highlight the usefulness of digital tools such as wearable sensors (IMUs and EMG sensors) and sensors embedded into smart devices (i.e., smartwatches and smartphones) in accurately capturing rigidity and bradykinesia.

Studies by Iakovakis, Oyama, Mahadevan and Shawen, collectively demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of using digital tools to capture features associated with upper limb rigidity and bradykinesia. These features range from keystroke dynamics to kinematic features extracted from wearable sensors during everyday activities. One study (Oyama et al., 2023) additionally demonstrated the robustness of such technologies to capture motor symptoms as evidenced by good test-retest reliability. Notably, gyroscope data, alongside accelerometry can enhance the bradykinesia classification accuracy.

This review presents crucial methodological insights into the data collection parameters that are essential for conducting experiments to assess motor symptoms in PD. One critical aspect is the sampling rate of the sensors used in the included studies which impacts the granularity, and effectively the quality of the data. Additionally, since PD is associated with asymmetrical motor symptoms the choice of the side at which participants wear the smartwatch constitutes an additional issue to be decided. Careful consideration of those parameters is paramount for designing data collection in such populations.

2.3.8 Digital assessments of posture and balance

Study selection

Our selection strategy for posture/balance digital assessment research focuses on selecting relevant publications within the Rayyan digital sensor literature search using specific keywords, such as fall(s), posture, balance, gait, and freezing of gait (fog). We excluded technological interventions that were not intended or effective for PD posture/balance evaluation, research unrelated to PD, and studies that examined platforms/services other than mobile applications. Furthermore, research that did not use mobile applications or mobile technology as supplementary tools was omitted. We thoroughly reviewed the titles and abstracts, followed by full-text screening for possibly relevant papers. **Table 24** summarizes the criteria for study inclusion for posture and balance digital assessment of PD. Inclusion criteria included the following:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,

AND

Methods and data for posture and balance assessment were provided,

AND

Use of data from wearable sensors and/or smart devices that enable monitoring of PD symptoms OR use of data from videos for posture and balance assessment.

Table 24 Selection criteria for digital assessments of posture and balance

Item	Definition
Population	PD patients
Keywords	Balance, posture, FOG, freezing, gait, fall
Outcomes	Motor assessment, postural abnormalities, gait dynamics, gait disorders, walking abnormalities, MDS-UPDRS scores, FOG detection, balance evaluation, arm swing analysis, and classification of PD based on gait information.
Apparatus	Wearable sensors (such as ankle, chest, and waist sensors), depth cameras (e.g., Kinect), noise-cancelling headband microphones, smart pillboxes, smartphones (Huawei P40), RGB-D cameras (Kinect v2.0), MS Kinect sensors, video recording devices, marker-less motion tracking tools (e.g., AlphaPose, OpenPose), and specialized systems for gait analysis (e.g., e-Motion Capture System, DensePose)

Using the Rayyan bibliographic searches, 383 articles were considered relevant for posture and balance digital assessment. These articles were carefully chosen based on specific keywords, including balance (26 articles), gait (209 articles), posture (29 articles), freezing of gait (85 articles), and falls (11 articles). Following a meticulous screening process, which involved assessing 68 articles for eligibility, a total of 25 articles were ultimately selected for inclusion in the analysis. The reasons for exclusion varied and encompassed factors such as the use of inappropriate sensor types (e.g., wearable sensors lacking a smartphone app), impractical system architectures, absence of ML or DL models, articles falling outside the scope of the study, use of inappropriate samples (e.g., healthy individuals instead of PD patients), review articles, focus solely on feasibility and usability metrics, study protocols, PD detection using speech or acoustic analysis, and usability studies.

Study characteristics

The average age range recorded in studies such as Dias et al. (2020) and Hong et al. (2022) was between 50 and 70 years old, which is in line with the usual onset age of PD. Nonetheless, not all studies consistently reported on certain age groups. Furthermore, there was variation in the inclusion criteria for the severity of the condition; several studies focused on individuals with more advanced disease progression (Hong et al., 2022; Ferraris et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019), while other studies included individuals at different stages of the disease (Dias et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018). Several studies included control patients (Connie et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022; Abe et al., 2022; Procházka et al., 2015; Buongiorno et al., 2019; Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022; Guayacán et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2021; Urcuqui et al., 2018).

Important clinico-demographic data was missing from some studies (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020), reported motor severity scores (Aldegheri et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Procházka et al., 2015; Erfianto et al., 2023; Li et al., 2016; Tupa et al., 2015). Additionally, some studies did not include information about sex (Procházka et al., 2015; Li et al., 2016; Erfianto et al., 2023). Some studies (Aldegheri et

al., 2023; Guayacán et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2021; Urcuqui et al., 2018; Buongiorno et al., 2019; Abe et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2022; Connie et al., 2022) also did not provide information on sex, disease duration, PD subtypes, and motor severity scores.

Digital assessments of posture and balance

Various sensors were employed across studies for posture and balance digital assessment. Studies explored automated systems for remote monitoring and assessment (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020; Aldegheri et al., 2023), proposing automated caretaking, balance evaluation, and posture analysis software, respectively. Additionally, motor assessment tools and Kinect-based systems for differentiating PD stages were developed (Dias et al., 2020; Dranca et al., 2018). Depth sensors and skeleton tracking in three-dimensional space were employed, as demonstrated by some studies (Procházka et al., 2015; Ferraris et al., 2019; Abe et al., 2022) while body motion was captured using kinetic sensors in others (Li et al., 2016; Dranca et al., 2018). Video recording, coupled with pose estimation tools such as AlphaPose, was used for extracting human joint coordinates (Guo et al., 2022; Abe et al., 2022). Similarly, video recording combined with OpenPose for analysis was employed (Liu et al., 2022). Additionally, a combination of Wii balance boards and Kinect sensors was used for balance evaluation (Wei et al., 2020). Standard video recording equipment was utilized for analysis in another study (Eguchi et al., 2023). Automatic recognition of Freezing of Gait (FOG) in PD patients (Li et al., 2022) and detection of abnormal gait transitions (Erfianto et al., 2023) were also explored. A mobile decision support system for PD management (Buongiorno et al., 2019) and a machine learning algorithm for PD classification (Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022) were proposed. Further, regional kinematic analysis to identify potential digital biomarkers of PD was conducted (Guayacán et al., 2022). Lastly, a neural network for estimating MDS-UPDRS scores (Lu et al., 2021) and a machine learning classifier for PD analysis based on gait data (Urcuqui et al., 2018) were introduced.

Collectively, these studies showcase innovative technological advancements for improved PD monitoring and assessment. **Table 25** provides an overview of study characteristics, methodologies, and results in balance and posture digital assessment of PD.

Table 25 Studies about digital assessments of posture and balance

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022	Anomaly detection dataset available on Kaggle; PD = 25	Developing an automated caretaking system to enable remote monitoring	N/A	N/A	Wearable sensors, depth camera	Fall detection system	Random Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost, MMET; Precision, recall, F1, accuracy	Eye-Tact accurately predicts falls in PD patients
Dias et al., 2020	early PD / moderate PD = 10/17	To present a motor assessment tool in the context of the iPROGNOSIS project	H&Y, UPDRS part III 8 (items 23, 24, 25, 26 and 28), MoCA	N/A	Depth sensor system	Statistical features	Pearson correlation, linear regression; r, r ²	Tests useful for monitoring PD progression
Hong et al., 2022	PD/HC = 70/30. Within PD, PwPA (postural abnormalities) = 36; PwtPA = 34	To propose a summary index for postural abnormalities (IPA) based on Kinect depth camera and explored its clinical value	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, NMSS, CSI, HADS, PDQ-39, MMSE, BBE, PSQI	N/A	Kinect motion analysis device	Posture assessment	Kolmogorov–Smirnov, Mann–Whitney U, Spearman; Sensitivity, specificity, AUC	Significant correlations between IPA and PD severity measures
Wei et al., 2020	PD/HC = 20/21	To propose an automated balance evaluation system	N/A	N/A	Wii balance board, Kinect	Centre of mass/pressure	Convolutional Neural Network; Sensitivity, specificity	Balance evaluation model correlates with traditional assessments of

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
		for home and clinical use						balance in PD patients
Aldegheri et al., 2023	PD = 55	To present a software that augments the human skeleton extrapolated by HPE software from RGB pictures with exact bone points for posture evaluation through computer vision post-processing primitives	N/A	PD = 62, male PD = 66.7	AutoPosturePD software	Axial postural abnormalities	Pearson correlation, CNN; Significance analysis	AutoPosturePD provides low-cost, portable evaluation of postural abnormalities in PD
Ferraris et al., 2019	PD/HC = 14/12	To present a self-managed, home-based system for the automated assessment of a selected set of PD motor symptoms	UPDRS tasks 3.8, 3.9, 3.10, 3.12 and 3.13, MMSE, H&Y	PD/HC = 68.0/66.2, male PD/HC = 68.57/43.33, PwPA / PwtPA = 5.9/4.0, MDS-UPDRS III. PwPA / PwtPA = 43.6/30.9	Optical RGB-Depth device	Posture, lower limb movements	Elastic Net, kNN, MLR, SVM; Significance, accuracy	System feasible for objective, automated assessment of PD at home
Dranca et al., 2018	early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 8/11/11	To build a Kinect-based system that can	H&Y, FOG-Q	All subjects (23-81) y, All male subjects = 63.41	Kinetic sensor, smartphone	Limb angles	Decision trees, Bayesian networks,	Bayesian Network: 93.40%

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
		distinguish between different PD stages					neural networks, K-nearest neighbours	accuracy, 7 relevant features.
Li et al., 2022	PD = 50	To automatically recognize FOG in PD patients through videos taken by mobile phone	MMSE, FOG-Q, UPDRS III (3.10+3.11), LEDD	PD = 71, male PD = 70.9	Azure Kinect, smartphone	Gait parameters	XGBoost algorithm	LOSO method: sensitivity = 87.5%, specificity = 79.82%.
Ospina et al., 2019	PD/HC = 30/30	To assess differences in gait dynamics between PwPD and HC and to investigate the effects of aging on these differences	MDS-UPDRS III, FOG-Q, DGI, MoCA	PD = 69, male PD = 70.9, PD = 5.8	Kinetic sensor, depth camera	Joint motion data	Proposed method, Covariance, Lie relative, Joint methods	Proposed method: avg. accuracy 79.0%, best accuracy 91.1%.
Procházka et al., 2015	PD/ HC/ young HC	To present a novel method of Bayesian gait recognition	N/A	early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 68.73/70.56/72.57, male early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 62.5/100/81.81, early PD / PD No-FOG / PD FOG = 3.08/7.04/11.15	Video analysis	Knee joint kinematics	OpenPose, K-Nearest Neighbours	TPR reached 100% for some cases. Potential for elderly home rehab.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Li et al., 2016	HC/Hemiplegic/PD = 15	To present an algorithm for classification of gait disorders arising from neuro-degenerative diseases	N/A	PD = 71.44, male PD = 58, PD = 7.0	MS Kinect	Stride length, velocity, age	Neural networks, radial basis function network	Accuracy = 97.2%. MS Kinect for gait disorder recognition.
Erfianto et al., 2023	HC/ Gait impairments / PD = 4/7/3	To detect abnormalities in walking transitions using the EMD and Hilbert spectra	N/A	PD/HC = 66/66, male PD/HC = 57/63, PD = 5.8, MDS-UPDRS III: PD = 39.06	Video recording, AlphaPose	Spatial-temporal features	Convolutional network	Accuracy = 65.66. Deep supervision enhances robustness.
Ferraris et al., 2022	PD7HC = 16/13	To present a system for gait analysis	MMSE, UPDRS, H&Y	PD/ HC/ young HC = 73.8/52.9/23.8	OpenPose, smartphone	Gait features	Random Forest	Accuracy = 93%. Front and side views show discriminative features.
Tupa et al., 2015	PD / HC / young HC = 18/18/15	To detect selected gait attributes by Microsoft (MS) Kinect image and depth sensors	H&Y	(range) HC/Hemiplegic/PD = 46-75 / 50-83 / 60-85	MS Kinect (image and depth)	Gait features	Skeletal tracking, Bayesian classification	Accuracy = 91.7% at optimal threshold. MS Kinect for gait disorders.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Guo et al., 2022	PD = 142 (+ test dataset, PD = 42)	To propose a two-stream multi-scale sparse spatial-temporal attention-aware graph convolutional network (GCN) under deep supervision for gait assessment in PwD.	MDS-UPDRS Gait score	N/A	Video recording	Gait features	Convolutional neural network	Predicts UPDRS III with MAE±SD = 6.9±5.2, R2 = 0.59.
Connie et al., 2022	PD/HC = 74/93	To extract PD-discriminative gait features from raw videos of subjects and demonstrate the potential of marker-less motion capture for PD prediction	N/A	PD/HC = 68.9/56.3, male PD/HC = 68.75/65.54, PD = 8.9, UPDRS = 34.0	Microsoft Kinect v2	Gait features	SVM, ANN, cross-validation	ANN: 89.4% accuracy for PD diagnosis. Vision system for gait assessment.
Liu et al., 2022	PD/HC = 68/48	To assess the differences in gait characteristics between patients with PD and HCs using 2D video and explore the diagnostic value of 2D video for early-stage PD.	H&Y, MoCA	PD / HC / young HC = 73.6/55/23.7	Kinect Motion (RGB-D)	Arm and leg variables	LR, SVM, DT, NB, RF	RF: 81.8% to 84.5% accuracy. ML useful for PD classification.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Abe et al., 2022	PD/HC = 19/9	To compare the arm swing data of PwPD during gait with the numerical values of the MDS-UPDRS	MDS-UPDRS II (2.12, 2.13), III (3.3, 3.10, 3.11): score 0 to 30, sum of values of gait (SVG)	N/A	DensePose, video recordings	Velocity, acceleration, curvature	Mask R-CNN framework, RF, SVM	Accuracy = 99.62% for lower limbs and head regions.
Procházka et al., 2015	P/HC = 18/18	To present a novel method of gait recognition using the image and depth sensors of MS Kinect to track the skeleton of a moving body	N/A	N/A	Video recordings, 3D skeleton	Joint distances, motion features	OF-DDNet with RCE	AUC = 0.84, F1 = 0.67. Predicts MDS-UPDRS gait scores despite noise.
Eguchi et al., 2023	PD = 74	to assess the feasibility of predicting the UPDRS score from gait videos using a convolutional neural network (CNN) model	Total UPDRS part III score and 4 sub-scores of axial symptoms (27, 28, 29, 30), bradykinesia (23, 24, 25, 26, 31), rigidity (22), tremor (20,	N/A	MS Kinect, e-Motion Capture	Gait features	LR, NB, RF, DT	RF: 82% accuracy. Low-cost gait information capture system

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
			21), MMSE, LEDD, H&Y					
Buongiorno et al., 2019	PD/HC = 16/14	To design and test a mobile low-cost decision support system (DSS) that can be easily used both in specialized hospitals and at home	MDS-UPDRS	PD/HC = 63.18/61.52, male PD/HC = 58.82/45.83, PD = 4, MDS-UPDRS III: PD = 34.56 (H&Y I-II); 46.62 (H&Y III-IV)	Microsoft Kinect v2 (RGB-D camera)	Gait: temporal, spatial, angular features	SVM, ANN with 5-fold cross-validation	ANN achieved best results for PD diagnosis (accuracy = 89.4%, sensitivity = 87.0%, specificity = 91.8%). Accuracy for PD severity rating was 95.0% with fewer features. Vision system supports gait assessment.
Muñoz-Ospina et al., 2022	PD/HC = 30/30	To propose a ML technique algorithm using the variables from upper and lower limbs, to classify PwPD from HC	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS III, FOG-Q, MoCA	PD/HC (range): 40s to 70s / 20s to 50s, male PD/HC = 68.42/55.56	Kinectr Motion (RGB-D camera)	Arm and leg variables	LR, SVM, DT, NB, RF	RF model performed best across all datasets (Dataset A: 81.8%, Dataset B: 83.6%,

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
								Dataset C: 84.5%). ML techniques accurately classify PwPD.
Guayacán et al., 2022	PD/HC = 11/11	To perform a robust regional kinematic characterization, which may result in a potential digital biomarker of PD	H&Y	PD/HC = 73.6/55.0, male PD/HC = 66.67/38.89	DensePose, video recordings	Velocity, acceleration, curvature features	Mask R-CNN, RF, SVM	High accuracy achieved for lower-limbs and head regions (99.62%) and head and trunk (94.73%). Ability to recover kinematic patterns in different body segments.
Lu et al., 2021	PD = 55	To introduce an ordinal focal neural network to estimate the MDS-UPDRS scores, to leverage the ordinal nature of MDS-UPDRS scores and combat class imbalance	MDS-UPDRS III (3.10)	PD = 63.4, male PD = 41, PD = 11.3, PD 0 23.7	Video recordings of gait	Joint Collection Distances, two-scale motion features	OF-DDNet with RCE	Effective method to predict MDS-UPDRS gait scores despite noisy data.

Study Characteristics				Age / Description / % M / F / PD Duration / (UPDRS-III)	Technical issues			Main Findings
Authors	Sample size	Study aim	Clinical outcome measures (scale used)		Sensors Used	Features	Model & Performance	
Urcuqui et al., 2018	PD/HC = 30/30	To propose and evaluate a ML classifier for the analysis of PwPD through their gait information	N/A	PD/HC = 74.9/73.5, male PD/HC = 81.25/71.43	MS Kinect, e- Motion Capture System	18 features	LR, NB, RF, DT	RF model identified as best classifier, offering low-cost gait information capture.

General discussion

Overall, the aim of this systematic review was to evaluate the efficacy of digital assessments in accurately capturing balance and posture. While several studies have undertaken data collection in clinical settings, the objective of AI-PROGNOSIS project is to assess these motor symptoms using smartphone camera-enabled body tracking and active motor tests. Therefore, our focus was on methodological designs that are aligned with this objective.

Studies have employed a variety of sensors to gather data, including cameras (RGB, depth), wearable sensors (accelerometers, gyroscopes), and specialized equipment such as Kinect (Microsoft) (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). Common assessment tasks include gait analysis (looking at factors such as walking speed and stride length), posture assessment, fall detection, and monitoring PD progression (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020).

Various ML models have been used to analyze sensor data. Some common models include Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Ferraris et al., 2019; Dranca et al., 2018). Feature selection techniques are often used to identify the most relevant data for training the models (Ferraris et al., 2019; Dranca et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022). To evaluate how well the models perform, researchers use metrics, such as accuracy, AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and recall (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2020). Many studies report promising results, with accuracy exceeding 80% (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Ferraris et al., 2019; Procházka et al., 2015).

Overall, this review suggests that ML-based systems using various sensors can effectively assess movement disorders such as PD (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). These systems have the potential to provide objective and quantitative measures for gait analysis, posture assessment, and fall risk prediction (Radhakrishnan & James et al., 2022; Dias et al., 2020; Hong et al., 2022). The use of inexpensive sensors such as cameras and smartphones make these technologies potentially suitable for home-based monitoring (Dias et al., 2020; Erfianto et al., 2023). However, there are some limitations to this area of research. Some studies acknowledge limitations such as small sample sizes or the need for further validation in larger populations (Li et al., 2022; Erfianto et al., 2023). Additionally, generalizability to different patient populations or disease severities needs to be investigated.

In conclusion, ML-based systems using diverse sensors offer significant promise in objectively assessing movement disorders. Despite certain limitations, these technologies hold significant potential to offer valuable assistance in diagnosing, assessing, monitoring, and managing PD.

2.3.9 Digital assessments of cognitive decline

Study selection

Our selection strategy for cognitive decline focused on selecting relevant publications within the Rayyan digital biomarkers literature search. Based on the articles identified using the specified keywords, our focus for digitally assessing cognitive decline centered on terms such as “cognition” and “cognitive”. Although we searched for additional keywords such as “dementia”, “dysexecutive”, “amnesia”, or “memory”, we found no relevant results within the scope of the study. Therefore, we focused solely on cognition and cognitive aspects. This narrowed the scope to articles addressing cognitive decline in PD patients. Studies involving participants with mental disorders were excluded, along with reviews, posters, letters, and expert opinion publications. Additionally, technological interventions not targeting or useful for PD cognitive assessment, those unrelated to PD, or those examining platforms/services other than mobile apps were also excluded. The titles and abstracts of all records were examined,

and full-text screening was performed for potentially relevant studies. Duplicates were removed during the screening process.

Moreover, several articles were excluded after full-text screening due to various reasons, including complexity of assessment setups not aligning with the AI-PROGNOSIS project's scope or methods, and the lack of digital assessment of cognition. These exclusions were vital to maintaining the relevance and consistency of the studies included within the scope of the present review. Some studies required further verification regarding the suitability of assessment methodologies, such as the use of a microphone and laptop. In addition, exclusions occurred when articles primarily focused on motor symptoms rather than cognitive assessment. The criteria for study inclusion are provided in **Table 26**. Inclusion criteria were the following:

Study participants were people diagnosed with PD,
AND
Methods and data for cognitive decline assessment were provided,
AND
Use of data from wearable sensors and/or smart devices that enable monitoring of PD symptoms OR use of data from videos for cognitive assessment.

Table 26 Selection criteria for digital assessments of cognitive decline

Item	Definition
Population	People with PD
Keywords	cognitive, cognition
Outcomes	Clinical measures such as H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, PDQ-39, GDS, REM SBDQ, ESC, SOPDAS, TMT-A, TMT-B, WAIS, RCFT, WMS, MASQ, CFQ, PD-CFRS, ESS, IFS, RBDSQ, DAT-SBR, BJLOT, SFT, SDMT, HVLT, LNS, MSE-ADL, QUIP A-E, STAI, CDR-SB, K-MoCA, K-MMSE, K-IADL, Berg Balance Scale, TUG, Sit to Stand, 6MWT, Falls
Apparatus	wearable sensors, smartphones, smartwatches, computers, tablets, pens, wrist sensors (Microsoft Band), sensor insoles (Moticon), smart pillboxes (SimpleMed+), noise-canceling headband microphones (Genius HS-04SU) connected to laptops.

In the Rayyan bibliographic searches, the keywords cognition and cognitive were considered. This refined the pool to 61 articles, which were subsequently screened for their title, abstract, and full text. During the title screening phase, 34 articles were deemed relevant and included for further examination, while 23 articles were excluded. Moving to abstract screening, 26 articles met the criteria for inclusion, with only 3 articles being excluded. Subsequently, during

full text screening, 13 articles were found to meet all criteria and were included in the final analysis, while 12 articles were excluded. Finally, out of the initial pool of 61 articles, only 13 met the inclusion criteria. These selected articles showcased a diverse range of digital assessment tools and methodologies, including mobile applications, ML approaches, wearable electronic devices, and digital biomarkers.

Study characteristics

Participants recruited across the included studies had a mean age ranging from 50 to 85 years. However, three studies did not report age directly but stratified participants into 10-30 years range bands (Lo et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022). Additionally, some studies lacked reporting crucial clinico-demographic information. For instance, one study omitted reporting sex information (Tsiouris et al., 2017), seven studies did not include data on disease duration (Holmes et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022; Weizenbaum et al., 2021, Tsiouris et al., 2017; Ryu et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; and Prince et al., 2019), and five studies failed to provide information regarding the reported motor severity score (MDS-UPDRS-III) (Tsiouris et al., 2017; Templeton et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Prince et al., 2019).

Several studies included control groups (Adams et al., 2023; Garcia et al., 2022; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Ryu et al., 2022; Templeton et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019). The nature of the control groups varies across studies (e.g., healthy controls, non-movement disorder patients). The duration of the studies varied considerably, for instance, some studies were cross-sectional, meaning data was collected at a single point in time (Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Ryu et al., 2022; Garcia et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019; Templeton et al., 2022; Rosenblum et al., 2021). Others involved longitudinal monitoring, with data collection occurring over weeks or months (Adams et al., 2023; Motlese et al., 2020; Alberts et al., 2021; Lo et al., 2019). The frequency of monitoring also differed (e.g., daily, weekly, monthly). Details on specific monitoring schedules are not provided for all studies.

Digital assessments of cognitive decline

Several studies in this group (Adams et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2022; Lauraitis et al., 2020; Motlese et al., 2020; Rosenblum et al., 2021) followed patients for five to ten years. Three other studies (Prince et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022; Tsiouris et al., 2017) examined individuals with a weakened sense of smell (idiopathic hyposmia) to find very early signs (prodromal symptoms) of PD. Two of the studies focused on individuals with REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD), a condition that is occasionally linked to PD (Prince et al., 2019; Ryu et al., 2022).

More specifically, Adams et al. (2023) compared PD patients and controls using conventional cognitive measures such as the Symbol Digit Modalities Test (SDMT) and the Trail Making Test-A (TMT-A). They discovered that PD patients performed significantly worse on these tasks. Exploring innovative techniques, a novel strategy was investigated by Holmes et al. (2022) who used novel approaches for cognitive assessment by investigating keyboard patterns. Their study revealed moderate correlations between specific cognitive categories and keyboard usage.

Overall, smartphone technology emerges as a promising platform for cognitive assessment in PD. Weizenbaum et al. (2021) investigated the viability and efficacy of cognitive tests administered via smartphones and discovered associations with conventional neuropsychological assessments. This makes smartphones useful instruments for evaluating cognitive performance in people with PD. Simultaneously, tablet-based tests offer intriguing opportunities for cognitive assessment. Prince used tablet technology for neurocognitive evaluation and multi-source ensemble learning to improve classification accuracy in PD.

Similarly, Templeton showed the promise of digital biomarkers and tablet sensors in cognitive assessment by quantifying neurocognitive performance using ensemble learning approaches and tablet-based exams. Technology-driven interventions aim to improve cognitive performance in people with PD beyond evaluation approaches. To promote cognitive health, Ryu concentrated on creating entertaining tablet-based workouts specifically designed for those with PD. Lauraitis investigated deep learning and machine learning algorithms for self-administered cognitive evaluations on smartphones concurrently, suggesting a move toward customized and adaptive assessment techniques.

Smartphone-based remote monitoring presents a fundamental shift in disease management overall. There are links between smartphone-based measures and cognitive function, according to research by Motlese (2020) et al. and Tsiouris (2017) on smartphone applications for remote monitoring of PD patients. This takes advantage of the widespread use of smartphones in daily life to create opportunities for long-term monitoring and early cognitive decline detection. **Table 27** provides an overview of study characteristics, methodologies, and results in PD cognitive decline digital assessment.

Table 27 Studies about digital assessments of cognitive decline

Study characteristics				Study Population on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
Adams et al., 2023	PD/HC	Early PD features	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.3 / 56M 36F / 24.1 (PD), 2.7 (HC)	Wearables, smartphone	Gait, tremor, cognitive tests	Stat Anal	Correlations, AUC	P < 0.05 for TMT-A, fewer correct responses in PD vs HC; MoCA weakly correlated with cognitive and motor tasks	Differences in arm swing, tremor time, and finger tapping were observed between early PD and controls, correlating variably with traditional assessments. Various devices highlighted slower finger tapping, increased tremor, worse cognition, and speech changes in PD.
Holmes et al., 2022	NC/CI	Cognitive performance	ADLQ, DRS-2, FAB, MoCA, etc.	71.1 / 51M 60F / N/A	Computer, smartphone	Keystroke patterns	ML, DL	Correlations, R2, MSE	Moderate correlations with cognitive subdomains; typing patterns reflect neurodegeneration in MCI and Alzheimer's	Utilizing a subdomain framework improved ML model performance, reflecting neurodegeneration in MCI and Alzheimer's.
Lauraitis et al., 2020	ND/HC	Digitization of SAGE	SAGE methodology	42.6 / 86M 50F / N/A	Smartphone	Tremor, cognitive, speech	ML, DL	TPR, FPR, Precision, Recall, AUC, MCC	Hybrid model achieved 87.5% accuracy; best results with fusion of 13 classifiers and	Best results were achieved with a fusion of 13 classifiers for finger tapping and SAGE features (96.12% accuracy) and BiLSTM for

Study characteristics				Study Population on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
									BiLSTM for speech analysis	speech analysis (94.29% accuracy).
Motlese et al., 2020	PD	Smartphone monitoring	H&Y, UPDRS, etc.	66.5 / 67M / 22	Smartphone	Gait, tapping, tremor, cognitive tests	Stats	Descriptive stats, Wilcoxon, Chi-square	Adherence related to therapy modifications, motor fluctuations; NMSQ symptoms related to adherence	Gait, tapping, tremor, and cognitive outcomes correlated with disease duration, UPDRS-III, and H&Y.
Rosenblum et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone MCI detection	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.6 / 64.7M / 26.2	Smartphone	Motor tasks, self-report scales	Descriptive	p-values	No differences between high and low MoCA scores positive usability outcomes	Usability outcomes were positive, with users able to navigate the app easily.
Ryu et al., 2022	PD/AMP	Digitized cognitive tests	UPDRS, H&Y	72.7 / 72.7M / 20F / 23.1	Tablet	Drawing and memory tasks	Stats	Kruskal–Wallis ANOVA, correlations	PwPD: lower drawing scores, higher pen speed stochasticity; voice changes in PwPD: higher SNR	Voice characteristics differed stochastically between PwPD and NT, suggesting potential utility in cognitive tests.

Study characteristics				Study Population on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
Tsiouris et al., 2017	PD	PD_Manager framework	MDS-UPDRS	N/A	Wrist sensor, smartphone	Gait, tremor, cognition	N/A	Accuracy	Gait impairment, tremor, dyskinesia detection accurately estimated	Gait, fog, tremor, dyskinesia, and bradykinesia were assessed, with no focus on cognitive assessment.
Weizenbaum et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone cognitive test	H&Y, UPDRS, MoCA, etc.	63.2 / 51.9M / 27	Smartphone	Mobile games of memory and executive function	Stats	Descriptive stats, Pearson correlations	Age negatively associated with memory task; UPDRS total score negatively associated with Trails-B task	Smartphone tests predicted spatial span performance but not Trails-B task accuracy, potentially due to limited variability.
Garcia et al., 2022	PD/HC	Action-concept markers	H&Y, UPDRS-III, IFS, etc.	62.25 / 62.5M / 62.5F / 31	Headband mic, laptop	Retelling tasks	SVM, etc.	Accuracy, Sens, Spec, F-score	Acc/sens/spec/F-score: PD/HC = 72.5/80.0/65.0/72.2; PD-nMCI/PD-MCI = 69.5/75.0/65.0/67.6;	Discrimination between patients and controls was effective using action-concept markers, particularly with action-laden text scores.
Alberts et al., 2021	PD	Smartphone app feasibility	H&Y, MDS-UPDRS, TUG, etc.	68.4 / 65.2M / 23.65	Smartphone sensors	Finger tapping, processing speed tests	Stats	Descriptive stats, t-tests, correlations	Smartphone tech characterizes PD symptoms, e.g., bradykinesia,	Smartphone assessments effectively characterized bradykinesia, akinesia, and nonmotor function in PD.

Study characteristics				Study Population on Age / Gender / Motor Severity (UPDRS-III)	Technical Issues					Key Findings
Authors	Sample	Aim	Outcomes		Sensors	Features	Model	Performance Metric	Performance Scores	
									akinesia, nonmotor function	
Templeton et al., 2022	PD/HC	ML classification	PDQ-39, Berg Scale, etc.	50-85 / 48M 52F / N/A	Tablet sensors	14 neurocognitive tests, 208 biomarkers	Decision tree	Accuracy, precision, recall	Acc: PD vs HC = 92.6%; early PD vs advanced PD = 73.7%; higher than gold standard tools	Early-stage PD showed lower sensor-based scores, while advanced-stage individuals had elevated perceptions of executive and behavioural functions.
Prince et al., 2019	PD/HC = 62.6	Method for handling missing data using ensemble	Memory task	62.6 / N/A / N/A	Smartphone	Memory	LR, RF, Ensemble, CNN	Accuracy, F1	Developed method for handling missing data in memory task	Multi-source ensemble learning improved PD classification accuracy compared to traditional techniques.
Lo et al., 2019	PD-MCI/PD-nMCI	Predict future PD outcomes with smartphone	Falls, Freezing, Postural instability, Cognitive impairment, Difficulty doing hobbies, Need for help at home	70.0 / 64M 54F / 27.6 (PD-MCI), 24.3 (PD-nMCI)	Smartphone (Accelerometer, microphone, screen)	998 features	RF	AUC	Falls: > 0.90, Freezing: > 0.90, Postural instability: > 0.90, Cognitive impairment: > 0.90, Difficulty doing hobbies: > 0.90, Need for help at home: > 0.90	The ability to predict key future clinical outcomes using a simple smartphone test

General discussion

In general, this systematic review aimed to assess the effectiveness of digital assessments in capturing cognitive deficits. In particular, the aim of AI-PROGNOSIS project is to assess the cognitive function via passive interactions between users and smartphones, alongside active cognitive tests. From this perspective, our attention was directed towards methodological approaches that align with this objective.

Among the selected studies, there were 6 out of 13 studies that utilized ML or DL approaches. Kinematic data from wearable devices played a significant role in several studies, encompassing complementary measurements related to gait, tapping, tremor, cognitive function, drawing tasks, and speech segments. These measurements were captured using sensors integrated into smartphones, smartwatches, tablets, or wristbands. Specifically, some studies (Lauraitis et al., 2020; Tsiouris et al., 2017; Templeton et al., 2022; Prince et al., 2019; and Lo et al., 2019) incorporated kinematic data in their analyses. Among the selected studies, various ML models were employed, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes Classifiers (NB), and Decision Trees. Notably, the studies by Holmes et al. (2022) and Lauraitis et al. (2020) employed ML/DL approaches.

The remaining seven studies in the analysis explored various aspects of PD using different methodologies. Adams et al. (2023), focused on measuring features of early PD without utilizing ML or Random Forests, but extensively analysing kinematic data from wearable sensors. Motlese et al. (2020), assessed the feasibility of smartphone remote monitoring for PD, relying on statistical analyses for data evaluation. Rosenblum et al. (2021), developed a smartphone app for detecting mild cognitive impairment (MCI) in PD patients, primarily employing descriptive statistics for analysis. Weizenbaum et al. (2021), investigated smartphone cognitive assessment feasibility without ML/DL approaches, utilizing statistical modelling and correlation analyses. Garcia et al. (2022), captured action-concept markers in speech to assess PD patients' cognitive function, employing ML classifiers alongside statistical analyses. Alberts et al. (2021), characterized PD symptoms using a smartphone app, employing statistical analyses for evaluation. Ryu et al. (2022), digitized traditional cognitive tests for PD patients, employing data-driven stochastic analyses and non-parametric statistical tests for data analysis.

In conclusion, this review underlines the diverse methodologies employed in digital cognitive assessment, showcasing the potential of ML alongside alternative statistical approaches in detecting cognitive deficits in diseases such as Parkinson's.

2.3.10 Summary, unmet needs, and research opportunities

Within the scope of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, we focused on PD progression and response to medication with regards to clinical, demographic, lifestyle and genetic factors. We also reviewed the potential role of machine learning approaches and digital sensors in determining the progression of symptoms in PD as well as the response to dopaminergic medication. The results of the review alongside the derived unmet needs and arisen research opportunities are outlined in **Table 28**.

Ongoing population research has established a set of demographic and lifestyle factors that influence PD progression. There are also clearly defined PD clinical subtypes characterised by distinct clinical features that progress in temporally distinct patterns across motor, cognitive and psychiatric domains. Genetic studies delving into PD progression are attempting to find genetic markers regarding levodopa response and disease progression in terms of clinical, neuroimaging and fluid biomarkers. The review identified numerous SNPs associated with a faster decline, and others that may be protective. Machine learning approaches have proven useful in predicting PD progression and the majority of research studies target predictions of

progression outcomes at a single future time point rather than examining multiple future intervals.

Digital solutions for capturing PD symptoms in the home setting such as rest tremor, bradykinesia and rigidity, balance and cognitive decline is a fast-growing field that has demonstrated its potential role in monitoring PD progression and response to treatment.

Table 28 Unmet needs and research opportunities in PD progression and response to dopaminergic medication

Unmet needs	Research opportunities
Prediction of clinical progression and medication response	
<p>PD is a complex disease and predicting the disease course at disease onset is challenging since PD subtyping is clinical and depends on the development of symptoms along the disease course.</p>	<p>ML approaches hold the future of transforming our understanding of the complexities of PD as numerous amounts of data can be fed into the models to delineate dynamic PD subtypes</p>
<p>The exponential increase PD incidence and lack of studies predicting response to medication is producing an overburden of consultations that most healthcare systems cannot. There is thus an unmet need for increasing the efficiency of patient care</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project will use machine learning approaches to predict PD progression and response to dopaminergic treatment</p>
<p>The field of genetic research in PD is growing but an in depth understanding of the how identified gene mutations and SNPs influence PD progression and particularly response to levodopa is lacking.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project includes genetic studies for subjects that will be followed clinically and through DAT imaging</p>
Machine learning approaches	
<p>Replication of existing ML models across cohorts remains limited.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis project, the designed ML models will be replicated in open-source cohorts as well as original data derived from three clinical trials</p>
<p>Currently, the majority of the ML models use cross-sectional data and assume each PD subtype follows a fixed progression trajectory, without considering positive or negative medication effects.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis project, the designed machine learning models will use longitudinal data and take into account medication changes</p>
<p>There is a need for more ML studies that target continuous future time frames and particularly for the translation of these models into clinical practice.</p>	<p>In the AI prognosis AI-PMP clinical trial, the ML models will be used to predict when a patient needs a clinical visit with their neurologist to improve efficiency.</p>
Digital assessment of tremor, dyskinesia, bradykinesia, rigidity, balance and cognitive decline	
<p>There is a need for objective and continuous monitorization of PD motor and non-motor symptoms that can facilitate and personalize patient care.</p>	<p>The AI prognosis project plans to design and develop passive capturing solutions for remote objective and continuous monitoring of PD patients in the home setting, using non-obtrusive hardware, such as IMU data from consumer smartwatches.</p>
<p>The performance of PD patients changes dramatically in the clinic so real-life assessment</p>	

in the home environment is important for PD monitoring	
Efficient rest tremor detection and assessment is possible based on data from a single accelerometer. However, dyskinesia is technically harder to capture.	The mAI-Care app designed by the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium through a collaborative effort of movement disorder specialists, engineers and patient panels will be designed to passively capture tremor, dyskinesia, bradykinesia, rigidity, balance and cognitive decline through a smartwatch.
Studies on digital tools for the assessment of bradykinesia and rigidity in the home setting are sparse.	
The interpretation of information from wearables and body sensors in daily clinical practice is still limited and guidelines on their scope and how to use them are lacking (Fabbri et al., 2023).	In the AI-PMP clinical study, patients will be assessed by bodily sensors as well as routine clinical practice in order to start establishing bridges from investigative efforts to clinical practice and thus provide guidelines for future use.
Studies investigating the effect of treatment modifications based on wearable sensors versus or complimentary to clinician-based decision are lacking. The threshold to medication response and what this really means is lacking and continuous variables such as those provided by digital assessments may use the patient as his/her own control and thus establish a personalized threshold response.	

3 Certified technologies for PD management

Following we present the currently approved devices for monitoring PD progression and medication response (**Table 29**). The devices listed below are based on recent published reports from members of the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium (Fabbri et al., 2023). Further, to inform the study procedures on usability and acceptability, AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts have shared their patients’ experience using these devices.

Table 29 FDA Approved and CE-marked (as medical device) technologies for PD management. FDA: U.S. Food and Drug Administration.

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
PDMonitor (PD Neurotechnologies)	Bradykinesia, gait impairment and medicine compliance monitoring via 5 wearable IMU sensors in different body parts	CE marked, NICE recommendation	<p>Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with sensors where good and bad days are recorded</p> <p>Negative: Proprietary device; Number of sensors (5)</p>	In use at KCL for last 3 years. Good support to detect bradykinesia, dyskinesias, gait impairment and treatment compliance. Good overall impression of device acceptance and usefulness.
PKG (PKG Health)	Tremor, bradykinesia, immobility, sleep, dyskinesia and medicine	CE marked and Nice recommended for PD patient monitoring,	Positive: User friendly as it is wearable sensor worn as watch for 6-10 days at home.	In use at KCL for the last 8 years. Clinically useful prior to initiation of treatment, adjusting treatment, and to monitor

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
	compliance monitoring through a wrist-worn sensor	FDA cleared	Negative: Proprietary device	patients remotely and supervise any motor and non-motor fluctuations.
STAT-ON (Sense4Care)	Waist-worn device (Holter) which monitors tremor, ON, OFF, dyskinesia and freezing of gait	Class 2a medical device. Only for motor fluctuation. Only certified for EU countries	Positive: User-friendly homebased monitoring Negative: Proprietary device; transfer data from internal device memory to server may burden patients	In use in Spain in many centres and patient associations. Provides detailed information on fluctuations. Lower sensitivity for limb dyskinesias and tremor than for axial symptoms.
Kinesia 360 (Great Lakes NeuroTechnologies)	Wrist-worn sensor monitoring tremor, bradykinesia, dyskinesia and medicine compliance	Clinically validated for PD motor symptoms	Positive: Low-burden continuous remote monitoring Negative: Proprietary device	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
DynaPort (Microberts)	Waist-worn sensor for motor symptom monitoring such as gait	Clinically validated, CE marked Class 1 medical device, FDA approved	Positive: Usefulness for detecting any issue with their gait. Negative: Requires clinical supervision; hospital assessment only.	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
FeetMe Monitor Insoles (FeetMe)	Insole with pressure and motion sensor used for gait analysis by a spatio-temporal gait parameters algorithm	Clinically validated	Positive: Usefulness for detecting any issue with their gait. Negative: Requires clinical supervision; hospital assessment only.	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Opal and Mobility Lab (APDM Wearable technologies)	Wearable movement sensors (in several body parts) capturing gait and balance analysis, fall risk calculation	Produced by company listed here and approved in USA	Positive: Can be used at home and is user friendly Negative: Proprietary device; number of sensors	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Strive PD (Rune Labs) powered by Apple	Free iOS disease management application	FDA cleared and validated for	Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with an	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the

Technology name (Company)	Device and symptoms captured	FDA/CE Approval	Pros and Cons	Experience from use in clinical practice of AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners
Movement Disorders API ⁴	passively collects tremor and dyskinesia data via Apple's movement disorder API – requires a compatible Apple Watch.	symptom tracking	off-the-self smartwatch (Apple Watch) Negative: Requires a specific smartwatch (Apple watch)	AI-PROGNOSIS consortium
Parky (h2o therapeutics) powered by Apple Movement Disorders API	Similar to Strive PD - Free iOS disease management application passively collects tremor and dyskinesia data via Apple's movement disorder API – requires a compatible Apple Watch.	FDA cleared and validated for symptom tracking	Positive: User friendly, phone app in sync with an off-the-self smartwatch (Apple Watch) Negative: Requires a specific smartwatch (Apple watch)	Not in use at any of the clinical sites in the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium

4 Identified datasets of interest

In this section, we present an epitomised description of the twenty-four third party retrospective datasets that have been considered of interest by the consortium of partners for the development of the project. In the **Table 30** we present the name of the data set, a brief description of its contents, what AI-PROGNOSIS model it contributes to and the current access status.

Table 30 Multi-source datasets from consortium partners and third-parties for the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
PPMI	Observational study collecting participant reported information from people with and without PD. Longitudinal measurements for more than 1700 individuals from multiple cohorts of interest (e.g., clinically diagnosed PD, non-manifest gene carriers, healthy controls, and prodromal)	Risk, Genetic profiling, Progression, Medication response	Yes

⁴ Apple Movement Disorders API - <https://developer.apple.com/documentation/coremotion/cmmovementdisordermanager>

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
Verily Study Watch Data	Subset of the PPMI dataset. Smartwatch accelerometer data	Risk, Genetic profiling, Progression, Medication response	Yes
Swedish Biofinder	Several large, longitudinal, prospective cohorts of more than 1600 patients with mild cognitive symptoms, dementia and parkinsonian symptoms as well as cognitively healthy elderly. The subjects undergo examinations repeated bi-annually and including imaging MRI, CSF and plasma analysis, amyloid and tau PET, skin biopsies, detailed clinical assessments and neuropsychological examinations.	Risk, Progression, Medication response	No
UK Biobank	Extensive environmental, lifestyle, and genetic data on half a million participants, including HC, diagnosed PD and prodromal PD	Risk. Genetic profiling	In progress
NS-PARK	Describe the natural history of PD, and to propose patient stratification models based on PD pathophysiological mechanisms. Standardized demographic, diagnosis, motor and non-motor symptoms evaluation, and treatment information are collected, and clinical data are updated at each visit of the patient at the centre. A blood sampling is performed at baseline for genetic testing and implement an associated biocollection.	PD progression predictive modelling. Genetic profiling.	In progress
OPDC Discovery cohort	A prospective, longitudinal study that has recruited patients with early idiopathic Parkinson's Disease, healthy controls and participants at risk of PD, and also participants with RBD	Risk, Progression, Medication response	On hold
COPPADIS	N = 1000. Observational longitudinal (5y) study. Clinical and demographic data. Comparison with healthy controls (caregivers). Motor, non-motor symptoms (incl cognitive data, QoL), biochemistry and imaging data	Progression, Medication response	Yes
AMP-PD cohorts	Clinical and omics (transcriptomic, genomic, proteomic, and single nucleus brain data) data from eight unified cohorts (BioFIND, HBS, LBD, LCC, PDBP, PPMI, STEADY-PD3 and SURE-PD3) including over 10,000 participants.	Progression, Genetic profiling.	Yes
Fox Insight	Demographics, Imaging, Medical Cannabis use, Genetic	Genetic profiling	Yes
RBD-Czech	Actigraphic recording (MotionWatch, CamNtech ltd.) and confirming polysomnographic recording. 45 RBD patients, 30 with other sleep related motor disorders, 20 Healthy subjects	Risk	Yes
IRBDSG	International RBD Study Group. No publication yet	Risk	Yes

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
PRESENCE	Phase 2 trial assessing response to symptomatic treatment of Lewy body dementia (LBD). 238 patients wore actigraphy for three 2-week periods daytime sleepiness was evaluated using the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)	Progression, Medication Response	On hold
CIS-PD	Accelerometer data and severity scores for tremor, dyskinesias and ON/OFF medication status. Symptoms are reported through 30-minute interval reports	Progression, Medication response	Yes
REAL-PD IMU smartwatch data	Smartwatch accelerometer gyroscope data Smartphone accelerometer data	Progression, Medication response	Yes
MJFF Levodopa response study	Accelerometer data collected in the laboratory with ground truth labels of symptom severity during the performance of scripted motor tasks as well as wearable sensor data collected in the home setting during the performance of unscripted motor tasks.	Progression, Medication response	Yes
i-PROGNOSIS	Body tracking-based intelligent Motor Assessment Tests (iMAT) in accurately reflecting the motor skill status of PD patients. Keystroke timing and pressure data that correspond to short text excerpts typed by early PD patients and healthy controls	Progression, Medication response	Yes
LIXIPARK	Data were collected in the framework of LIXIPARK, a multicenter, randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind, parallel-group study of lixisenatide in 156 patients with early Parkinson's disease (PD) (78 on placebo, 78 on lixisenatide). It was run at 21 centers of the French NS-Park/FCRIN network. Patients with early PD (< 3 years since diagnosis) on stable symptomatic medications and without motor complications were randomised to receive subcutaneous injections of placebo or 20 µg lixisenatide once daily for 12 months, followed by a 2-month wash-out period. The primary endpoint was the change from baseline to month-12 in the MDS-UPDRS part III (motor examination) score in the ON condition.	Progression, Medication response	In progress
LEAP clinical trial	Randomized double blind placebo controlled delayed start trial that assigned patients with early PD to receive levodopa or placebo for 40 weeks followed by levodopa (delayed-start group).	Medication response, Progression	In progress
PD-MED study	Pragmatic, open-label randomised trial, including de novo PD patients who were randomly assigned between levodopa-sparing therapy (dopamine agonists or MAOBI) and levodopa alone.	Medication response	On hold

Name of the dataset	Short description	Domain	Access
Iceberg Cohort (France)	Observational, prospective, monocentric study to assess clinical features, imaging and biologic biomarkers PD patients and rate of progression compared to healthy controls and subjects at risk to develop (subjects with iRBD and subjects related to a patient with genetically confirmed PD).	Risk, Progression, medication response	No
RBDact	Home wrist actigraphy and PSG of patients .	Risk	No
NILS	Longitudinal study of PD patients baseline and follow up to 7 to 10 years	Progression, Medication response	In progress
KCH PKG data	Wearable device data contains values and percentiles of bradykiensia, imobility, sleep, dyskinesia and tremor	Progression, Medication response	In progress
Opisleep data	PD patients sleep data of PDSS, ESS daytime somnolence and demographic followup data of 20 patients	Progression, Medication response	In progress

5 Dataset harmonisation and curation

As healthcare systems generate vast volumes of heterogeneous data from diverse sources, ranging from clinical data to genomic sequences or time series, the need to harmonize this information becomes critical. Data harmonisation involves the processes of standardization, integration, and normalization, aimed at aligning disparate datasets into a coherent form.

In the context of AI-PROGNOSIS, the data harmonisation pipeline is responsible for retrieving, transforming, and harmonizing healthcare data from various sources, ultimately storing the harmonized data in a designated cloud storage. The primary objectives of this component are to ensure uniformity and compatibility of healthcare data across different sources by conforming to a common data model, such as FHIR, OMOP or a custom one, as well as to evaluate and curate the harmonized data based on stringent criteria for trustworthiness in AI applications. By incorporating AI trustworthy evaluation into the healthcare data harmonisation pipeline, the system not only ensures data homogeneity, but also takes proactive measures to evaluate, debias, and curate the data according to ethical and trustworthy AI principles formulated based on the AI-PROGNOSIS needs. This comprehensive approach enhances the system's credibility, transparency, and reliability, aligning with the highest standards of responsible AI usage in healthcare applications.

Figure 3 presents the logical view diagram of the data pipeline component, a representation focusing on the functional and conceptual aspects without delving into the details of the implementation.

Figure 3 Logical view of data pipeline components. The continuous and dotted lines show possible data flows that are to be determined.

The key functionalities of the data harmonisation pipeline include:

1. Data Retrieval:
 - The pipeline will be designed to fetch healthcare data from diverse sources, which may include cloud storage repositories or federated sources distributed across multiple healthcare providers.
 - Implements secure and efficient data retrieval mechanisms to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive healthcare information.
2. Data Harmonisation:
 - Normalization: Ensures consistent representation of data by standardizing units, codes, terminology, language and potentially measurement frequency sampling and timing.
 - Mapping: Establishes relationships between disparate data elements to align with the common data model.
3. AI Trustworthy Data Evaluation:
 - Implements checks to evaluate the trustworthiness of healthcare data based on predefined criteria, considering factors such as robustness, generalization, explainability, transparency, reproducibility, fairness, privacy preservation, and accountability.
 - Generates documentation detailing the steps taken for bias evaluation, ethical considerations and in other trustworthiness pillars.
4. Data Curation:
 - Utilizes debiasing algorithms to identify and mitigate biases present in the data, promoting fairness and preventing unintended consequences in downstream applications.
 - Potentially implements dynamic debiasing techniques that continuously adapt to evolving data patterns and emerging biases.
 - Potentially allows users to configure bias mitigation strategies based on specific requirements and ethical considerations, providing a customizable approach to bias correction.

5. Data Storage:
 - Interfaces with cloud storage solutions for both source and destination data repositories.
 - Effectively manages the storage and retrieval of harmonized data, ensuring secure and scalable operations.
6. Security and Compliance:
 - Implements access controls to safeguard sensitive healthcare data.
 - Adheres to healthcare data privacy regulations (such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation -GDPR) and industry standards to maintain compliance.
7. Scalability:
 - Designed to scale horizontally to accommodate increasing volumes of healthcare data from the initial or additional data sources.

Input and output data

The harmonisation and curation data pipeline will be designed to intake healthcare datasets derived from dedicated studies, such as those from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI), from the UK Biobank etc., but also retrospective data from clinical partners involved in the AI-PROGNOSIS project. These datasets may either be sourced directly from hospital databases or retrieved as files, and subsequently stored in a designated file server within the project's cloud infrastructure. The input data processed by this component can be of various forms, for example structured data encompassing various types, such as biomarkers, time series data (e.g., accelerometer readings), genetics data containing SNPs at specific genomic positions, demographics information and other. The output data will be harmonized and curated healthcare data, ready to be consumed by the AI models for accurate and informed modelling.

6 Conclusions

This initial report provides a domain review regarding PD risk and PD progression and medication response within the framework of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It also provides the currently approved digital technologies used today as well as an overview of the third-party datasets that have been accessed and where they will be applied in the project along with harmonisation and curation techniques.

The key messages from this report are:

- The extensive review assessing PD risk and prodromal PD based on clinical, lifestyle and demographic factors, genetic markers, machine learning models and the digital tracking of two pre-motor symptoms: (daytime somnolence and RBD) provides the current SoA and the gaps in our current knowledge. Machine learning approaches considering clinical, imaging and genetic data may help characterize the heterogeneity of PD prodromal states and thus allow for targeted intervention trials.
- The extensive review assessing PD progression and medication response considering lifestyle, demographic and clinical variables, genetic markers, machine learning and digital assessments of motor symptoms such as tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, postural instability and side effects, such as dyskinesias, as well as cognitive decline, provides an updated background of our current knowledge and also points to the unmet needs and research opportunities in monitoring PD. Machine learning approaches hold the future of transforming our understanding of the complexities of PD as numerous amounts of data can be fed into the models to delineate dynamic PD subtypes.

- There are currently seven FDA or CE approved digital technologies used to monitor PD, each with strengths and weaknesses that the AI-PROGNOSIS project will build on.
- Twelve multi-source datasets from AI-PROGNOSIS partners and third-party databases/biobanks/cohorts have been accessed by the project to date. Six will be used for disease progression and medication response models, two for PD risk and prodromal PD models, two for genetic profiling models, and two for all these objectives.
- Data from different sources has to be sanitised, debiased, munged and harmonised. The report describes the common data model to be used following established standards and clinical knowledge for the standardisation of representations of multi-site outcome assessments.

This is “living document” that will be updated regularly until the final version is delivered at month 24 of the project.

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